

Octupole deformation in neutron-deficient plutonium isotopes

Hamid Reza Francis Ayatollahzadeh

A thesis presented in partial fulfilment for the degree of
Doctor of Philosophy

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

School of Computing, Engineering, and Physical Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

United Kingdom

November 25, 2025

Abstract

The extent of the well-established region of octupole correlations in the light-actinide region has recently been brought into question by new theoretical calculations. The new calculations suggest that the region extends into the neutron deficient plutonium ($Z=94$) and curium ($Z=96$) nuclei, and to even higher values of Z . In order to test these new predictions, an experiment has been performed using the AGATA spectrometer at the Legnaro National Laboratory to study the onset of octupole correlations in previously unstudied neutron-deficient plutonium ($Z=94$) isotopes. The primary goal of the experiment was to identify excited states in the isotopes ^{232}Pu and ^{234}Pu , through the technique of γ -ray spectroscopy, for which there are presently none known. Using multi-nucleon transfer reactions, the cross sections for these reaction channels, taking prompt fission into consideration, were predicted to be 0.4 (^{232}Pu) and 0.7 mb (^{234}Pu). The nuclei of interest were populated using a beam of ^{112}Sn at an energy of 808 MeV, delivered by the Tandem-XTU and ALPI accelerators, incident on a thin ^{238}U target. The AGATA γ -ray spectrometer, in conjunction with the DANTE charged-particle detector array and the PRISMA mass spectrometer were used to select the populated nuclei of interest. The identification of low-lying negative-parity states and E1 transitions in the level schemes of the nuclei of interest would be indicative of octupole correlations. The application of AGATA-PRISMA and AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE coincidences have been performed. The observation of low intrinsic efficiency in DANTE limited the level of selectivity able to be applied to the dataset. Nevertheless, the application of TKEL selectivity to the AGATA-PRISMA coincidences has allowed the tentative identification of excited states in ^{232}Pu and ^{234}Pu for the first time. Using the identified states, tentative level schemes for the ground-state bands of the plutonium nuclei of interest have been developed. The inference of the reflection-asymmetric characters of these nuclei was not possible.

Declaration

No part of the work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other university or other institute of learning.

Acknowledgements

I would firstly like to thank my supervisor Professor John F. Smith for the opportunity to pursue a PhD, his guidance throughout, and kindness when I faced any challenges. I would also like to thank Dr. James Keatings for his regular help and patience with my questions.

I would like to thank members of the Nuclear group: Professor Robert Chapman, Professor Marcus Scheck, Dr. David O'Donnell, Dr. S. Nara Singh Bondili, Dr. Michael Bowry, and Dr. Ryan Meeten for always being friendly and welcoming, and for encouraging questions without judgement. Additionally, I would like to thank all the PhD students I have had the pleasure of working alongside: Dr. George Beeton, Dr. Gery Malanda, James Deary, Dylan White, Ben Hogg, Sulagna Dutta, and Cameron Cassells.

I would like to thank all members of the INFN-LNL nuclear group for their help during the experiment and subsequent data analysis, in particular, thanks go to Dr. Rosa maria Pérez-Vidal, Dr. Daniele Brugnara and Elia Pilotto for the many emails and video calls to help with any issues I had.

I would like to express thanks to STFC for the availability of funding for my studies.

Finally, I would like to thank my family - Mum, Baba, my sisters and their families -for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout my studies, and Roisin for always being there when I needed her and pushing me to achieve my best. I am very grateful.

Hamid

Contents

Abstract	ii
Declaration	iv
Acknowledgements	vi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Historical Context	1
1.2 Motivation For This Thesis	3
1.3 Layout of This Thesis	4
2 Nuclear Structure Theory	5
2.1 Nuclear Shell Model	5
2.1.1 Evidence For The Shell Model	5
2.1.2 The Nuclear Potential	7
2.1.3 Spin-Orbit Interaction	8
2.2 Collective Model	9
2.2.1 Nuclear Vibrations	10
2.2.2 Nuclear Rotations	11
2.3 Deformation in Nuclei	12
2.3.1 Quadrupole Deformation	13
2.4 Nilsson Model	14
2.5 Octupole Correlations in Nuclei	15
2.5.1 Early Predictions and Experimental Work	16
2.5.2 Theoretical Predictions of Octupole Correlations	17
2.5.2.1 Regions of Octupole Correlations	17

2.5.2.2	Light Actinides	18
2.5.2.3	Neutron-Rich Lanthanides	19
2.5.2.4	$N = Z = 56$ Region	19
2.5.2.5	$N = Z = 34$ Region	19
2.5.3	Properties of Nuclei with Octupole Correlations	19
2.5.4	Spectroscopy of Nuclei with Octupole Correlations	21
2.5.5	Recent Theoretical Predictions	24
2.5.6	Specific Predictions for $Z > 92$	27
3	Experimental Techniques	29
3.1	Radioactive Decay	29
3.1.1	Alpha Decay	29
3.1.2	Gamma Decay	30
3.1.3	Internal Conversion	32
3.2	Heavy-Ion Reactions	32
3.2.1	Fusion Reactions	34
3.2.2	Deep-Inelastic Collisions	34
3.2.3	Quasi-elastic Reactions	35
3.2.4	Grazing Angle	35
3.3	Interaction of γ rays with Matter	35
3.3.1	Photoelectric Effect	36
3.3.2	Compton Scattering	37
3.3.3	Pair Production	38
3.4	Interaction of Charged Particles	38
3.5	Gamma-ray Spectroscopy	40
3.5.1	Gamma-ray coincidences	40
3.5.2	Compton Suppression	41
3.5.3	Doppler Effect	42
3.5.4	Semiconductor Detectors For γ -ray Detection	42
3.5.4.1	Semiconductor Concept	42
3.5.4.2	High-Purity Germanium Detectors	44
3.5.5	Scintillator Detectors For γ -ray Detection	44
4	Experimental Setup	48
4.1	Accelerator and Ion Source	48

4.1.1	Tandem-XTU Accelerator	48
4.1.2	Acceleratore Lineare Per Ioni - ALPI	48
4.2	AGATA: Advanced Gamma Tracking Array	49
4.2.1	Motivation	49
4.2.2	AGATA Design	50
4.2.3	Data Acquisition	51
4.2.4	Pulse-Shape Analysis	53
4.2.5	Gamma-ray Tracking	54
4.2.5.1	Forward Tracking and Clusterisation	54
4.2.5.2	Back Tracking	55
4.3	DANTE	56
4.4	Lanthanum Bromide Detectors	58
4.5	PRISMA: Large Solid Angle Magnetic Spectrometer	58
4.5.1	Large-Area Micro-Channel Plate Entrance Detector	59
4.5.2	Magnetic Optics	60
4.5.3	Multi-Wire Parallel-Plate Avalanche Counter	61
4.5.4	Ionisation Chamber	61
4.6	Experimental Details	63
5	Data Analysis	64
5.1	The AGATA Spectrometer	64
5.1.1	Pre-processing Corrections	64
5.1.1.1	Initial Energy Calibration	65
5.1.1.2	Time Alignment	66
5.1.1.3	Cross-talk Correction	66
5.1.1.4	Unstable Segments	68
5.1.2	PSA Corrections	69
5.1.3	Post-PSA Corrections	69
5.1.3.1	Neutron-Damage Correction	69
5.1.3.2	Final Energy Re-calibration	71
5.1.3.3	Force Segments to Core	71
5.1.3.4	Global Time Alignment	72
5.2	PRISMA Analysis	73
5.2.1	Detector Calibration	73
5.2.1.1	MCP	73

5.2.1.2	MWPPAC	75
5.2.1.3	Ionisation Chamber	78
5.2.1.4	Side Sections	78
5.2.2	Z Identification	79
5.2.3	Time-of-Flight Calibration	80
5.2.4	Ion Identification	81
5.2.4.1	Trajectory Reconstruction	81
5.2.4.2	Optical Parameter Optimisation	83
5.2.5	Charge State Selection and Mass Identification	84
5.2.5.1	Charge State Identification	84
5.2.5.2	Aberrational Corrections	87
5.2.5.3	Mass Calibration	90
5.2.6	Doppler Correction	95
5.3	DANTE Analysis	97
5.3.1	Time Alignment of DANTE	97
5.3.2	DANTE Coincidences	99
5.4	Total Kinetic Energy Loss Selection	101
6	Results and Discussion	104
6.1	Aims of the Experiment	104
6.1.1	Rate Estimates	105
6.1.2	Systematics of Nuclei of Interest	105
6.2	AGATA Testing	109
6.2.1	Energy Resolution	109
6.2.2	Efficiency Calibration	110
6.3	AGATA γ -ray Spectra	112
6.3.1	AGATA-PRISMA Results	114
6.3.1.1	Inelastic Channel	116
6.3.1.2	One Proton Transfer Channel	119
6.3.1.3	Two-Proton Transfer Channel	122
6.3.1.4	Three-Proton Transfer Channel	124
6.3.1.5	Four-Proton Transfer Channel	125
6.3.1.6	Five-Proton Transfer Channel	129
6.3.1.7	Nuclei of Interest	130
6.3.2	AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE Results	134

6.3.3	TKEL Gated AGATA-PRISMA Results	137
6.3.3.1	TKEL selectivity for ^{236}Pu	137
6.3.3.2	TKEL selectivity for ^{234}Pu	138
6.3.3.3	TKEL Selectivity for ^{232}Pu	140
6.3.3.4	Rotational Alignments for Nuclei of Interest	141
6.3.3.5	TKEL Evolution	142
7	Summary	146
	Appendices	149
A	Analysis Codes and Configuration Files	150
A.1	AGATA Analysis	150
A.1.1	The Preprocessing Actor	150
A.1.2	The post-PSA Actor	151
A.2	PRISMA Analysis	152
A.2.1	Configuration Files	152
A.2.2	Data Sorting	153
A.3	DANTE Analysis	154
A.3.1	Time Alignment	154
A.4	Merging	155
B	In-beam AGATA-PRISMA Spectra	157
B.1	Projectile-like Spectra	157
B.1.1	tin - 0p channel	157
B.1.2	indium - 1p transfer channel	158
B.1.3	cadmium - 2p transfer channel	159
B.1.4	silver - 3p transfer channel	160
B.1.5	palladium - 4p transfer channel	161
B.1.6	rhodium - 5p transfer channel	162

List of Figures

2.1	The two-neutron separation energy as a function of the neutron number. The figure is taken from Ref. [12].	6
2.2	$E(2^+)$ transition energies against A for the lowest states of even- Z , even- N nuclei, where the lines connect sequences of isotopes. This figure was taken from Ref. [12].	10
2.3	The different projections of j along the symmetry axis for the $f_{7/2}$ orbital for varying value of β parameter. Figure taken from Ref. [13].	15
2.4	The nuclear chart displaying octupole magic numbers (red lines) and surrounding regions (red circles). Also indicated are the spherical magic numbers (black lines).	17
2.5	A diagram showing the projections of the nuclear spin. As indicated, the aligned angular momentum i_x is shown as a projection of the spin on the rotation axis x . Here, K is the projection of the total angular momentum on the symmetry axis z and ω is the rotational frequency. This figure is taken from Ref. [17].	22
2.6	Aligned angular momenta for radium isotopes with $220 \leq A \leq 228$. The plots on the left show aligned angular momentum, i_x , as a function of rotational frequency for positive-parity (black circles) and negative-parity (white circles). The right hand plots show the difference between the positive and negative parity band levels as a function of angular momentum. Here, the dashed lines indicate $\Delta i_x = 3$ and $\Delta i_x = 0$. This figure is taken from Ref. [36].	23
2.7	The parity splitting between positive-parity and negative-parity bands (left) and rotational frequency ratios (right) as a function of angular momentum for a series of radium isotopes. This figure is taken from Ref. [79].	24
2.8	A comparison between a theoretical model and experimental results for even-even nuclei with $Z \geq 8$. Here the circles represent experimental data and the triangles represent the theoretical predictions. This figure was taken from Ref. [80].	25

2.9	Reflection asymmetry across the nuclear chart. Predicted octupole deformed nuclei are shown in circles and stars with the legend indicating the number of theoretical energy density functionals that predict octupole deformation. The green solid line indicates the currently known nuclei. This figure was taken from Ref. [10].	26
2.10	Potential energy surface plots for two theoretical models. The colour code indicates the energies in MeV up to 10 MeV. This figure was taken from Ref. [11].	27
3.1	Several impact parameter, b , values showing different potential trajectories, leading to different reactions. The grazing collisions take place when b is close to b_0 . This figure is taken from Ref. [85].	33
3.2	The reaction cross section plotted against the orbital angular momentum. Here the different regions for fusion (σ_F), deep-inelastic scattering (σ_{DIC}), and quasi-elastic scattering (σ_{qe}) are indicated. This figure is taken from Ref. [86].	33
3.3	The three main interaction mechanisms of photons with matter as a function of the atomic number, Z , of the absorber and energy of the incident photon. This figure is taken from Ref. [93].	36
3.4	Energy loss of an alpha particle with energy of the order of MeV along its path in matter. This figure is taken from Ref. [94].	39
3.5	Pulse height spectra from a ^{60}Co source. (a) Normal spectrum from a central germanium detector. (b) Application of additional scintillation detectors in anti-coincidence mode. This figure is taken from Ref. [94].	41
3.6	Representations of the addition of impurities to a silicon crystal creating donor (a) and acceptor (b) states. This figure is taken from Ref. [94].	43
3.7	The three common shapes of coaxial crystals. Taken from Ref. [94]	45
3.8	A comparison of two γ -ray spectra for the detection of natural background as measured by NaI(Tl) and HPGe detectors for one million seconds. This figure is taken from Ref. [100].	46
4.1	The three different crystal geometries of the AGATA spectrometer that together form a triple cluster. The bottom right diagram shows the depth of each crystal with the dashed lines indicated the six segments of the crystals. Dimensions shown are in millimeters [8].	51
4.2	The AGATA crystal segmentation into 6 sectors consisting each of 6 segments. [8].	52
4.3	A schematic representation of the layout of the AGATA data acquisition system, taken from Ref. [8]	53
4.4	A schematic representation of the backtracking process including the interaction points i , j , and k taken from Ref. [116, 117].	56

4.5	A picture of the DANTE detector array mounted at the target position taken during this experiment, with three MCP detectors in place within the holder. Also shown are thin sheets of aluminium placed across half of the face of the MCPs in order to reduce the high count rates experienced in the experiment.	57
4.6	A picture of nine LaBr ₃ (Ce) detectors around the target position at INFN-LNL. Also pictured are the target chamber and AGATA crystals for reference.	58
4.7	A schematic representation of the PRISMA magnetic spectrometer, with each section labelled, taken from Ref. [123, 124]. The distances given are not to scale.	59
4.8	Top: A schematic of the micro-channel plate detector from above, taken from Ref. [125]. The carbon foil centre is at 25cm from the target. Bottom: A picture of the MCP, taken from Ref. [125].	60
4.9	A picture of the PRISMA magnetic spectrometer in place at INFN-LNL. Here the focal plane detectors are indicated by A (MWPPAC) and B (IC), taken from Refs. [129, 130].	62
5.1	Diagram of the workflow of the Narval actors. This figure is taken from Refs. [129, 130]. . .	65
5.2	Time signal peak for segment 15 of crystal 06A before (red) and after (black) the online time alignment.	66
5.3	The segment sum energy peaks for the $E_\gamma = 1332.5$ -keV transition from a ⁶⁰ Co source with increasing segment fold. For every increasing fold the peak position shifts by 2.32 keV and the peak width decreases by 0.5 keV. This test was done using the AGATA detector crystal S001 in a single test cryostat. The percentages provide a fold distribution, e.g. only 38% of the detected γ rays contribute to the two-fold photopeak. This figure was taken from Ref. [134].	67
5.4	Segment 15 of crystal 00A before (red) and after (black) the neutron-damage correction process has been applied. The full-energy peaks of the 1173-keV γ ray and 1332-keV γ ray are shown from a ⁶⁰ Co source run performed after the experiment. Here, a gain of 1.25 was applied during the correction process and so the 1332-keV peak is seen at channel 1665. . .	70
5.5	A γ -ray energy spectrum from the decay of a ¹⁵² Eu source showing the 1408-keV peak from a segment of crystal 00A for multiple stages of the correction process. Here, the signal after the neutron-damage correction process has been applied is shown in red and the black signal represents the result after the neutron-damage correction and final energy re-calibration have been applied.	71
5.6	Time signal peaks for segment 0 in crystal 00A, compared to all other segments for $\sim 6\%$ of the dataset after the global time alignment process has been completed. Here the dotted line indicates channel 500.	72

5.7	Top: Raw un-calibrated two-dimensional MCP matrix. As shown the red line indicates the gate applied to remove unwanted events. Bottom: Calibrated two-dimensional MCP matrix showing the cross close to the expected reference points used for calibration.	74
5.8	Left: Raw x_l signal spectrum for segment 4 of the MWPPAC. The red lines shown indicate the threshold lines used to constrain the data. Right: Raw cathode signal spectrum for segment 4 of the MWPPAC. Threshold lines are set loosely here.	76
5.9	Calibrated x_{FP} distribution. Here a peak can be seen at the centre of each segment from the short circuiting of the central wires.	77
5.10	The application of a gate on the matrix of $x_r + x_l$ vs. $x_{cathode}$. This allows the removal of events arising from noise.	77
5.11	Energy loss for four sections of the IC. The four sections represent the full depth of the chamber with sections A, B, C, and D shown for the second row of 10 segments.	78
5.12	Energy loss spectra for four side sections. Thresholds are used to exclude noise and the resulting signals are used to veto events.	79
5.13	Energy loss in the first two IC layers plotted against the total energy. The atomic numbers of the reaction products are labelled in red.	80
5.14	Energy loss measured in the first two layers of the IC plotted against the total energy of the reaction products. Here the yellow shape indicates the projectile-like ions that result from multi-nucleon transfer. The red shape indicates reaction products measured arising from fission of the target-like uranium ions. A colour scale has been set for the z-axis to emphasizes the different structures.	81
5.15	Time-of-flight plotted against the x -position at the focal plane as measured by the MWPPAC. The different sections of the focal-plane detector are visible along with the estimated ToF value.	82
5.16	The difference between optimised and non-optimised optical parameters. (A) and (C) show the plot of the mass-to-charge ratio against the x_{FP} of the MWPPAC, (A) demonstrates poor optimisation and (C) shows improved optimisation. (B) and (D) show the total measured ionisation chamber energy against the product $\rho\beta$. Here (B) shows the result of poor optimisation and (D) good optimisation.	85
5.17	$Z = 50$ (top panel) and $Z = 48$ (bottom panel) gated matrices of the total IC energy against $\rho\beta$ allowing selection of the individual charge states.	86
5.18	$Z = 50$ gated matrix of the total IC energy against $\rho\beta$ with applied two-dimensional gates to select the charge states from $q = 39$ to $q = 31$, moving left to right. This is a result of the summation of all of the data in order to demonstrate the charge states.	87

5.19	Top row: A/q against the x -position of the MCP before (left) and after (right) the aberrational corrections are applied. Middle row: A/q ratio against the Y-position of the MCP before (left) and after (right) the aberrational corrections have been applied. Bottom row: A/q ratio against the X-position of the MWPPAC before (left) and after (right) the aberrational corrections have been applied.	89
5.20	A $Z = 50$ gated A/q distribution before (red) and after (blue) aberrational corrections have been applied.	90
5.21	A Zq -gated A/q distribution before (red) and after (blue) the final linear calibration has been applied. Assigned mass (A) values are labelled for most prominent peaks and masses in both distributions for reference.	91
5.22	Calibrated Z -gated mass distributions for the observed projectile-like nuclei.	92
5.23	Two-dimensional projection of the mass distribution as a function X_{FP} of the MWPPAC gated on $Z = 48$	94
5.24	Measured centroid values for the $Z = 50$ $A = 112$ mass peak as a function of the run number.	94
5.25	Top panel: Non Doppler-corrected spectrum of the measured γ -ray energies as a function of the angle of emission. Bottom panel: Doppler-corrected spectrum of the measured γ -ray energies as a function of the angle of emission. Both spectra are gated on the projectile $^{112}_{50}\text{Sn}$ and show the energy of the $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ ground-state transition.	96
5.26	Timestamp difference between the raw timestamp of the AGATA spectrometer and that of DANTE.	98
5.27	Timestamp difference peak between the AGATA spectrometer and DANTE after the alignment process has been completed.	98
5.28	Time-of-flight difference between the MCP at the entrance of the PRISMA spectrometer and the MCP of DANTE opposite the entrance of the PRISMA spectrometer. The top panel shows an example of the difference for a run in which PHA digitisers were used and the bottom panel shows a run for which the digitizers with PSD firmware were used.	100
5.29	The difference in time-of-flight between the MCP at the entrance to the PRISMA spectrometer and the MCP of DANTE opposite the entrance to PRISMA against the total kinetic energy loss (TKEL) measured in the ionisation chamber of the PRISMA spectrometer.	101
5.30	The total kinetic energy loss distribution for the reaction $^{112}\text{Sn} + ^{238}\text{U}$ in the top panel. The bottom three panels show the results before (top) and after gating on the selections denoted by 'A' and 'B' on the top panel. It should be noted that the top panel is not calibrated to give accurate TKEL values.	102

6.1	Energies of states in the ground-state bands of $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ up to $16\hbar$, plotted against the mass number, A	106
6.2	Total angular momentum along the rotation axis for the positive-parity (black) and negative-parity (red) bands of $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ against the rotational frequency.	107
6.3	The energy difference between the midpoint of positive-parity states and the adjacent negative-parity states for the $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ nuclei as a function of the spin.	108
6.4	Rotational frequency ratios for the $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ nuclei, calculated from the known level energies against the spin.	109
6.5	The ratio of the FWHM and the measured energy centroids against the measured energy centroid for three data sets. The black points and fitted line indicate the energy resolution curve using data from a ^{152}Eu source run. The red and blue points indicate the same measurement using the in-beam AGATA-PRISMA-gated γ -ray spectra for ^{112}Sn and ^{238}U after a Doppler correction has been applied, respectively.	110
6.6	The relative detection efficiency as a function of measured γ -ray energy using combined data from ^{152}Eu and ^{133}Ba source runs. Fitted line of best fit was performed using the RadWare analysis software.	112
6.7	A γ -ray energy spectrum for the core electrode and after the tracking algorithm has been applied.	113
6.8	(a) A histogram showing the time difference between the timestamps of events in AGATA and PRISMA. The shaded regions indicate the gates used to identify the origins of the peaks. (b) A γ -ray spectrum in coincidence with the pink shaded region. (c) A γ -ray spectrum in coincidence with the blue shaded region.	115
6.9	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{112}Sn with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 50$, from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 112$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through PRISMA has been applied.	116
6.10	A partial level scheme for ^{112}Sn showing the transitions observed in this work.	117
6.11	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{238}U with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 50$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 112$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the unobserved binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.	118
6.12	A partial level scheme for ^{238}U showing the transitions observed in this work. The $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$ and $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ transitions have dashed lines to indicate they were not observed in this work.	119

6.13	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{112}In with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 49$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 112$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	120
6.14	Partial level scheme for ^{112}In showing the transitions observed in this work.	121
6.15	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{238}Np with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 49$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 112$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.	121
6.16	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{110}Cd with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 110$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	122
6.17	A partial level scheme for ^{110}Cd showing the transitions observed in this work.	123
6.18	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{240}Pu with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 110$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.	124
6.19	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{109}Ag with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 47$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 109$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	124
6.20	A partial level scheme for ^{109}Ag showing the transitions observed in this work.	126
6.21	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{241}Am with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 47$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 109$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.	126
6.22	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{106}Pd with the selection of $Z = 46$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 106$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	127
6.23	A partial level scheme for ^{106}Pd showing the transitions observed in this study.	128

6.24	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{244}Cm with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 46$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 106$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.	128
6.25	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{105}Rh with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 45$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 105$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	129
6.26	Partial level scheme for ^{105}Rh showing the transitions observed in this work.	130
6.27	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{245}Bk after with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 45$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 105$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.	131
6.28	The γ -ray singles spectrum with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 116$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	131
6.29	Partial level scheme for ^{116}Cd showing the transitions observed in this work.	132
6.30	The γ -ray singles spectrum with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 118$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	132
6.31	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{232}Pu after with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 118$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.	133
6.32	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{234}Pu after with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 116$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.	134

- 6.33 Singles γ -ray spectra for ^{236}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{114}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner. (a) Spectrum with a condition on the detection of ^{114}Cd in PRISMA, a Doppler correction for the binary partner, and with a gate on the time coincidence between AGATA and PRISMA. (b) Same as (a), but also requiring that a signal is detected in DANTE within a time coincidence between DANTE and AGATA-PRISMA. (c) Same as (b) with an additional condition on the ToF versus TKEL distribution selecting only the target-like reaction products resulting from multi-nucleon transfer. 135
- 6.34 Singles γ -ray spectra for ^{234}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{116}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner. (a) AGATA γ -ray spectrum with a condition on the detection of ^{116}Cd in PRISMA, a Doppler correction for the binary partner, and with a gate on the time coincidence between AGATA and PRISMA. (b) Same as (a), but also requiring that a signal is detected in DANTE within a time coincidence between DANTE and AGATA-PRISMA. (c) Same as (b) with an additional condition on the ToF versus TKEL distribution selecting only the target-like reaction products resulting from multi-nucleon transfer. 136
- 6.35 (a) TKEL distribution for ^{114}Cd that is gated on to obtain the coincident γ -ray energy spectra. (b) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{236}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{114}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner when selecting all of the distribution in (a). (c) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{236}Pu after the gate shown in (a) is applied. Only the resulting γ -ray energy spectra are re-binned here to identify transitions. 138
- 6.36 (a) TKEL distribution for ^{116}Cd that is gated on to obtain the coincident γ -ray energy spectra. (b) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{234}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{116}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner when selecting all of the distribution in (a). (c) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{234}Pu after the gate shown in (a) is applied. Only the resulting γ -ray energy spectra are re-binned here to identify transitions. 140
- 6.37 Tentative level scheme for ^{234}Pu using transitions identified from the AGATA-PRISMA, TKEL-gated γ -ray spectrum. Only transitions in the ground-state band are identified. Here, the values of x and y are the energies of the $J^\pi = (4^+)$ and $J^\pi = (2^+)$ states, respectively, which could not be identified in this work. 141
- 6.38 (a) TKEL distribution for ^{118}Cd that is gated on to obtain the coincident γ -ray energy spectra. (b) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{232}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{118}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner when selecting all of the distribution in (a). (c) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{232}Pu after the gate shown in (a) is applied. Only the resulting γ -ray energy spectra are re-binned here to identify transitions. 142

6.39	Tentative level scheme for ^{232}Pu using transitions identified from the AGATA-PRISMA, TKEL-gated γ -ray spectrum. Only transitions in the ground-state band are identified. Here, the values of x and y are the energies of the $J^\pi = (4^+)$ and $J^\pi = (2^+)$ states, respectively, which could not be identified in this work.	143
6.40	Total angular momentum along the rotation axis for ground-state bands in $^{232,234,236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ as a function of rotational frequency. In the case of $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ the data points are calculated using the transition energies identified in this work.	144
6.41	A plot showing the TKEL distributions for the series of observed cadmium nuclei ranging from $^{105-118}\text{Cd}$	145
B.1	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{113}Sn with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 50$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 113$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	157
B.2	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{111}Sn with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 50$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 111$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	158
B.3	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{111}In with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 49$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 111$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	158
B.4	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{113}In with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 49$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 113$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	159
B.5	The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{109}Cd with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 109$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	159
B.6	The γ -ray singles spectrum with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 111$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.	160

- B.7 The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{108}Ag with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 47$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 108$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied. 160
- B.8 The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{110}Ag with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 47$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 110$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied. 161
- B.9 The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{105}Pd with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 46$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 105$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied. 161
- B.10 The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{107}Pd with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 46$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 107$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied. 162
- B.11 The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{104}Rh with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 45$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 104$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied. 162
- B.12 The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{106}Rh with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 45$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 106$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied. 163

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Historical Context

One of the first discoveries in modern nuclear physics was made in 1896 when Henri Becquerel identified that uranium salts emitted a new form of radiation, different to the X-rays previously discovered by Röntgen, which he labelled as uranic rays. Today it is understood that these rays are the emission of beta and gamma radiation as the uranium isotopes decayed. Continuing research into this new form of radiation led Marie and Pierre Curie to the discovery of additional elements, including polonium and radium, which also emit radiation spontaneously. This term was coined *radioactivity* and its discovery began a period labelled as the “golden age of nuclear physics” [1]. In 1902, Ernest Rutherford developed the understanding of radioactivity by determining that after the emission of a spontaneous event, such as the emission of α or β particles, a nucleus of a different element was produced. This was later confirmed by Frederick Soddy who discovered that naturally-radioactive elements had a number of different isotopes with similar chemical properties [2]. In 1932 James Chadwick discovered the neutron by directing alpha particles at a ${}^9\text{Be}$ nucleus, giving ${}^{12}\text{C}$ and one neutron. The neutrons produced were identified by measuring how they scattered from paraffin wax. Paraffin has a high proton density, therefore the mass of the incidence radiation can be inferred by measuring the energy ranges of the scattered protons. It was found that the radiation had similar mass to that of the proton, but with no net charge [3]. This result provided a significant contribution to the understanding of the structure of a nucleus where, previously, it was thought that the atom only contained protons and electrons [4]. In the same year, Cockcroft and Walton were the first to split the atomic nucleus, transforming a lithium atom into helium atoms using an accelerated proton beam. Then in 1938 Hahn and Meitner would discover that when bombarding uranium with neutrons, barium is produced. This provided the first identification of

the occurrence of nuclear fission.

It was not until the 1949 that Goeppert-Mayer developed the first description of the nuclear shell model with added spin-orbit interaction [1, 5]. This has since provided a valuable understanding of the nuclear shape and the behaviour of nuclear matter. This model describes the structure of nuclei as protons and neutrons, collectively labelled as nucleons, within energy levels, or shells, that obey the Pauli exclusion principle. It was found that at specific nucleon numbers where the shells are filled, there is a large energy gap to the next highest energy level. The nucleon numbers in these cases are known as *magic numbers* and nuclei possessing nucleons with these numbers are shown to be especially stable. The shell model is able to be applied for nuclei near closed shells to describe the structure of nuclei. However, the application of this model to describe all nuclei begins to break down when moving away from closed shells. Therefore, in order to understand nuclei that have nucleon numbers far away from closed shells, it was required that new theoretical models were developed. The collective model was introduced to describe the nucleus as a group of nucleons that move together and can be modelled as a liquid drop which displays excitations through vibration or rotation of the collective matter [6]. Nuclei that are described by this model are deformed and can take a non-spherical shape. The majority of nuclei are found to display some sort of deformation with the most popular being that of quadrupole deformation, leading to a *prolate*-shaped or *oblate*-shaped nucleus. For more exotic nuclei, a nucleus can display octupole deformation. This is when the nucleus takes on an asymmetric shape, similar to that of a pear. Analogous to the magic numbers described for nuclei with closed shells, there are numbers of nucleons at which maximal *octupole* correlations in nuclei are expected. These so-called *octupole magic numbers* are 34, 56, 88, and 134. It is found that nuclei possessing nucleon numbers close to these values are only found in particular areas of the nuclear chart. Currently, the largest amount of experimental evidence for octupole deformation comes from the actinide region, which lies close to the $Z = 88$ and $N = 134$ magic numbers. Historically, this region of the nuclear chart has been difficult to reach experimentally due to the lack of beam and target combinations and the propensity to fission. Only with the advancement of specialised techniques and detection systems has the study of these nuclei been possible.

Recent advancements in detector fabrication have led to the introduction of segmented detector crystals. The use of these crystals in γ -ray spectroscopy allows improved detection efficiency due to the reconstruction of γ -ray events which scatter between detector crystals. The detection of the positions of the γ -ray interactions within the crystal are measured, from which an algorithm is applied to determine the correct interaction sequence and correlate events occurring from a single γ -ray across multiple crystals to recover the full energy of the γ ray. There are currently two detector arrays that employ this segmentation technique. These are

GRETINA/GRETA and, of interest in this thesis, the Advanced Gamma Tracking Array (AGATA) [7–9]. As part of a European collaboration, the construction of the AGATA 4π γ -ray detector array using segmented HPGe crystals was proposed in the early 2000s. Currently, the AGATA detector array is based at INFN Legnaro National Laboratory (LNL) with a solid angle coverage of $\sim 1\pi$. The use of a reaction that can populate nuclei at the limits of in-beam spectroscopy, combined with the AGATA detector array provides a method to identify nuclei that previously have not been studied.

1.2 Motivation For This Thesis

Currently, the actinide region hosts the best experimental evidence for octupole deformation to date with examples of radium and thorium isotopes, amongst others, displaying key characteristics of nuclei with octupole deformation. There is, however, a limited amount of experimental evidence for octupole deformation in actinide nuclei with $Z > 92$ despite strong theoretical evidence. Theoretical models have been used by Cao *et al.* [10] to predict regions of octupole deformations in even-even nuclei across the nuclear chart. Of interest is the neutron-deficient actinide region which provides strong evidence for octupole deformation but is beyond the boundary of experimentally discovered nuclei. More specifically, even-even isotopes of plutonium ($Z = 94$) nuclei are predicted by a number of energy density functionals to have octupole deformation. These nuclei are also the focus of theoretical predictions by Nomura *et al.* [11], with potential energy surfaces plotted for plutonium nuclei with $224 \leq A \leq 234$. Here a rapid increase in non-zero octupole deformation parameter values is predicted as A decreases. Currently, however, plutonium nuclei with $A < 136$ have not been identified through in-beam spectroscopy, due to the experimental limits previously explained, providing no experimental evidence to support the theoretical predictions of octupole deformation explained above.

In this work, an experiment conducted at LNL to study the neutron-deficient isotopes $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ using in-beam spectroscopy for the first time is presented. The experiment used a combination of the AGATA spectrometer, the PRISMA large solid-angle magnetic separator, and the DANTE detector array. In order to populate the reaction products of interest multi-nucleon transfer (MNT) reactions were used due to the inability of accessing these nuclei through other methods such as fusion evaporation due to the insufficient beam and target combinations. The AGATA detector array was used to implement the novel γ -ray tracking technique to take advantage of the increased detection efficiency when compared to conventional γ -ray detection methods. The PRISMA spectrometer was used to select the projectile-like MNT reaction products and the DANTE detector array was used to detect the target-like reaction products.

1.3 Layout of This Thesis

This thesis consists of seven chapters. The first chapter provides an introduction, giving historical context to the work described later. Chapter two gives the theoretical background and discusses octupole correlations in the nuclear chart. Chapter three discusses the experimental techniques that have been used including the methods of radioactive decay, details of heavy-ion reactions, interactions of radiation with matter and explanations of γ -ray spectroscopy techniques. Chapter four describes the experimental setup, including the details of the individual detectors and specific settings unique to this experiment. Chapter five explains the steps of the data analysis for each detector array described. Chapter six provides the results of the analysis and discusses the impact of these results. Finally, Chapter seven summarises the main points included in this thesis and provides a future outlook.

Chapter 2

Nuclear Structure Theory

2.1 Nuclear Shell Model

2.1.1 Evidence For The Shell Model

Historically, nuclear physicists have struggled to describe the microscopic properties of nuclei due to the complexity of the interactions between nucleons. An initial ideology was to describe the nucleus as a liquid drop with the mass of an atomic nucleus, M , given by the difference between the rest mass of the nucleons Zm_p , Nm_n , and the binding energy, E_B , of the nucleus as,

$$M = Zm_p + Nm_n - \frac{E_B(N, Z)}{c^2}. \quad (2.1)$$

To approximate the binding energy, the semi-empirical mass formula (SEMF) can be used. This formula introduces different terms derived from experiment which relate to properties of the nucleus. The SEMF gives good approximations of nuclear masses and the majority of empirically measured binding energies. Discrepancies are found between the results of the SEMF and observed experimental results for nuclei around particular nucleon numbers. For this reason, the introduction of a new model to represent the nucleus was required, leading to the introduction of the nuclear shell model.

The shell model arises from the fact that nucleons in the nucleus, like electrons in an atom, appear to form shell structures where a certain number of neutrons or protons can occupy an orbital. When a shell is filled completely by a specific amount of nucleons it is labelled as a *closed shell*. This specific number of nucleons

is referred to as a *magic number* and nuclei possessing proton or neutron magic numbers (or both) are experimentally shown to be more stable. The experimentally observed nucleon magic numbers are 2, 8, 20, 28, 50, 82, and 126. Currently, 126 is only a magic number for neutrons. Further evidence for additional stability in nuclei with nucleons near magic numbers is presented by a plot of the two-neutron separation energy as a function of the neutron number. This is shown in Figure 2.1. Here, it is seen that the energy required to remove two neutrons from the nucleus increases drastically around the magic numbers. This is also the case for the removal of protons from the nucleus. Nuclei near closed shells can be described with good accuracy by treating the nucleus as an inert core with the additional nucleons described as valence particles or holes. When moving to nucleon numbers in the mid-shell region, it is found that the shell model explanation of the nucleus breaks down due to the interaction of valence nucleons with one another. Moreover, far from shell closures, i.e. with increasing numbers of valence nucleons, other models are needed to explain the microscopic behaviour of the nucleus (see Section 2.3 - 2.4).

Figure 2.1: The two-neutron separation energy as a function of the neutron number. The figure is taken from Ref. [12].

.Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

2.1.2 The Nuclear Potential

In order to reproduce the magic numbers the nuclear potential needs to be modelled or approximated. The nuclear shell model attempts to approximate the potential felt by nucleons within a nucleus as a central potential that is created by all other nucleons. This is briefly explained here. After this, the models for the nuclear potential are compared.

Due to the complexity of the interactions between all nucleons the two-body problem was introduced to describe the interaction as a central, mean potential rather than nucleons interacting with one another individually [13]. The Hamiltonian, \hat{H} , for the mean field case takes the form,

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{i=1}^A \left(\frac{\hat{p}_i^2}{2m_i} + U(\hat{r}_i) + V_{i,\text{res}} \right), \quad (2.2)$$

where \hat{p}_i is the momentum of a nucleon labelled i in the potential, m_i is the mass of the nucleon, $U(\hat{r}_i)$ is the potential experienced by the nucleon with coordinates r , and V_{res} is the residual interaction contribution. It is then inferred that the nucleons occupy single-particle states which are bound to the nucleus via the central potential. The goal of an independent-particle model is to accurately represent the motion of the individual nucleons within the central nuclear potential.

Attempting to describe the nuclear potential as a simple square well is problematic due to the levels in a square well being of equal energy. The magic numbers of 2, 8, and 20 are reproduced by this potential, but, for higher nucleon numbers, the prediction from the potential well is not accurate. Additionally, the square well potential fails to model the edge of potential which, when considering the observed shape of nuclei, shows an edge which is not sharp and describes the nuclear charge and matter distribution well. To account for the inaccuracy of the square well near the edge of the potential, another option is introduced called the *harmonic oscillator* potential. By neglecting the residual interaction term in Equation 2.2, it can be assumed that the one-body potential can be described as a harmonic oscillator given by

$$V(r_i) = \frac{1}{2} \mu_i \omega_0^2 r_i^2, \quad (2.3)$$

where r_i is the position, μ is the reduced mass, and ω_0 is the frequency for a nucleon, i [14]. This potential can be expanded into three dimensions with degenerate energies between nucleons existing in the same shell. Using this method the magic numbers 2, 8, and 20 are reproduced. The harmonic oscillator potential is

inaccurate at low- r values despite its realistic results near the nuclear edge. Because the harmonic oscillator does not accurately approximate the nuclear potential and the experimentally observed results, the Woods-Saxon potential was introduced. The formula to describe the potential felt by a nucleon in the Woods-Saxon potential is given by

$$V(r) = \frac{-V_0}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{r-R}{a}\right)}, \quad (2.4)$$

where V_0 represents the depth of the potential well that a nucleus must overcome in order to be ejected from the nucleus, a is the skin thickness of the potential well, r is the distance to the centre of the nucleus from a nucleon of interest, and R is the radius of the nucleus given by,

$$R = R_0 A^{1/3} \text{ fm}, \quad (2.5)$$

with $R_0 = 1.25 \text{ fm}$ [13].

2.1.3 Spin-Orbit Interaction

The Woods-Saxon potential reproduces the observed magic numbers up to 20, but it does not reproduce the higher magic numbers. For this reason, an additional term was introduced to account for the higher magic numbers. Analogous to atomic electrons, nucleons obey quantum mechanical statistics and have quantum numbers that govern them. Electrons are governed by four quantum numbers, namely; N (principal quantum number), L (angular quantum number), M (magnetic quantum number), and S (spin quantum number). The four atomic quantum numbers are also inherent in nucleons, with the angular quantum number and the intrinsic spin having different allowed values in this case. The interaction between the intrinsic spin and angular momentum quantum numbers leads to a new quantum number, the total angular momentum quantum number, J , defined as,

$$J = L + S. \quad (2.6)$$

Since L can only take integer values and S is always $\pm\frac{1}{2}$ when dealing with nucleons, the allowed values of the total angular momentum are $L + S \leq J \leq |L - S|$ [14]. These allowed values of the total angular momentum determine the maximum number of allowed nucleons for each orbital shell, using the rule that if $J = \frac{x}{2}$ then the total number of nucleons allowed in the orbital is $x + 1$. Analogous to atomic physics, an additional spin-orbit interaction term, V_{so} , is introduced which is given by,

$$V_{so} \propto \frac{dV}{dr} L \cdot S. \quad (2.7)$$

Here, the product of the nucleon's spin angular momentum, S , and orbital angular momentum, L , provides the splitting of the levels within the potential. Combining Equations 2.4 and 2.7 gives,

$$U(\hat{r}_i) = \frac{-V_0}{1 + \exp(\frac{r-R}{a})} + V_{so}. \quad (2.8)$$

In atomic physics the spin-orbit term causes the fine structure of spectral lines. When applying this term to nucleon orbitals it causes a force to be felt by a given particle depending on the alignment of its spin and orbital angular momentum, which can be aligned parallel or anti-parallel [15]. Therefore, from Equation 2.6, nucleons occupying states with different values of J will experience different forces and thus possess different energies [12]. For example, the $1g$ ($\ell = 4$) level is split into the $1g_{\frac{9}{2}}$ and $1g_{\frac{7}{2}}$ levels, with occupations of 10 and 8 nucleons, respectively. This splitting forms the $N = Z = 50$ shell gap. Applying this correction for all nucleon numbers, the Woods-Saxon potential with the added spin-orbit interaction can reproduce all the experimentally observed magic numbers for stable nuclei.

2.2 Collective Model

The nuclear shell model accurately calculates the shell closures when using the Woods-Saxon potential with the added spin-orbit interaction. The shell model is also useful in determining other experimentally observed phenomena, but begins to break down in some instances. It is experimentally observed that the majority of even-even nuclei away from magic numbers have $J^\pi = 2^+$ states that are at energies lower than the energy that would result from the breaking of pairs of nucleons [13]. The first $J^\pi = 2^+$ state in the majority of even-even nuclei is the lowest excited state. These phenomena, amongst others, are examples of properties that cannot be described by the shell model. The observables can be attributed to the contributions of many nucleons to the characteristics of the nucleus, and are referred to as *collective* properties. Figure 2.2 shows an example by plotting the energies of the $J^\pi = 2^+$ states against A . Excluding the regions around closed shells, the change in the excitation energy does not vary significantly for isotopic chains of nuclei.

For even- Z , even- N nuclei with $A < 150$, the first excited states are observed at an energy of the order of 1 MeV. For nuclei in the range $150 < A < 190$ and $A > 230$ the energy of the lowest excited state is significantly lower than that for nuclei near closed shells with $E(2_1^+)$ of the order of 100 keV. The difference between these two regions indicates that there are two distinctive types of excitation for nuclei, one where

$A < 150$ and the other when nuclei lie the range $150 < A < 190$ and $A > 230$ [13]. A nucleus displaying collectivity can have excitations that are modelled by thinking of the nucleus as a liquid drop which can have vibrational and/or rotational behaviours and therefore models based on these processes are applied to describe collective excitations in the respective ranges.

Figure 2.2: $E(2^+)$ transition energies against A for the lowest states of even- Z , even- N nuclei, where the lines connect sequences of isotopes. This figure was taken from Ref. [12].

2.2.1 Nuclear Vibrations

To describe nuclear motion under collective vibration, the nucleus is treated as a liquid drop vibrating at a high frequency. A point on the nuclear surface labelled $R(t)$ with coordinates (θ, ϕ) can be described by,

$$R(t) = R_{av} + \sum_{\lambda \geq 1} \sum_{\mu = -\lambda}^{+\lambda} \alpha_{\lambda\mu}(t) Y_{\lambda\mu}(\theta, \phi), \quad (2.9)$$

where $\alpha_{\lambda\mu}(t)$ gives the amplitude of each component of the spherical harmonics $Y_{\lambda\mu}$, and R_{av} is the average nuclear radius [16]. The vibrational excitation results in a change in the shape of the nucleus without a change in the density, with the excitation of the nucleus displaying modes which describe different shape oscillations that deviate from a spherical equilibrium. The excitation can be understood using a harmonic-oscillator potential with discrete energy states each representing different oscillator modes. The modes are represented by

different values of the λ parameter in Equation 2.9, where a unit of quantised vibrational energy is labelled a *phonon* with units $\hbar\omega$. For $\lambda=0$, a monopole excitation is observed and there is an expansion and contraction of the nuclear radius. This excitation is sometimes referred to as a *breathing mode* and is produced via an excitation of several hundred MeV to the $J^\pi = 0^+$ state. When $\lambda=1$, a dipole excitation is observed, resulting in either an *isoscalar* or *isovector* oscillation. In the isoscalar case a change in the nuclear matter is not observed since all nucleons move in unison. The isovector mode results in neutrons and protons moving in opposite directions. This can lead to phenomena such as giant dipole resonances. Similar to the breathing modes, large amounts of energy are required to excite these modes (~ 20 MeV). A single unit of $\lambda=2$ $\hbar\omega$ is labelled a quadrupole phonon. This excitation produces either a prolate or oblate shape oscillation of the nuclear surface, opposed to a movement of the whole nucleus. The analogous case to the giant dipole resonance here is the giant quadrupole resonance, which requires large excitation energies and thus quadrupole vibrations are thought of mainly as surface excitations. Adding one quadrupole phonon to the $J^\pi = 0^+$ ground state would produce the $J^\pi = 2^+$ state. Adding two quadrupole phonons to the system would give five possible components of each phonon, $\mu_{1,2}$, these being $\mu_{1,2} = -2, -1, 0, 1, 2$. Then applying symmetric combinations of phonon wave-functions a total 15 allowed combinations are found. This results in a characteristic triplet of states with spins $J^\pi = 0^+, 2^+, 4^+$ for the two-phonon state. The $\lambda=3$ mode is the octupole vibrational mode which carries three units of angular momentum and negative parity. The first excited state of an octupole vibrational band from the $J^\pi = 0^+$ state would then have spin and parity of 3^- . Octupole vibrational states are found in nuclei usually at energies higher than the quadrupole triplet. At higher energies still, the vibrational model begins to break down and give way to single-particle excitations arising from the breaking of nucleon pairs.

2.2.2 Nuclear Rotations

Nuclear rotations can occur for nuclei that have deformation (see Section 2.5). This is reinforced by the description of the nuclear wavefunction for a spherical nucleus having no preference in direction and that a rotation of such a system does not result in an observable change. As an example, nuclei in the rare earth and actinide region of the nuclear chart, $A > 150$ in Figure 2.2, have deformation and deviations from spherical nuclear shapes are prominent, providing the best candidates for excitation via rotation. Because of this, these nuclei have characteristic low-lying first excited states, which are seen at much lower energies compared to the rest of the nuclear chart. The Hamiltonian corresponding to a deformed rotor is given by,

$$H_{\text{rot}} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2\mathcal{J}} R^2 = \frac{\hbar^2}{2\mathcal{J}} (I - I_{\text{add}})^2, \quad (2.10)$$

where \mathcal{J} is the moment of inertia, R is the rotational angular momentum, and I_{add} , is the is the additional angular momentum that arises from, for example, an odd particle. From Equation 2.10, the rotational energies, E_{rot} , are derived in terms of \mathcal{J} , the angular momentum quantum number, I , and the energy of the lowest member of the rotational band, E_K , giving,

$$E_{\text{rot}} = E_K + \frac{\hbar^2}{2\mathcal{J}}I(I + 1) \quad [17]. \quad (2.11)$$

Increasing the angular momentum would therefore add rotational energy to the system, creating nuclear excited states that would, as the angular momentum increased, create a rotational band. For an even-even nucleus, the ground-state spin and parity will always be $J^\pi = 0^+$. From the rotational wave function, only even total angular momentum, J , states are allowed for $K = 0^+$, where K is the projection of J on the symmetry axis. This gives allowed J^π states of 0^+ , 2^+ , 4^+ , 6^+ , 8^+ , etc. Opposingly, states with odd- J values are only allowed for a $K^\pi = 0^-$ band, giving $J^\pi = 1^-$, 3^- , 5^- , 7^- , 9^- , etc.

2.3 Deformation in Nuclei

The introduction of nuclear deformation can be traced to more than a century ago when, in 1930, Enrico Fermi developed the hyperfine structure theory of atoms and molecules which was related to the electromagnetic interaction between nuclei [18]. Later, in 1939, Niels Bohr presented the liquid-drop model of the nucleus to explain vibrational excitations of nuclei [19]. It was not until 1953 that Aage Bohr and Ben Mottelson introduced the interplay between nuclear single-particle motion and collective motion of the nucleus [6]. This along with contributions by Hill and Wheeler [20], lead to a formalism for the microscopic understanding of the nucleus and its constituents that has had significant impact on low-energy nuclear physics [21]. These advances in theoretical understanding in combination with the measurement of experimental observables such as electric quadrupole moments, low-lying rotational transitions, and single-particle excitations paved the way for the present description of non-spherical nuclear shapes [22].

Deformation occurs in nuclei that are far from closed shells and has its origin arising from the long range component of the residual nucleon-nucleon interaction, or quadrupole-quadrupole interaction. This gives additional binding energy to nuclei far from closed shells if they are deformed [17]. From a similar form of Equation 2.9 the deformation of a nucleus can be expressed by describing the radius, R , of the nucleus using,

$$R = R_0 \left[1 + \sum_{\lambda} \sum_{\mu} \alpha_{\lambda\mu} Y_{\lambda\mu}(\theta, \phi) \right]. \quad (2.12)$$

Here, $Y_{\lambda\mu}$ are the spherical harmonics, $\alpha_{\lambda\mu}$ are the expansion coefficients, and R_0 is the radius of a spherical nucleus. The subscript λ expresses the multipolarity of the deformation which can take values of 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4, ..., etc. for monopole, dipole, quadrupole, octupole, and hexadecapole deformation, respectively. The value of μ describes the orientation of the deformation inferred by the λ parameter and can take $2\lambda + 1$ integer values between $-\lambda$ and $+\lambda$.

2.3.1 Quadrupole Deformation

Quadrupole deformation is the most common form of deformation observed in nuclei. Here, a nucleus is invariant under a reflection about the rotation axis. It can be visualised as the nucleus taking the form of an oblate or prolate ellipsoid. The extent of the quadrupole deformation can be understood by introducing two parameters which are related to the expansion coefficients in Equation 2.12. The parameters β and γ are related to the α_{20} and α_{22} coefficients using,

$$\alpha_{20} = \beta \cos \gamma, \quad (2.13)$$

and,

$$\alpha_{22} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}} \beta \sin \gamma, \quad (2.14)$$

where β describes the magnitude of the quadrupole deformation and γ infers the degree of axial asymmetry. Commonly, the subscript '2' refers to the λ parameter and is written as β_2 , to specifically denote a quadrupole deformed shape. Here, a value of $\beta_2 > 0$ describes a prolate shape and $\beta_2 < 0$ describes an oblate shaped nucleus [13]. The Lund convention is introduced to describe the level of quadrupole deformation and *triaxiality* a nucleus has, using a set of coefficients β and γ , respectively. where a nucleus is described as triaxial if its three principal axes have different lengths. This provides the description of nuclei from small to large quadrupole deformations as well as the definition of the principal axes in space, allowing the description of a range of nuclei from those with axial symmetry to extreme axial asymmetry. As an example, a nucleus with a non-zero β value and $\gamma = 30^\circ$ would display axial asymmetry whilst retaining reflection symmetry.

Additional quantities can be defined to characterise deformed nuclei. In particular, the quadrupole moment and moment of inertia are important. The quadrupole moment, Q_0 , is a measure of the deviation from a spherical shape using nucleon charge distributions and to second order in β is written as,

$$Q_0 = \frac{3}{\sqrt{5}\pi} Z R_0^2 \beta (1 + 0.16\beta), \quad (2.15)$$

where Z is the atomic number of the nucleus. To first order, the moment of inertia, \mathcal{J} , of a quadrupole deformed shape can be written as,

$$\mathcal{J} = \frac{2}{5} A M R_0^2 (1 + 0.31\beta), \quad (2.16)$$

where A is the mass number, M is the nuclear mass, measured in atomic mass units, R_0 denotes the radius of a spherical nucleus of equivalent volume, and β is the deformation parameter discussed above. The rotation of a rigidly deformed nucleus such as the example described above can be described microscopically using the cranked shell model which employs methods to determine the collective properties of the system as it rotates [23, 24].

2.4 Nilsson Model

The shell model works well for spherical nuclei but less well for nuclei that are deformed. The Nilsson model is therefore introduced to predict energies of single-particle orbitals in deformed nuclei. It is found that when using the Schrödinger equation to calculate a non-spherical potential for a deformed nucleus, the orbital angular momentum, ℓ , is no longer a good quantum number. Since nuclei away from closed shells contain valence nucleons which result in the nuclear potential containing residual interactions which drive a non-spherical shape, the shell model potential is no longer applicable. It is then evident that a new potential is required to describe the deformed nucleus. As a result, the quantum numbers previously used will now differ depending on the nuclear potential. Quantum numbers such as the orbital angular momentum, ℓ , will now be a mixture of different ℓ values. Similarly, the energy levels in the deformed potential will now be dependent on the spatial orientation of the orbit. In terms of quantum numbers this means that the energy will depend on the component of the total angular momentum, j , along the symmetry axis. Nilsson calculated properties of wave-functions using the Schrödinger equation for a deformed potential. The resulting Nilsson model includes expansion coefficients $a(N\ell j)$ to describe the deviation from a spherical nuclear potential by introducing the description of wave functions for single-particle states in deformed nuclei. Here a is the amplitude which can take any value. The labels N and j alone cannot be used to describe a deformed state, therefore, several new quantum numbers are adopted to describe the states in a deformed nucleus. These are written in the form,

$$\Omega^\pi [N n_z \Lambda]. \quad (2.17)$$

Here, N is the major-shell oscillator quantum number, n_z is the number of oscillator quanta along the symmetry axis, Λ is the component of the nucleon orbital angular momentum along the symmetry axis, Ω is the component of j along the symmetry (z) axis, and π is the parity.

Figure 2.3: The different projections of j along the symmetry axis for the $f_{7/2}$ orbital for varying value of β parameter. Figure taken from Ref. [13]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

The component of the total angular momentum projected along the symmetry axis is equal to $\Omega = \Lambda + \Sigma$, where $\Sigma = \pm \frac{1}{2}$ is the projection of the intrinsic nucleon spin on the symmetry axis [15, 23]. In the spherical case, energy levels of single-particle states have degeneracy $(2j + 1)$. For deformed orbitals this is no longer the case. Nucleon orbits that are closer to the core of the nucleus will be more tightly bound and will be lowest in energy. For prolate deformed nuclei, i.e. when the deformation parameter $\beta_2 > 0$, the orbit with the lowest value of Ω interacts most strongly with the core and is more tightly bound and therefore has the lowest energy. The reverse is the case for oblate deformed nuclei, $\beta_2 < 0$. This is represented pictorially for the case of the $f_{7/2}$ orbital in Figure 2.3 [17].

2.5 Octupole Correlations in Nuclei

For nuclei that display reflection asymmetry, the symmetry seen in quadrupole deformed nuclei with respect to a reflection along the symmetry axis is broken. Due to the interest in this subject in this thesis, a more

detailed understanding of reflection asymmetric nuclei is given here. This section first outlines the historical background and initial experimental work, then discusses theoretical predictions for reflection asymmetric nuclei. After this, the characteristic properties of reflection asymmetric or octupole correlated nuclei are discussed, along with specifics about spectroscopy of these nuclei. Finally, recent theoretical predictions are explained along with motivation for studying neutron-deficient nuclei with $Z > 92$.

2.5.1 Early Predictions and Experimental Work

The origin of octupole deformation can be traced to atomic physics where in 1937 Jahn and Teller theorised that, given orbital degeneracy for electronic states within an atom, the atom is liable to symmetry instabilities and asymmetric deformation[25]. This is provided that the electrons in the atomic orbits are bound strongly with the atom. The emergence of this theorem proved pivotal for molecular and atomic science as it provided the first explanation for stable asymmetric shapes. It can also be adapted to the atomic nucleus by considering single-particle states of nucleons. Similarly to the electronic orbits in the atom, neutrons and protons exist within orbital configurations within the nucleus and are therefore prone to similar symmetry breaking effects. This is therefore named the nuclear Jahn-Teller effect. The degeneracy of the eigenvalues of the single-particle Hamiltonian for nucleons around the Fermi level provides the mechanism that causes the instability with respect to shape vibrations, spontaneous symmetry breaking, and the experimentally observed static deformation [16]. This nucleon orbital degeneracy is especially prominent for nuclei that exist far from closed shells. Analogous to the atomic description, it is the coupling of the degenerate single-particle states with the nuclear collective motion that drives the Jahn-Teller effect. It is found that the spin-orbit splitting causes the spherical particle model levels to split at certain nucleon numbers, causing one level to split into two, as explained in Section 2.2.3. As a result, the $\ell + s$ orbital is pushed across the magic number gap, acting as the ‘intruder’ state, and therefore causing the degeneracy.

Initial observations of experimental evidence for reflection-asymmetric nuclei came in the early 1950’s when Asaro *et al.* [26, 27] identified the low-lying $J^\pi = 1^-$ state in ^{224}Ra at 215-keV from the α decay of ^{228}Th . In this case, the 1^- state decayed to both the 2^+ and 0^+ states with characteristic electric dipole (E1) transitions. After this, Alder *et al.* [28] and then later Leander *et al.* [29] expanded the understanding of these low-lying states, which are connected to states of opposite parity via E1 transitions, by associating them to a distortion of the reflection symmetry of the nuclear shape. In the latter study, rotational bands of interleaving parity are introduced with characteristic E1 transitions between the bands. From the E1 moment and transition rates further understanding of the deformation of a nucleus can be inferred.

2.5.2 Theoretical Predictions of Octupole Correlations

In the case of octupole deformation, single-particle states that differ in total and orbital angular momentum by three units of angular momentum come close together in energy and interact near the Fermi level through the octupole interaction. This level is defined as the energy of the highest single-particle state in a quantum system assuming all lower energy orbitals are filled. The interaction between these states near the Fermi surface occurs for specific nucleon numbers, which are sometimes referred to as octupole magic numbers, and for nuclei that have nucleon numbers close to the magic numbers, the maximal octupole correlations are expected [30]. The octupole magic numbers occur at nucleon numbers (and specific orbital states): 34 ($g_{9/2}$, $p_{3/2}$), 56 ($h_{11/2}$, $d_{5/2}$), 88 ($i_{13/2}$, $f_{7/2}$), and 134 ($j_{15/2}$, $g_{9/2}$).

2.5.2.1 Regions of Octupole Correlations

Figure 2.4 shows an example of the chart of nuclides highlighted with regions of reflection asymmetry or octupole collectivity. Currently, there are four regions in the nuclear chart that are predicted to display octupole correlations. These are the region around $N = Z = 34$, the lanthanides, including the $N = Z = 56$ and $100 > N > 80$ regions, the light-actinides, and the actinides with $Z > 90$. However, only the lanthanides and part of the light-actinides are currently accessible with sufficient production cross sections for spectroscopy.

Figure 2.4: The nuclear chart displaying octupole magic numbers (red lines) and surrounding regions (red circles). Also indicated are the spherical magic numbers (black lines).

2.5.2.2 Light Actinides

The light-actinide region of the nuclear chart is the most studied region related to octupole deformation, with examples of signature interleaved positive-parity and negative-parity bands observed in radium, thorium, and uranium nuclei [31–35].

Although the region of deformation is referred to as the light-actinides, it extends to lower- Z elements as well. Examples of radium ($Z = 88$) nuclei considered to display octupole correlations include those in the mass region $222 \leq A \leq 226$ [36]. The even-even isotopes $^{224,226}\text{Ra}$ display the best experimental evidence for stable octupole deformation in the region thus far, with ^{224}Ra having measured $B(E3)$ transition probability for the $0^+ \rightarrow 3^-$ transition of 42(3) W.u. and ^{226}Ra having 42(8) W.u. which is compared to values of 23(3) W.u. for ^{236}U and 33(4) W.u. for ^{220}Rn , which are both considered as octupole vibrational nuclei [35, 37–39]. Similar to ^{222}Ra , octupole vibrational bands are seen in other nuclei around $Z = 86$ such as $^{218,220,222,224,226}\text{Rn}$ [31, 32, 36]. The first listed actinide element is actinium ($Z = 89$) and due to its vicinity to the octupole magic number $Z = 88$, strong evidence of octupole properties in multiple isotopes have been observed. Nine actinium isotopes from ^{218}Ac to ^{230}Ac display characteristic alternating-parity bands, of which, $^{220,221,223,224,225,227}\text{Ac}$, are interpreted as having strong evidence of being octupole deformed [40–48]. As suggested in Ref. [41], the transition from an octupole vibrational band built upon a spherical ground state, to a deformed ground state in actinium, radium, and thorium nuclei is estimated to occur between $N = 129 - 132$. This is evident in the actinium nuclides with $^{219}_{89}\text{Ac}$ identified as marking the transition from a vibrational nucleus to a reflection-asymmetric nuclear shape.

Thorium isotopes ($Z = 90$) provide good evidence experimentally for octupole correlations with $^{220-232}\text{Th}$, excluding ^{229}Th , displaying the characteristic level scheme features associated with octupole deformation [49–55]. The isotope ^{220}Th marks a lower limit, with observations of interleaving parity band structures in the level scheme, with suggestions by Reviol *et al.* that this could mark a transitional region between a non-collective and collective behaviour [49]. In the case of the heavier thorium nuclei with $A \geq 232$, there are some theoretical models that predict octupole deformation is present, as explained in [56]. However, with increasing mass the experimental limits are increasingly evident. Nuclei with $Z > 90$ are scarcely populated to the degree necessary to identify octupole collectivity. The identification of excited states has been made in ^{229}Pa with other protactinium isotopes only theoretically predicted to have octupole collective properties [57–60]. There are two uranium ($Z = 92$) nuclei that display octupole collectivity, these being ^{224}U [61, 62] and ^{226}U [63], with other uranium isotopes being populated, as detailed in Refs. [54, 55, 64–68].

2.5.2.3 Neutron-Rich Lanthanides

Regions of reflection asymmetry in the lanthanides are observed, with studies of octupole deformation in neutron-rich $^{143,145,146}\text{Ba}$ by Brewer *et al.* [69] and a previous study identifying direct E3 strengths in ^{146}Ba through Coulomb excitation by Bucher *et al.* [70].

2.5.2.4 $N = Z = 56$ Region

In addition to the barium isotopes with $A > 140$ there are also predictions of octupole correlations around the region surrounding the $N = Z = 56$ octupole magic number. Predictions around ^{112}Ba have been made by Stalski for deformation energies of even-even nuclei in this region [71]. In this work non-zero β_3 values are predicted for several tellurium, xenon, and barium nuclei. Experimentally, the evidence for octupole correlations in this region is sparse.

2.5.2.5 $N = Z = 34$ Region

The region surrounding ^{64}Ge is also expected to display octupole correlations due to its vicinity to the octupole magic number 34. There is however no experimental or theoretical evidence for octupole deformed nuclei in this region. The even-even doubly magic ^{68}Se provides more evidence of shape coexistence than the expected reflection asymmetry [72, 73].

2.5.3 Properties of Nuclei with Octupole Correlations

Identifying characteristic features of reflection-asymmetric nuclei is crucial to understand key aspects of octupole collectivity and helps to establish a clearer region of these nuclei throughout the nuclear chart. One of the main spectroscopic features of octupole deformation is the observation of rotational bands built on excited states with alternating parity. Often, one band consists of even-spin, positive-parity states ($J^\pi = 0^+, 2^+, 4^+, 6^+, \dots$), while the other consists of odd-spin, negative-parity states ($J^\pi = 1^-, 3^-, 5^-, 7^-, \dots$). Characteristically low-lying negative-parity states can indicate octupole collective effects in nuclei. The rotational bands increase in spin by 2 units of angular momentum and are therefore characterised by electric quadrupole (E2) transitions, with the transitions between bands of opposite parity are expected to be enhanced electric dipole (E1) transitions for an octupole collective shape. The actual strength octupole collectivity for a nucleus is measured through the B(E3) transition strength.

In the case of the electric dipole (E1) moment, the enhancement arises from the fact that charge accumulates on the narrower end of the octupole-deformed nucleus. This, in turn, causes a separation of the centre of mass and the centre of charge in the nucleus leading to an increase in the E1 moment. The extent to which

the moment increases is dependent on the individual and collective contributions of the nucleons [74]. As shown in Ref. [29], the dipole moment can be written as,

$$D_0 = C_{LD}AZe \left(\beta_2\beta_3 + \frac{88}{27\sqrt{5}}\beta_3\beta_4 + \dots \right), \quad (2.18)$$

where e is the charge of an electron. Here $\beta_2\beta_3$ arises from protons moving towards the narrow end of the nucleus and the subscripts 2, 3, and 4 indicate the parameter value for quadrupole, octupole, and hexadecapole deformation, respectively. Here, C_{LD} is the liquid-drop dipole moment constant given by,

$$C_{LD} = \frac{9}{56\sqrt{35}} \frac{e^2}{\pi C}. \quad (2.19)$$

It was determined by Leander *et al.* [29] that an additional shell correction term has to be added to the dipole moment shown in Equation 2.18 to account for the isovector nuclear field contribution,

$$D_0^{SC} = e \frac{N}{A} [\langle z_{p.c.m} \rangle - \langle z_{n.c.m} \rangle]. \quad (2.20)$$

Here, $\langle z_{p.c.m} \rangle$ and $\langle z_{n.c.m} \rangle$ denote the expectation values for the centre-of-mass coordinates of the protons and neutrons, respectively. For a reflection-asymmetric nucleus $z_{p.c.m} \neq z_{n.c.m}$ and, therefore, D_0^{SC} is non-zero [75, 76]. The combined equation for the dipole moment is then written as the sum of the two contributions,

$$D_0 = D_0^{LD} + D_0^{SC}. \quad (2.21)$$

Direct measurement of the electric dipole moment is difficult and often a measurement of the branching ratio, $B(E1)/B(E2)$, or observation of a reduced transition rate, $B(E1)$, is required. These measurements require the intensities and energies of the transitions a nucleus undergoes. The formula for the branching ratio, $B(E1)/B(E2)$, in an octupole band structure is given by [77],

$$\frac{B(E1)}{B(E2)} = 0.771 \frac{I_\gamma(E1)}{I_\gamma(E2)} \frac{E_\gamma(E2)^5}{E_\gamma(E1)^3} (10^{-6} \cdot fm^{-2}). \quad (2.22)$$

Due to the influence of the shell correction term on the value of the electric dipole moment, a more reliable measurement of the octupole deformation can be made. Measurement of the octupole moment, $(E3)$, the deformation parameter, β_3 , and E3 matrix elements, which are less affected by the shell correction term,

provides direct measurement of the octupole strength of the nucleus. The measurement of the reduced transition probability, $B(E3)$, is often the most viable method to determine octupole collectivity and provides a direct measurement of the collective strength of the electric-octupole transition ($J^\pi = 0^+ \rightarrow 3^-$) [76]. There are various methods used to measure $B(E3)$ such as lifetime measurements and inelastic electron scattering. These are further detailed in Ref. [78]. The measurement of the reduced transition probability directly leads to understanding of β_3 from,

$$B(E3) = \left(\frac{3}{4}\pi\right)^2 (ZeR^3)^2 \beta_3^2. \quad (2.23)$$

Here a collective nucleus with uniform charge distribution is assumed.

2.5.4 Spectroscopy of Nuclei with Octupole Correlations

Systematics of observable properties are used to trace the evolution of a property of a nucleus. These can be seen as a function of neutron or proton number to determine how the property changes.

One property of interest is the projection of the angular momentum on the rotation axis, labelled as the aligned angular momentum, i_x , as shown in Figure 2.5. This property describes the projection of the total angular momentum, j , on the rotation axis. From the figure it is inferable that the average value of the aligned angular momentum can be written as,

$$\langle i_x \rangle = \sqrt{I(I+1) - K^2} \hbar, \quad (2.24)$$

where I is the spin and K is the projection of the total angular momentum on the symmetry axis. Observing the aligned angular momentum with varying rotational frequency, $\hbar\omega$, which for a rotational band can be written as,

$$\hbar\omega = \frac{\Delta E}{2}, \quad (2.25)$$

allows the comparison between the positive and negative parity bands of a nucleus' level scheme to be observed as the angular momentum increases. Microscopically, this describes how the intrinsic angular momenta of individual nucleons align with the total rotation of the nucleus. Where the observation of a delayed alignment with respect to reflection symmetric nuclei provides evidence of reflection asymmetry. As shown

in Figure 2.6 the rotational alignments for a radium nuclei are plotted [36, 79]. The smooth increase shown indicates the rotational nature of these nuclei. The evolution of the difference between aligned angular momentum for the positive-parity, i^+ , and negative-parity, i^- , band states of the nuclei can also be calculated. This is given by,

$$\Delta i_x = i_x^- - i_x^+. \quad (2.26)$$

For a nucleus with stable octupole deformation it is expected that Δi_x is zero [36]. Experimentally it is seen that Δi_x is close to three for low angular momentum then as the spin increases, Δi_x decreases towards zero. It is seen that nuclei which are known to have the largest octupole correlations, such as ^{224}Ra and ^{222}Ra , have Δi_x values of ~ 2 for low rotational frequency values, as shown in Figure 2.6. Then as the rotational frequency increases the value of Δi_x tends towards zero. For a Δi_x value closer to 3 an octupole vibrational nucleus is expected, due to the octupole phonon carrying 3 units of angular momentum. The physical understanding for the radium nuclei shown in Figure 2.6 are explained in Ref. [36]. For $A = 222 - 226$ the rotation of the nucleus appears to stabilise the octupole deformation in these nuclei. For $^{220,228}\text{Ra}$ an octupole vibrational shape is expected at low frequency, then with increasing rotation reflection symmetry is restored. This restoration is shown to occur for lower rotational frequency in ^{220}Ra compared to ^{228}Ra .

Figure 2.5: A diagram showing the projections of the nuclear spin. As indicated, the aligned angular momentum i_x is shown as a projection of the spin on the rotation axis x . Here, K is the projection of the total angular momentum on the symmetry axis z and ω is the rotational frequency. This figure is taken from Ref. [17]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

Figure 2.6: Aligned angular momenta for radium isotopes with $220 \leq A \leq 228$. The plots on the left show aligned angular momentum, i_x , as a function of rotational frequency for positive-parity (black circles) and negative-parity (white circles). The right hand plots show the difference between the positive and negative parity band levels as a function of angular momentum. Here, the dashed lines indicate $\Delta i_x = 3$ and $\Delta i_x = 0$. This figure is taken from Ref. [36].

In addition to the aligned angular momentum, there are other plots that can be made to determine systematic trends. Two examples are the ratio of the rotational frequencies and the parity splitting between the positive-parity and negative-parity states of the level scheme. These are plotted in Figure 2.7 as a function of the angular momentum for radium nuclei with $218 \leq A \leq 228$. In the limit of stable octupole deformation, the ratio of the rotational frequencies of the positive and negative-parity bands should approach one [79]. For positive parity states this ratio is given by,

$$\frac{\omega^-(I)}{\omega^+(I)} = 2 \frac{E(I+1^-) - E(I-1^-)}{E(I+2^+) - E(I-2^+)}, \quad (2.27)$$

and for negative parity states,

$$\frac{\omega^+(I)}{\omega^-(I)} = 2 \frac{E(I+1^+) - E(I-1^+)}{E(I+2^-) - E(I-2^-)}. \quad (2.28)$$

As shown in Figure 2.7, it appears that several radium nuclei approach the stable octupole limit for high spins, indicating that in these nuclei a value closer to the rigid body value is achieved as the spin increases [79]. The displacement between the positive and negative parity band states of a nucleus is determined by calculating the deviation in energy of a negative-parity band state from the midpoint of the two adjacent positive-parity bands states. As a result, the parameter δE is determined. Plotting δE as a function of the angular momentum, as shown in Figure 2.7, it is expected that nuclei displaying stable octupole deformation will have δE close to zero. Typically, for octupole deformed nuclei δE is above zero for low spin, then with increasing spin δE tends to zero.

Figure 2.7: The parity splitting between positive-parity and negative-parity bands (left) and rotational frequency ratios (right) as a function of angular momentum for a series of radium isotopes. This figure is taken from Ref. [79]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

2.5.5 Recent Theoretical Predictions

Theoretical predictions are important in order to determine the regions of the nuclear chart that are expected to possess specific observable features. In this case octupole deformation has been predicted in several regions across the nuclear chart using several different theoretical models. These are now explained briefly.

A publication by Robledo and Bertsch [80] used a computational methodology to determine systematics of octupole excitations, $E_x(3^-)$, in even-even nuclei across the nuclear chart. Using this theoretical approach a comparison between the experiment data from Kibédi and Spear [38] was performed. This is shown in Figure 2.8. Here, the theoretical model predicts far more extensive regions of octupole excitation energies than are currently inaccessible experimentally. It is clear that the theory does however match the enhanced excitation energies that are seen in the experimental data for the expected mass regions.

Figure 2.8: A comparison between a theoretical model and experimental results for even-even nuclei with $Z \geq 8$. Here the circles represent experimental data and the triangles represent the theoretical predictions. This figure was taken from Ref. [80]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

Another theoretical study by Agbemava *et al.* [56] used covariant density functional theory to analyse the prevalence of octupole deformation in even-even nuclei with $Z \leq 106$. This work identifies a new region of octupole deformation centred around $Z \sim 98$, $N \sim 196$ which is close to the actinide region of the nuclear chart, a well known experimentally observed region that hosts octupole collective nuclei. Included in this theoretical study are potential energy surfaces (PES), plotting the octupole deformation parameter, β_3 , against the quadrupole deformation parameter, β_2 . This allows the level of the predicted deformation to be viewed.

Plots of the PES for the even-even light-actinides from radon ($Z = 86$) to thorium ($Z = 90$) are shown in Ref. [56]. Above $Z = 90$ PES plots are shown for even-even nuclei from uranium ($Z = 92$) to fermium ($Z = 100$) with non-zero β_3 values around $A \sim 230$.

A more recent publication by Cao *et al.* [10] used energy density functional theory to predict the landscape of the octupole collective regions of the nuclear chart. Shown in Figure 2.9 the plot of the nuclear chart indicates even-even nuclei with $Z \leq 110$ and $N \leq 210$ that are predicted to have ground-state octupole deformations by a different density functionals. In addition to the light-actinide region around ^{224}Ra and the neutron-rich lanthanide region around ^{146}Ba , regions of predicted octupole deformation are seen around very neutron-rich ^{200}Gd and ^{288}Pu , as well as around ^{112}Ba . This study also predicts candidates in the neutron-deficient actinide region that possess ground-state octupole deformations. These nuclei are identified as being accessible experimentally including $^{224,226,228}\text{U}$ and $^{226,228,230}\text{Pu}$.

Figure 2.9: Reflection asymmetry across the nuclear chart. Predicted octupole deformed nuclei are shown in circles and stars with the legend indicating the number of theoretical energy density functionals that predict octupole deformation. The green solid line indicates the currently known nuclei. This figure was taken from Ref. [10]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

The actinide region with $Z > 90$ is theoretically predicted to be a region with octupole collectivity, with non-zero β_3 values predicted for $^{228-238}\text{Cf}$ and $^{228-232}\text{Pu}$, amongst others. Recent calculated potential energy surfaces by Nomura *et al.* [11] are shown in Figure 2.10 to support this. The theoretical model predicts β_3 values from $0.1 \leq \beta_3 \leq 0.2$ for the majority of the plutonium nuclei with the largest minima value of $\beta_3 \approx 0.17$ for ^{228}Pu . Additional PES are shown in Ref. [11] for californium nuclei, with only three nuclei

predicted to have non-zero β_3 values.

Figure 2.10: Potential energy surface plots for two theoretical models. The colour code indicates the energies in MeV up to 10 MeV. This figure was taken from Ref. [11]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

2.5.6 Specific Predictions for $Z > 92$

Several neptunium ($Z = 93$) and plutonium ($Z = 94$) isotopes are theoretically predicted to display octupole deformed characteristics [81–83], but none have been identified through in-beam spectroscopy to date. As mentioned in the theoretical predictions by Cao *et al.*, there are nuclei in the neutron-deficient actinide region that display stable ground-state octupole deformation and are now experimentally reachable. More specifically even-even plutonium nuclei ($Z = 94$) with $224 \leq A \leq 234$ all have theoretical models which

infer octupole collectivity. These nuclei have, as yet, not been studied using in-beam spectroscopy. Of these nuclei, $^{226,228,230}\text{Pu}$ provide the strongest evidence for octupole deformation, however, these nuclei are very neutron deficient and are out of scope of experimental studies. Less neutron-deficient plutonium nuclei such as $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ are more accessible, however. In-beam spectroscopy results of even-even plutonium nuclei with $236 \leq A \leq 240$ are known and can be used in to determine systematics to infer the expected transition and level energies of the nearby $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ nuclei. Populating these nuclei would provide the first such study of predicted octupole-deformed neutron-deficient plutonium isotopes in this region and would yield experimental data that can be used to compare to the theoretical predictions explained in Section 2.5.5.

Chapter 3

Experimental Techniques

This chapter contains a discussion of the reaction employed and physical phenomena relating to the population of the nuclei of interest. The chapter begins with a brief background of radioactive decay, then provides details on heavy-ion reactions. After this a description of the interaction of γ rays and charged particles with matter is included. Then Finally, Information on γ -ray spectroscopy is given.

3.1 Radioactive Decay

A nucleus in an excited state can transition to a lower-energy state through the emission of radiation. The decay mechanism depends on the number of neutrons and protons, which determines the neutron and proton separation energies, and the initial energy of the excited state. The most prevalent methods of nuclear decay are discussed here.

3.1.1 Alpha Decay

This type of decay occurs when a nucleus emits an α particle, which is the same as a nucleus of a ${}^4_2\text{He}$ atom. The emission of the α particle reduces both the neutron, N , and proton, Z , number by two units, as given by,

where A is the mass number of the nucleus. The Q -value for the emission of the α particle can be calculated as the difference between the initial, M_i , and final, M_f , states using the binding energy and the atomic masses

of the initial nucleus (M_{Mother}), the α particle (M_{α}), and the resultant nucleus after the decay (M_{Daughter}) using,

$$Q_{\alpha} = M_i - M_f = (M_{\text{Mother}} - (M_{\alpha} + M_{\text{Daughter}}))c^2. \quad (3.2)$$

The fraction of energy, T_{α} , that the α particle takes after the reaction is then,

$$T_{\alpha} = Q \left(1 - \frac{4}{A} \right). \quad (3.3)$$

The α particle emitted carries away angular momentum with the allowed values between minimum and maximum values of $I_i + I_f$ and $|I_i - I_f|$. The change in parity is given by $\pi = (-1)^{\ell_{\alpha}}$ where ℓ_{α} represents the angular momentum that the α particle carries away.

Decay via α -particle emission is more favourable in very neutron-deficient nuclei, or nuclei north-east of ^{208}Pb on the chart of nuclides. This method of decay is rarely seen in nuclei with mass number $A < 150$ because the Coulomb barrier for α -particle emission is higher in energy for lighter nuclei compared to heavier nuclei. This is due to the increase in Coulomb repulsion in heavy nuclei from the larger number of protons and also from the fact that tightly bound groups of four nucleons created by the greater saturation of the nuclear force leads to a reduction in the energy required to separate the α cluster from the rest of the nucleus [14, 84].

3.1.2 Gamma Decay

When a nucleus undergoes γ decay it emits γ rays to remove excess energy and angular momentum from the system. The energy of the γ ray, E_{γ} , is given by,

$$E_{\gamma} = E_i - E_f, \quad (3.4)$$

which is the difference in energy between the initial, E_i , and final, E_f , energies of the states of the nucleus. The decay of a nucleus via γ -ray emission has the possibility of electric and magnetic transitions depending if there is a change in parity between the initial and final states. In the case of a magnetic transition, nucleons within the nucleus each possess magnetic-dipole moments and collectively the nucleus, along with the current loops arising from proton orbital motion, create the magnetic transitions in nuclei. In the case of electric transitions, the underlying phenomena from which the transitions arise comes from a change in the charge distribution of the protons within the nucleus. As mentioned, γ rays carry angular momentum away from the

nucleus when they are emitted. From the conservation of angular momentum, the initial angular momentum of the state, \vec{I}_i , can be written as,

$$\vec{I}_i = \vec{I}_f + \vec{L}, \quad (3.5)$$

where \vec{I}_f is the final angular momentum of the state and \vec{L} is the angular momentum carried by the γ ray, which can take minimum and maximum values of $I_i + I_f$ and $|I_i - I_f|$, respectively. The transition between initial and final states can also cause a change in parity. For electric-multipole transitions, the parity is defined as,

$$\pi = (-1)^L, \quad (3.6)$$

and for magnetic-multipole transitions the parity change is defined by,

$$\pi = (-1)^{L+1}. \quad (3.7)$$

The transition probability of a γ ray being emitted depends on the energy, E , and the mass number, A , of the nucleus. The larger the amount of angular momentum carried, the lower the transition probability. These probabilities are given per unit time and are accurate if it is assumed that the transition is a single-particle transition. Often referred to as Weisskopf estimates, these probabilities are determined for magnetic and electric transitions and are given in Table 2.1 for the lowest order transitions [13]. It is noted that the Weisskopf estimates are not used as accurate theoretical values to be compared with empirical results, instead, the estimates provide a basis for comparison. For example, experimentally calculated transition rates greater or less than the Weisskopf estimates may indicate to the user that there are other factors influencing the transition rate value [13].

$T(E1) = 1.0 \times 10^{14} A^{2/3} E^3$	$T(M1) = 5.6 \times 10^{13} E^3$
$T(E2) = 7.3 \times 10^7 A^{4/3} E^5$	$T(M2) = 3.5 \times 10^7 A^{2/3} E^5$
$T(E3) = 34 A^2 E^7$	$T(M3) = 16 A^{4/3} E^7$
$T(E4) = 1.1 \times 10^{-5} A^{8/3} E^9$	$T(M4) = 4.5 \times 10^{-6} A^2 E^9$

Table 3.1: Weisskopf transition rate estimates for the lowest-order electric and magnetic multipolarities. E is in MeV.

3.1.3 Internal Conversion

Internal conversion is the process in which an atomic electron is ejected from its atomic shell due to an interaction with the multipole field of the nucleus, which provides enough energy to liberate the electron from the shell that it is occupying. The ejected electron usually occupies the K or L shells, leaving a hole in the shell which is then filled with an outer-shell electron. This transition between electron shells causes an x-ray or Auger electron to be emitted with characteristic energy equal to the energy gap between shells [13]. The energy that the electron carries away from the atom as kinetic energy is the energy of the transition minus the binding energy which must be overcome to disassociate the electron from its orbit. The binding energy will depend on the shell that the electron is emitted from.

Internal conversion competes increasingly with γ -ray emission as a de-excitation method with increasing Z and decreasing transition energy, and has a much higher probability to occur for the emission of an electron from the K shell [84]. For nuclei with increasing Z values the electron binding energy increases due to the increasing positive charge of the nucleus. This means that the probability of the nucleus interacting with the inner shell electrons increases making it more likely that a conversion electron is emitted. The internal conversion coefficient is expressed as a function of the atomic number through,

$$\alpha \propto \frac{Z^3}{E_\gamma^{2L+1}} \quad (3.8)$$

where E_γ is the γ -ray energy, and L is the multipole order. Due to electrons having discrete energies, similar to γ rays, internal conversion electron spectroscopy can be used to as an alternative or a complement to γ -ray spectroscopy.

3.2 Heavy-Ion Reactions

There is a wide range of interactions that can be classed as heavy-ion reactions. In terms of classical mechanics, the mechanism that is observed experimentally will depend on the impact parameter, b , which describes the distance of closest approach between the projectile and target. Examples of several impact parameter values are illustrated in Figure 3.1. The cross section of a specific reaction mechanism can then be written in terms of b . As a quantum mechanical analogue, the partial cross-section, σ_r , can be expressed in terms of the wavenumber, k , and orbital angular momentum, ℓ , as,

$$\sigma_r(\ell) = \frac{2\pi}{k^2} \ell. \quad (3.9)$$

Figure 3.1: Several impact parameter, b , values showing different potential trajectories, leading to different reactions. The grazing collisions take place when b is close to b_0 . This figure is taken from Ref. [85]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

As shown in Figure 3.2, the value of $\sigma_r(\ell)$ between the values $\ell = 0$ and $\ell = \ell_{gr}$ provides the three main mechanisms of heavy-ion reactions; fusion, deep-inelastic collisions, and quasi-elastic collisions. During heavy-ion reactions it is difficult to populate nuclei from one specific mechanism, and as such results from a spectrum of mechanisms are observed. The border regions of Figure 3.2 indicate the overlap of mechanisms. Due to the variance in reaction mechanisms it is important then to distinguish each process by defining what is meant by each of the possible reaction mechanisms.

Figure 3.2: The reaction cross section plotted against the orbital angular momentum. Here the different regions for fusion (σ_F), deep-inelastic scattering (σ_{DIC}), and quasi-elastic scattering (σ_{qe}) are indicated. This figure is taken from Ref. [86]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

3.2.1 Fusion Reactions

At small values of the impact parameter, heavy-ion reactions lead to compound formation or fusion. There are three sub-mechanisms within the scope of a small impact parameter; incomplete fusion, fusion evaporation, and fission [85, 86]. For fusion evaporation and fission reactions the impact parameter is small enough such that the interaction between the projectile and target nuclei results in an exit channel that is independent of the compound system of projectile and target. The impact parameters for fusion-evaporation reactions and fission reactions are roughly similar, the only difference occurs when a larger amount of angular momentum is present in the system, leading to the compound system fissioning into separate nuclei. Incomplete fusion occurs when the impact parameter is slightly larger than for the other two sub-mechanisms. Here, Coulomb and centrifugal fields become more important resulting in the projectile nuclei breaking up into clusters. One of the clusters may then fuse with the target nucleus, leaving the remaining fragments to follow the beam velocity and direction [87]. After the reaction, the products de-excite via the emission of neutrons, α particles or protons until they are below the respective separation energies, and then γ -ray emission.

Fusion begins to breakdown as a possible reaction mechanism at higher projectile and target masses due to the increased Coulomb repulsion. In these cases, deep-inelastic collisions play a greater role.

3.2.2 Deep-Inelastic Collisions

Deep-inelastic collisions (DIC) occur when heavy ions collide close to the value of the impact parameter that results in a grazing collision. The resulting exit channel is binary, i.e. two nuclei are resulting from the interaction [88]. These reactions, sometimes called damped or dissipative collisions, are characterised by substantial kinetic energy transfer and multi-nucleon exchanges, with the exit channel having knowledge of the initial reactants in the form of masses and charges. The total kinetic energy loss (TKEL) in DIC can be of the order of several hundred MeV. When the projectile and target interact they exchange nucleons in a redistribution that is governed by strong driving forces associated with the potential energy surface of the binary system. The redistribution is what is known as N/Z equilibration. The amount of energy dissipated from the system then depends on the amount of protons and neutrons being exchanged [89].

There is also potential for a large transfer of angular momentum of up to $50\hbar$ during the interaction [85]. This is transferred to the internal degrees of freedom and eventually removed from the system by the γ rays emitted as a product of the reaction. For a brief period of time the di-nuclear complex will rotate and dissipate angular momentum, with the grazing of the projectile and the target causing friction which induces a rotation [90]. This tangential friction can be broken into ‘sliding’ friction and ‘rolling’ friction, which work together

to reduce the initial orbital angular momentum. The sliding friction induces a relative rotation of the nuclei that are sliding on one another which is then counteracted by the rolling friction. When the velocities of the two parts of the system are equal, the sliding friction reduces to zero and the rolling friction continues to reduce the rolling mode and the nuclei stick together and rotate as a compound system. This explanation considers the system independent of the exchange of mass transfer and, therefore, in order to correctly model the complex system, the transfer of mass would have to be considered along with the angular momentum transfer. On top of this the transfer of nucleons can also be a cause of the friction observed between the projectile and target.

3.2.3 Quasi-elastic Reactions

Quasi-elastic transfer reactions have a small energy dissipation and the angular distribution is concentrated around the grazing angle. Here, similar but less severe phenomena are observed as inelastic collisions, with experimental observables such as single nucleon exchange and a smaller kinetic energy losses to the internal excitations being possible. A clear experimental distinction between deep-inelastic collisions and quasi-elastic reactions is not possible, as the method to produce these reactions exhibits insufficient sensitivity to separate reaction products from each mechanisms. Further information is detailed in Ref. [91].

3.2.4 Grazing Angle

The minimum value of the impact parameter at which nuclear forces are negligible compared to the Coulomb interaction is labelled the grazing value (b_0 in Figure 3.1). Around this value, reactions predominantly exhibit a binary character; the favoured processes are quasi-elastic scattering and deep-inelastic scattering. The grazing angle can then be thought of as the angle at which the cross section for these types of interactions is largest or the angle at which the target and projectile interact with the distance of closest approach between the two equal to the radius of the target. The grazing angle changes depending on the reaction and its kinematics.

3.3 Interaction of γ rays with Matter

As photons pass through matter they interact and transfer energy to the atomic electrons in the matter. There are three main processes whereby electromagnetic radiation can interact with matter [92]: Compton scattering, the Photoelectric effect, and pair production. Figure 3.3 illustrates these interaction mechanisms as a

function of the atomic number, Z , and the photon energy.

Figure 3.3: The three main interaction mechanisms of photons with matter as a function of the atomic number, Z , of the absorber and energy of the incident photon. This figure is taken from Ref. [93]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

3.3.1 Photoelectric Effect

The photoelectric effect is the name given to the process where an incident photon interacts with a bound inner-shell electron in a material, depositing all its energy and liberating the electron from its shell causing outer-shell electrons to fill inner-shell gaps and emit x-rays with characteristic energy. The energy of the photon has to be greater than that of the binding energy of the electron in order to free it. It then follows that the energy of the emitted electron can be written as,

$$E = h\nu - E_B, \quad (3.10)$$

where E_B is the binding energy of the electron and $h\nu$ is the energy of the incident photon.

For photon energies lower than the binding energy of the most bound electrons, the photon may still deposit its energy to an outer-shell electron, such as a L or M-shell electron. This causes the cross-section for the photoelectric effect to change rapidly at specific energies, depending on the material. These rapid changes in

the cross-sections are known as shell ‘edges’. For lower energy photons ($< 1 \text{ MeV}$) the photoelectric effect can dominate the observable interaction with matter.

3.3.2 Compton Scattering

The Compton effect describes the elastic scattering of a photon off an atomic electron. The photon of energy, $h\nu_0$, is scattered at an angle, θ , with some reduced energy $h\nu$, resulting in a shift in wavelength and frequency. It can be shown that the shift in wavelength of the photon due to the scattering is independent of the incident energy and also that the maximum shift in the wavelength when $\theta = 180^\circ$, can be written as,

$$(\Delta\lambda)_{\max} = \frac{2h}{m_e c} = 2\lambda_c, \quad (3.11)$$

where $\lambda_c = 2.43 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}$ is the Compton wavelength. The shift in the wavelength after scattering is given by the difference between the wavelength after scattering, λ' and the initial wavelength of the photon, λ . Considering the conservation of energy and momentum the difference can be written in terms of the scattering angle, θ , the rest mass of the electron, m_e , Planck’s constant, h , and the speed of light, c , as,

$$\lambda' - \lambda = \frac{h}{m_e c} (1 - \cos \theta). \quad (3.12)$$

Then using the relation between the wavelength and energy of the photon,

$$E = \frac{hc}{\lambda}, \quad (3.13)$$

it can be shown that Equation 3.3 simplifies to provide the relationship between the initial, E_γ , and scattered photon energies, E'_γ , as,

$$E'_\gamma = \frac{E_\gamma}{E_\gamma/m_e c^2 (1 - \cos \theta) + 1}. \quad (3.14)$$

For a small incident energy, the resulting photon energy is not changed significantly during the scattering process, however, for large incident energies the photon imparts the majority of its energy to the electron. Here the photon and electron will scatter in opposite directions from one another.

The differential cross-section for Compton scattering is given by,

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{r_e^2}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda}{\lambda'} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\lambda}{\lambda'} + \frac{\lambda'}{\lambda} - \sin^2\theta \right), \quad (3.15)$$

where $r_e \approx 2.82$ fm is the classical electron radius. This equation was derived by Klein and Nishina who applied the Dirac equation for relativistic electrons to describe the probability and angular distribution of the scattered photons [13].

It should be noted that Compton scattering is the dominant interaction for photons within the energy range considered for this experiment.

3.3.3 Pair Production

This phenomenon occurs only for photon energies greater than twice the rest mass of the electron (~ 1.022 MeV). Under this condition, the photon energy is completely absorbed and an electron-positron pair is created spontaneously. The creation of the pair must also happen within the field of a nucleus or electron in order to obey the conservation of momentum. After the production of the electron-positron pair a common occurrence is the annihilation of the resulting positron with another electron which creates a pair of 511-keV photons emitted at opposing angles from one another. At energies above 5 MeV, pair production dominates for photon interactions with matter, as shown in Figure 3.3. It is worth noting that this is significantly higher energy than γ rays emitted in this experiment.

3.4 Interaction of Charged Particles With Matter

A charged particle incident on matter will lose energy via the action of its electric field on the atoms of the medium it travels through. In the majority of cases energy is lost through ionisation of the atoms in the medium. This is due to the fact that electron stopping dominates and nuclear stopping is negligible. This is because the interaction cross sections for interactions with electrons is greater than with nuclei. The rate at which a particle loses energy per unit path length is known as the stopping power of the medium. This can be derived quantum mechanically as,

$$-\frac{dE}{dx} = \left(\frac{ze^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \right)^2 \frac{4\pi Z\rho N_A}{Amv^2} \left[\ln \left(\frac{2m\nu^2}{I} \right) - \ln(1 - \beta^2) - \beta^2 \right], \quad (3.16)$$

where $\nu = \beta c$ is the ion velocity, ze is its electronic charge, m is the mass of an electron, N_A is Avogadro's number, and A , Z , and ρ are the atomic mass number, atomic number and density of the stopping mate-

rial, respectively [12]. It can be shown that the relationship between the energy loss, dE , and total energy deposited in the medium, E is given by,

$$\frac{dE}{dx} \sim \frac{AZ^2}{E}, \quad (3.17)$$

where dx is the distance travelled, with the quantity $\frac{dE}{dx}$ representing the energy loss per unit length. The loss of energy is different for electrons and heavy charged particles like protons. This is because of the mass of an electron being significantly less than that of a proton and therefore, assuming the same given energy, electrons are much faster than protons in the medium. This means that the stopping power of the medium is much smaller for electrons than for heavy charged particles. Nevertheless, electrons that interact with atomic electrons in the medium have a higher probability of depositing all their energy from a single collision compared to heavy particles. Therefore, due to the uncertainty of the interaction point, the range of an electron in a medium is much less well defined. For heavy charged particles, it is found that as the incident particle travels further in the medium, the stopping power increases up to a maximum as the particle will undergo several interactions and therefore dissipate its energy until it comes to rest. This maximum, illustrated in Figure 3.4, is known as the Bragg peak and is used to determine the range of various charged particles in matter.

Figure 3.4: Energy loss of an alpha particle with energy of the order of MeV along its path in matter. This figure is taken from Ref. [94]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

3.5 Gamma-ray Spectroscopy

The technique of γ -ray spectroscopy is employed widely in nuclear physics in order to study the properties of excited nuclear states such as energy and decays. It can also be used to determine quantities such as the lifetimes of states from which structural properties can be determined. The emission of γ rays, as mentioned in Section 3.1.2, occurs when a nucleus makes a transition from a state of higher energy to a state of lower energy.

3.5.1 Gamma-ray coincidences

Typically when decaying from a higher-energy state to the ground state, a nucleus will pass through multiple short-lived excited states, therefore emitting several γ rays within a short period of time, this is sometimes called a cascade. Transitions within the same cascade are defined as being *in coincidence* with each other as they are observed within a short time window, often effectively at the same time.

From the detection of a γ -ray, the detector produces electronic signals related to the γ -ray interaction with the detector material. These electronic signals are processed to create spectra which can display the emitted radiation energy as photopeaks, which are measured to infer properties about the measured decays and thus about the nucleus that emitted the radiation. During the decay of a nucleus from high-lying excited states, the emission of multiple γ rays is expected as the nucleus transitions to lower energy states to remove excess energy and angular momentum. In order to determine structural information about the nucleus, it is of interest to identify all the transitions that the nucleus makes whilst decaying. The cascade of γ rays can be identified in the spectra through the use of two-dimensional and three-dimensional histograms. By applying gates on one or two γ rays of known energy, the transitions which are in coincidence with the selected photopeaks are identified. The application of coincidence gating can help distinguish weak signals or a physical signal that would ordinarily be obscured by background in the spectrum. From the identification of a cascade of γ rays a level scheme can be built and properties of the nucleus can be inferred.

Using γ -ray spectroscopy also allows the measurement of angular distributions between populating and depopulating transitions which can be used to infer the multipole of the transitions via a comparison of the distribution with theoretical predictions for multipole combinations. This information, therefore, allows the identification of the excited states from which they are emitted [13].

3.5.2 Compton Suppression

In an ideal case a γ ray will only interact once and deposit all of its energy in the detector material. In reality this is not always the case. More commonly, incident γ rays will scatter within the detector material multiple times, as described in Section 3.3.2, and then escape the detector volume. This leads to incomplete detection of the full energy of the incident radiation. In order to address this, Compton suppression shields are used. These are additional detectors placed around the initial detector and can be used in two modes: coincidence and anti-coincidence. In coincidence mode, if the scattered γ ray is detected in the additional detectors within a specific time window of the initial interaction with the initial detector crystal then the deposited energies are summed and treated as one event. This is allowed by requiring an event to correspond to more than one interaction within the detectors before they are recorded. In the anti-coincidence mode, the additional detectors are used to veto any events within a time window of the detection of a scattered γ ray. In this case, only full-energy absorption events are accepted. In both these modes the Compton continuum that would result from the detection of partial deposition of the energy of a γ ray is significantly reduced, leading to a cleaner overall spectrum. The application of the anti-coincidence mode is illustrated in Figure 3.5, with a clear reduction in the continuum being shown.

Figure 3.5: Pulse height spectra from a ^{60}Co source. (a) Normal spectrum from a central germanium detector. (b) Application of additional scintillation detectors in anti-coincidence mode. This figure is taken from Ref. [94]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

3.5.3 Doppler Effect

If a nucleus in motion emits a photon the measured energy of the photon will be Doppler shifted. The Doppler shift depends on the velocity of the nucleus and the direction of the photon relative to the direction of the nucleus. The Doppler shift has to be considered in order to determine the energies of the photon.

Considering a nuclear reaction with a projectile impinging on a thin target, with the resulting reaction products recoiling from the reaction site, the resulting observed energy of a γ ray emitted from the reaction product is,

$$E_{\gamma} = \frac{1}{2}(E_i - E_f) \left(1 + \frac{E_f}{E_i} \right) \frac{[1 - (v/c)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 - (v/c) \cos \theta}, \quad (3.18)$$

where E_i and E_f are the initial and final energies of the nucleus, v is the velocity of the nucleus in the laboratory frame, and θ is the laboratory angle between the nuclear velocity and the γ ray. It can then be assumed that the first two terms in Equation 3.18 can be simplified to the energy of the γ ray in the moving reference frame, E_{γ}^0 . Then substituting $\beta = v/c$ gives,

$$E_{\gamma}(\theta) = \frac{E_{\gamma}^0(1 - \beta^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 - \beta \cos \theta}. \quad (3.19)$$

After detection of the radiation, the resulting γ -ray spectrum illustrates the effect of the Doppler shift via shifted centroids and/or a general broadening of the photopeak due to the varied distributions of β and θ [95]. In order to account for the Doppler shift knowledge of the velocity of the recoiling nucleus and the angle of emission of the γ ray is needed. Further details of the corrections applied in this work are explained in Section 5.2.6.

3.5.4 Semiconductor Detectors For γ -ray Detection

3.5.4.1 Semiconductor Concept

Semiconductors are a good choice for γ -ray detection purposes when compared to other material types such as basic conductors due to the band structure of the materials. The semiconductor material has a band structure that allows the movement of free charge, in the form of electrons and holes, easily enough to collect charge and allow current to flow when radiation, such as a γ ray, interacts with the material. Semiconductors also have a band gap between the valance and conduction band. This limits the amount of charge accumulating in the conduction band due to thermal excitation that would otherwise causes a constant leakage current, therefore resulting in a background that is unacceptable for a γ -ray detector.

Figure 3.6: Representations of the addition of impurities to a silicon crystal creating donor (a) and acceptor (b) states. This figure is taken from Ref. [94] Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

Often semiconductor detectors are doped with another material in order to add beneficial properties to the materials structure to increase the efficiency of detection. Introducing an impurity atom to the lattice structure of the material causes a free charge carrier to be inherent in the structure. This results in two scenarios which produce two types of semiconductor materials, *p-* or *n-type*. Applying the impurity can give rise to additional holes in the material which act as extra energy states known as acceptor states just above the valence band. In this case the semiconductor is labelled *p-type*. In contrast, if the impurity atom now left the system with extra electrons it would be labelled as a donor atom and donor states would be created just below the conduction band. The material in this case would be labelled *n-type*. An illustration of the band gap for *p-type* and *n-type* semiconductors is shown in Figure 3.6. The overall effect of introducing impurities is to increase the number of available states around the edges of the band gap effectively reducing its size. This increases conductivity for the material allowing for a larger movement of charge carriers. Generally, detector materials used to measure γ rays are a combination of *p-* and *n-type* semiconductors. The interaction of these materials when they are placed together creates what is known as a p-n junction. The excess charge carriers inherent in both materials are found to re-distribute as they are liberated through thermal excitations. Eventually, electrons and holes meet and annihilate, cancelling each other out. This creates a region in the material called the depletion region. This region is the active region of the detector, which can be increased by applying a reverse biased voltage across the region. A detector has the largest efficiency when its depletion region is as large as possible.

Key properties of ideal semiconductors are high purity, good energy resolution, and the ability to produce depletion regions which are the order of cm in size [96]. There are two main materials that are commonly used for semiconductors: silicon and germanium. Silicon is a good candidate due to the advancements in high-purity silicon production and the reasonable cost of the material. However silicon has some significant disadvantages when applied in γ -ray spectroscopy, namely its lower atomic number, resulting in a lower absorption coefficient. This means that it is less effective for the detection of γ rays. Therefore, germanium is most commonly used.

3.5.4.2 High-Purity Germanium Detectors

High-purity germanium detectors (HPGe) are commonly used for γ -ray spectroscopy due to their excellent energy resolution of ~ 0.3 keV. In order to achieve this resolution the detectors need to be cooled using liquid nitrogen to ~ 77 K, therefore reducing the amount of thermal excitations of electrons into the valence band. [96, 97]. There are two main types of HPGe detector: planar and coaxial. Planar HPGe detectors are generally in the form of a flat disk with contacts on either side of the disk which are reverse biased to create the depletion region. The benefit of planar detectors is the almost uniform field applied across the detector volume which allows a constant drift of charge carriers [94]. Due to the small size of planar detectors the absorption coefficient is lower than for other detector types and therefore they are mostly applied for the detection of low-energy γ rays. Coaxial detectors are frequently manufactured in three main shapes; true, closed-ended, and tapered, as shown in Figure 3.7. Generally, coaxial detectors have a larger active volume than planar detectors (e.g. 750 cm^3 compared to 30 cm^3). Due to the cylindrical nature of the detectors, a hole can be made in the centre of the cylinder and contacts can be placed within the centre and on the outer face of the cylinder, allowing a larger depletion region to be constructed. A true coaxial detector, like a coaxial cable, does not have a front face and therefore suffers from large leakage currents due to the accumulation of charge on the surface. Because of this the closed-ended coaxial detector is favoured. A disadvantage of the closed-end coaxial detector is that the front face of the coaxial shape leads to regions of non-uniformity in the electric field applied across the detector, which produces regions of the detector that have weaker fields. To combat this the hole in the centre of the detector can be extended as far as possible and the crystal can also be bulletized, essentially smoothing out the corners of the crystal face, to reduce the low field regions.

3.5.5 Scintillator Detectors For γ -ray Detection

Scintillation is the emission of light when atoms within a material are excited via incident radiation. The incident radiation, usually a photon, must have enough energy to excite electrons in the atomic shell structure

Figure 3.7: The three common shapes of coaxial crystals. Taken from Ref. [94] Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

to higher energy states. The atom then de-excites by emitting photons of visible light. By coupling the scintillator material to a photomultiplier, the emitted visible photon can be converted into an electric pulse which can be analysed and counted to provide information about the incident radiation [98, 99]. More commonly, the incident photon interacts with the scintillator medium several times, until it has dissipated all its energy. This causes multiple instances of electrons being raised to excited states and therefore multiple photons being emitted during the de-excitation of the atom [12].

There are several types of scintillator materials used for detection purposes. The type of material used depends on what type of particle or radiation is being detected. This section solely focuses on the use of scintillation detectors for γ -ray detection and therefore the use of inorganic scintillators is of primary interest as organic scintillator detectors are more favourable when attempting to detect beta particles or fast neutrons [94]. Inorganic scintillator crystals are commonly grown with added impurities to increase the probability of photon emission during de-excitation by adding activator states between the valence and conduction band [94]. These activator states provide sites within the crystal lattice that reduce the band gap between the valence and conduction band. This allows excited electrons to de-excite via these activator states and emit visible photons.

Scintillation detectors are often used in place of, or alongside, semiconductor detectors when conducting γ -ray spectroscopy experiments. The intrinsic timing resolution of scintillator detectors is significantly better than that of semiconductor detectors and can be of the order of nano or sub-nanoseconds in some cases [99]. The improvement in timing resolution is attributed to the fast signal generation due to the rapid production of photons after an interaction in the material. The timing resolution can be beneficial when attempting to reduce random events in energy coincidence measurements, particularly during high-fold events. In addi-

tion, scintillator detectors are often operated at room temperatures in comparison to the temperatures needed for semiconductor detectors (~ 77 K). This allows a wide range of applications for scintillators without the requirement for liquid nitrogen cryostats or potential issues filling with liquid nitrogen during experiments. Scintillator detectors do, however, have a significantly poorer energy resolution than that for semiconductor detectors like HPGe detectors, as shown in Figure 3.8. This is because of the energy required to produce a scintillation photon compared to that required for semiconductor counterparts. This means that the number of charge carriers per interaction is significantly less for scintillators giving poorer energy resolution. It is because of this that semiconductor detectors are preferred in γ -ray spectroscopy when the accurate measurement of the energy of a transition is required.

Figure 3.8: A comparison of two γ -ray spectra for the detection of natural background as measured by NaI(Tl) and HPGe detectors for one million seconds. This figure is taken from Ref. [100]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

The use of an inorganic scintillator material instead of an organic material is, as mentioned, dependent on what radiation or particle is required to be detected. Similarly, the choice of crystalline materials used to create the inorganic scintillator detector is dependent on the sensitivity required on the timing and energy. Common examples of scintillator materials for γ spectroscopy are NaI(Tl), CsI(Tl), CsI(Na), or BGO. Each of these have various advantages and disadvantages compared to the others and the decision of which material to use is experiment dependent. One of the most common materials is NaI(Tl) which has excellent light yield

and close to linear response to electrons and γ rays between 100 - 1000 keV [94], meaning that the light output of the scintillator is roughly proportional to the energy of the incident radiation. Using scintillators made from NaI(Tl) suffers, however, with a scintillation pulse of 230 ns, which is too long for applications of fast timing or high counting. A relatively new material being used for scintillation detectors is LaBr₃(Ce) which has improved energy and timing resolutions (sub-nanoseconds) compared to NaI(Tl) and CsI materials. The fast timing resolutions can allow measurements of electromagnetic transition strengths between excited nuclear states, which are used to measure multipolarities and as a result the spins and parities of nuclear states [99, 101].

Chapter 4

Experimental Setup

This chapter discusses the details of the apparatus used during the experiment, starting with the accelerator and ion source used, then moving onto the individual detectors. After this, details specific to this experiment are included.

4.1 Accelerator and Ion Source

In the work discussed here the beam was delivered by the Tandem-ALPI complex at the Legnaro National Laboratory (LNL) in Italy. The main details of the accelerators are further discussed in this section.

4.1.1 Tandem-XTU Accelerator

The Tandem-XTU Van de Graaff accelerator at LNL has a maximum voltage of 14.5 MV. The tank is filled with sulphur hexafluoride (SF_6) at 7 atmospheres. Ions generated from an external source are passed through the two-step tandem acceleration system. At the exit of the tandem the particles are passed through a series of focusing elements before being driven to either the ALPI accelerator for further acceleration to higher energies or to the experimental hall.

4.1.2 Acceleratore Lineare Per Ioni - ALPI

The name ALPI is an acronym of Acceleratore Lineare Per Ioni - Linear accelerator for ions. ALPI is a linear superconducting accelerator which is used to further accelerate beams from the Tandem-XTU. The ALPI cryostats that contain the accelerating cavities are maintained at near absolute zero temperatures (-269°),

allowing operation in the superconducting regime [102]. Taking advantage of the low resistivity of the niobium cavities used for acceleration to alternating currents at these temperatures, the ALPI accelerator has an increased energy efficiency when compared to accelerating cavities operating at room temperature due to a higher maximum operating electromagnetic field. Cryostats are used to contain four accelerating cavities, acting to thermally isolate the cavities. Liquid nitrogen is used in the cryostat to retain the critical temperature required to provide superconducting conditions.

The cavities are of the Quarter Wave Resonator (QWR) type with one end being short-circuited, giving regions where the RF magnetic field is at a maximum and other regions where the electric field is a maximum. The first cavities, labelled as low- β resonators, operate at 80 MHz with the second group, medium- β , operating at 160 MHz providing an accelerating field of 5 MV/m and the third, high- β group, operating at 240 MHz. The respective properties of the three resonators are detailed in Table 1 of Ref. [103]. The Tandem-XTU-ALPI complex is able to accelerate ions from ^{12}C to ^{197}Au with an equivalent high voltage of $V_{eq} = 45\text{-}52\text{ MV}$. For ion beams with an atomic mass larger than 100, the Positive Ion Accelerator for Very Low velocity ions (PIAVE) linac was developed [104]. PIAVE can also be used as the ion source for ALPI instead of the Tandem-XTU.

4.2 AGATA: Advanced Gamma Tracking Array

AGATA is the Advanced Gamma Tracking Array. AGATA is a new type of γ -ray spectrometer in which scattered γ rays are tracked and their positions and energies are reconstructed. The full AGATA array will have unprecedented sensitivity to γ -ray detection - an improvement of several orders of magnitude over earlier γ -ray spectrometers. The significant improvement in resolving power is achieved by analysis of complex data involving pulse-shape analysis to determine interaction positions followed by tracking to reconstruct the scattered γ rays. This section introduces the motivation to build AGATA, the general concept of AGATA, the design of the AGATA array, the AGATA project, as well as a description of how pulse-shape analysis and tracking are performed.

4.2.1 Motivation

High resolution γ -ray spectroscopy has employed high-purity germanium (HPGe) detectors for almost 50 years to investigate nuclear structure [105, 106]. The introduction of HPGe crystals to detect γ rays provided a much more viable choice than other options such as lithium-drifted germanium Ge(Li) detectors. As an example, HPGe detectors are able to be stored at room temperature and can also be made from n-type materials, which are less sensitive to neutron damage than p-type materials. Due to the many improvements over

previous detection systems, HPGe are used in γ -ray spectroscopy. A major drawback of early full solid-angle coverage germanium arrays was the inability to distinguish between two γ rays measured in adjacent detectors and a single γ ray interacting in one detector and Compton scattering into the adjacent detectors [106, 107]. Without creating a 4π array of over 1000 detectors, which would be costly, the only solution to this limitation was the precise measurement of the position, energy, and time of every γ -ray interaction in the detector material through γ -ray tracking, therefore increasing the detection efficiency to a greater extent than could be achieved with previous arrays [8, 9, 107]. This technique relies upon the segmentation of the detector material.

Photolithography enables the electrical segmentation of the outer electrical contact of the HPGe detector crystal, allowing each segment to provide distinct signals to the output electronics. The process results in segments with a gap of less than $200\ \mu\text{m}$ between one another, improving the detector granularity and allowing the reduction of γ -ray broadening due to the Doppler effect (see Section 3.5.3) [108, 109]. Due to the amount of active material compared to the size of the dead layer, the closed-end n-type coaxial Ge detectors are considered to be the best choice for the desired applications [106].

4.2.2 AGATA Design

The full AGATA array is designed to have 180 tapered hexagonal HPGe crystals arranged into 60 triple clusters. This design allows the crystals to fit together to form a large sphere. Each crystal within a cluster has an asymmetric hexagonal shape that fits together with others to almost completely cover the spherical surface. The drawings of the crystal geometries, shown in Figure 4.1, are taken from Ref. [8].

The three crystal geometries that form an AGATA triple cluster shown in Figure 4.1 are indicated by the blue, green, and red colours with each colour being slightly different in size and shape from the others. Each triple cluster is then formed of a red, green and blue detector in order for the best solid angle coverage. The maximisation of the solid angle coverage is an important design factor to consider when aiming to achieve a good detection efficiency. The utilization of this setup is predicted to allow for a solid angle coverage of 82% and 43% efficiency for a 1 MeV photon when the full AGATA array is completed [8]. The crystals themselves are made from high purity n-type germanium and are tapered and also highly segmented. The segmentation is a key aspect of the AGATA detector array. Each crystal is divided into 6 azimuthal and 6 longitudinal segments giving a total of 36 segments for each crystal and with the addition of a central core signal, providing 37 output signals per crystals. The segmentation is shown in Figure 4.2. The longitudinal segmentation into segments with the dimensions specified in Figure 4.1 are optimised for the best pulse-shape

Figure 4.1: The three different crystal geometries of the AGATA spectrometer that together form a triple cluster. The bottom right diagram shows the depth of each crystal with the dashed lines indicated the six segments of the crystals. Dimensions shown are in millimeters [8]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

sensitivity and uniform γ -ray interactions. The segmentation allows for the reconstruction of γ -ray events using the γ -ray tracking algorithm.

4.2.3 Data Acquisition

The AGATA spectrometer data acquisition (DAQ) system is designed to receive and process preamplifier signals through several stages before being stored. The DAQ receives these signals from the front-end electronics (FEE) which are used to digitise and process the signals in real time to determine when a γ ray is detected in the crystals. The FEE are also used to determine the energy deposited in the crystals and to give the interaction a timestamp.

The chain of data flow applies algorithms needed to interpret interaction point information and is shown in Figure 4.3. After the FEE signals are received, Pulse-Shape Analysis (PSA) is conducted. This is performed

Figure 4.2: The AGATA crystal segmentation into 6 sectors consisting each of 6 segments. [8]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

with data from all crystals which are subsequently merged depending on the AGATA triggers applied. A trigger can be a signal in one of the AGATA detectors, an ancillary detector connected to the AGATA spectrometer, or both. These triggers can apply specific conditions on variables such as the timestamp, therefore applying selectivity on the merging of the data. After the merging of the data, tracking is performed to reconstruct γ -ray events. The reconstructed events are then stored on a local disk.

Due to the high counting rates per crystal of around 50 kHz and the required processing power for such rates, the data processing for the PSA is carried out on several computers to speed up the analysis, resulting in around 400 MB/s per crystal received from the FEE [8]. The data acquisition system, called Narval, uses algorithms called actors, which apply specific processes to receive and transmit data at any stage of the data flow [110]. A specific configuration of actors is called a topology and different topologies are applied throughout the analysis to process the data according to the users input. Narval is connected via the AGATA

Figure 4.3: A schematic representation of the layout of the AGATA data acquisition system, taken from Ref. [8] Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

spectrometer Data Flow (ADF) library interface to the PSA and tracking algorithms.

4.2.4 Pulse-Shape Analysis

The pulse-shape analysis (PSA) technique allows the extraction of the deposited energy and location of γ -ray interactions with the detector material by utilizing the measurement of the waveforms which arise from the charge collection in the detector segments.

Due to the high event rate observed in the crystals, and the corresponding digitizer data rate, the determination of pulse shapes for all interaction points in real time is unrealistic with the current accessible computing power. Instead PSA employs a comparison between measured pulse shapes and several reference pulse shapes, which are determined through simulations, in order to determine several key parameters by identifying the most comparable pulse shape to the reference pulse shape and therefore the most probable interaction point. The determined parameters include the interaction position, energy, and time. Therefore, the PSA algorithms that are in place must be sufficiently developed to measure the positions and energies in real time in order to be effective. Various algorithms have been tested for a multitude of event types with the adaptive grid search being the most popular algorithm [111]. The segment is subdivided using a conceptual grid, where each section has a simulated signal. The adaptive grid search algorithm provides a first interaction position within a grid of length 6 mm per grid point, then a second grid of length 2 mm per grid point is applied around

the first interaction position [111]. Using this algorithm the PSA can achieve an energy-dependent position resolution for the γ -ray interaction of the order of a few millimetres.

4.2.5 Gamma-ray Tracking

The implementation of γ -ray tracking relies on the use of segmented germanium crystals and PSA in order to reconstruct the event as each interaction of the γ ray can be detected in a different segment. By using digital sampling electronics to extract time, energy and position information, the tracking algorithm is applied to correlate signals in separate segments to determine which events are linked, allowing the reconstruction of the full energy of the initial γ ray. This technique improves the efficiency of the detection system by specifying the direction of emission of an individual γ ray which is crucial for good Doppler correction and hence energy resolution in the in-beam experiment. The γ -ray tracking technique negates the requirement for a Compton suppression system due to the reconstruction of the full energy of the γ ray using the tracking algorithm. This increases the usable solid angle allowing more coverage with germanium detectors, hence improving the overall detection efficiency [112].

The tracking algorithm establishes, firstly, if the event is complete and, secondly, the order in which the measured γ -ray events took place by reconstructing the scattering sequence. This is done by comparison with predicted Compton scattering angular cross sections, since this is the dominant interaction mechanism for the photon in the range 150 keV to 10 MeV [8]. In order to determine the order of the scattering sequence the tracking array can employ two different tracking algorithms; forward tracking and clusterisation, or backwards tracking. It is accepted that forward-tracking algorithms are more efficient than backward-tracking algorithms [112]. Using PSA and tracking, simulations have provided resolution estimates of less than 5 mm and 3 keV (at ~ 1 MeV) for the position and energy of the detected γ ray, respectively [106, 112–114].

4.2.5.1 Forward Tracking and Clusterisation

The algorithm of choice in the majority of cases is the Orsay Forward Tracking algorithm (OFT).

Forward tracking and clusterisation follows three steps. First, the interaction points are grouped into clusters in (θ, ϕ) space. Then the correct sequence of interactions is chosen depending on the best figure of merit (FoM) value, which is used to quantify the efficacy of the algorithm. To begin, the grouping of the interaction points is constrained by a maximum angular separation, α_{max} , between any sequence of points given by,

$$\alpha_{max} = \cos^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{2}{\left(\frac{n_{int}+2}{3} \right)^{0.9}} \right), \quad (4.1)$$

where n_{int} is the number of interactions [115]. The OFT algorithm searches for events within this maximum separation and considers points within an angle, α , of an interaction point to be within the same γ -ray interaction cluster if it satisfies the relationship,

$$| \cos^{-1} (\sin\theta_j \sin\theta_i \cos(\phi_j - \phi_i) + \cos\theta_i \cos\theta_j) | \leq \alpha. \quad (4.2)$$

The figure of merit is determined by comparing measured and theoretical interaction energies whilst considering Compton scattering rules. For a sequence of interactions the total FoM is given by,

$$\text{FoM} = \left\{ \prod_{n=1}^{N-1} P_n \exp \left(-\frac{\alpha(E_{s,p} - E_{s,e})^2}{\sigma_c^2} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2N-1}}, \quad (4.3)$$

where P_n is the probability for Compton or photoelectric interaction, σ_E is the uncertainty on the scattered energies arising from the uncertainty on the position of the interaction points, $E_{s,p}$ is the scattered energy measured from the interaction point energy, and $E_{s,e}$ is the scattered energy measured using the scattering angle from the Compton scattering formula, which can be written as,

$$E_{s,e} = \frac{E_\gamma}{1 + \frac{E_\gamma}{m_0 c^2} (1 - \cos(\theta))}. \quad (4.4)$$

The final step in forward tracking is then to accept or reject γ -ray interaction clusters depending on the sequence that best maximises the FoM. The maximum FoM value is then compared to an absolute limit which is used to decide if the event is good or not. It is found that forward-tracking algorithms are more efficient than back-tracking due to the fact that back tracking algorithms rely on the identification of the last interaction point which is hard to determine after pulse-shape analysis and also due to the fact that the photon deposits increasingly less amounts of energy as the number of interaction points increases giving close proximity between the final interaction points, thus making it harder to determine the interaction sequence. [8, 112, 116].

4.2.5.2 Back Tracking

Another algorithm that can be applied considers the final interaction point of the γ ray and works backwards to determine interaction points within the specific energy range to find the initial interaction and therefore

determine the scattering sequence. It can be summarised in four steps. Firstly, within the γ -ray event the algorithm sorts all interaction points by increasing energy and determines the distances between points. The second interaction point is determined to be that with the smallest distance to the first point and is confirmed using the expected photoelectric range in germanium for a photon, as explained in Ref. [112]. The incident direction of the photon is determined using,

$$\cos(\theta) = 1 - m_e c^2 \left(\frac{1}{E_{sc}} - \frac{1}{E_{in}} \right), \quad (4.5)$$

where E_{sc} is the energy deposited at the final interaction point, m_e is the mass of an electron, and E_{in} is the sum of the energies deposited at the final and penultimate interaction points [112]. The last step is repeated to find all previous interaction points until the initial source information is determined, Figure 4.4 shows this schematically. The performance of backtracking was evaluated through GEANT4 simulations using a solid sphere of germanium as explained in Ref. [116]. Here, the interaction points of a single γ ray of energy 1.33 MeV are calculated. A peak-to-total ratio of 0.421 is obtained, which, when compared to the simulation without tracking, gave a peak-to-total ratio of 0.736 [115, 116]. The discrepancy in the ratio is accredited to the fact that the γ rays that do not deposit all their energy in one interaction, and therefore do not contribute towards single-interaction events, increasing the background.

Figure 4.4: A schematic representation of the backtracking process including the interaction points i , j , and k taken from Ref. [116, 117].

4.3 Detector Array for multi-Nucleon Transfer Ejectiles

The Detector Array for multi-Nucleon Transfer Ejectiles (DANTE) micro-channel plate (MCP) array is a position-sensitive, heavy-ion ancillary detector. DANTE consists of several detector units that allow position and timing measurements of the reaction products [118, 119]. The modular aspect of the DANTE detector array allows up to eight MCP detectors to be placed around the target position at different angles as required by the reaction. Each detector provides a timing signal that can be used for precise time-of-flight (ToF)

measurements. Individually, the modules have a Mylar foil entrance windows which produce electrons from the interaction with the emitted ions [120]. The electrons then interact with the MCPs which provide a timing signal and two position signals, x and y using a delay-line readout. The MCP can achieve position and timing resolutions of 1 mm and 130 ps, respectively [119]. The design was employed to maximise the detection efficiency of the reaction products and improve the selectivity of the data through coincidence events of AGATA-DANTE, DANTE-PRISMA, or AGATA-DANTE-PRISMA. The timing signal of the MCP of DANTE that can be placed opposite the entrance of PRISMA can be used for a comparison of ToF values between the PRISMA separator and DANTE to apply selectivity on the different reaction mechanisms and hence the resulting coincident γ rays. In particular, DANTE is effective when employed in the removal of events arising from target-like reaction products, which have high fission probabilities. An example of the DANTE detector array in place around the target position is shown in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: A picture of the DANTE detector array mounted at the target position taken during this experiment, with three MCP detectors in place within the holder. Also shown are thin sheets of aluminium placed across half of the face of the MCPs in order to reduce the high count rates experienced in the experiment.

4.4 Lanthanum Bromide Detectors

Cerium-doped lanthanum bromide ($\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$) detectors offer a timing resolution of the order of sub-nanoseconds and high detection efficiency of high energy γ rays [121]. These properties make $\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$ detectors an appropriate ancillary detector when conducting measurements of nucleic lifetimes in conjunction with semiconductor detectors like HPGe. A picture of $\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$ detectors in place at INFN-LNL is shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: A picture of nine $\text{LaBr}_3(\text{Ce})$ detectors around the target position at INFN-LNL. Also pictured are the target chamber and AGATA crystals for reference.

4.5 PRISMA: Large Solid Angle Magnetic Spectrometer

The PRISMA magnetic spectrometer can be used in combination with the AGATA spectrometer to detect heavy-ions for nuclear structure studies [122]. The PRISMA spectrometer consists of four parts; the micro-channel plate entrance detector (MCP), the quadrupole-dipole magnets, the Multi-Wire Parallel-Plate Avalanche Counter (MWPPAC), and the Ionization Chamber (IC). A schematic representation of PRISMA is shown in Figure 4.7 which includes the approximate sizes of the component parts.

Figure 4.7: A schematic representation of the PRISMA magnetic spectrometer, with each section labelled, taken from Ref. [123, 124]. The distances given are not to scale.

4.5.1 Large-Area Micro-Channel Plate Entrance Detector

The micro-channel plate entrance detector (MCP) provides a time signal as well as the x and y positions of using a position-sensitive anode. The MCP has a high counting rate meaning that it can be placed close to the target position where ordinarily high background is measured from charged particles and other unwanted processes. Due to the positioning of the detector, it is able to cover the whole solid angle of the spectrometer. A diagram of the setup is shown in Figure 4.8. The ions first pass through a gold-plated tungsten wire grid before passing through a second inner grid, which is a thin carbon foil biased to $\simeq -2300$ V, causing secondary electrons to be emitted. The emitted electrons are accelerated up to 300 eV at a backwards angle towards the two $80 \times 100 \text{ mm}^2$ MCP detectors via the inner grid. A parallel magnetic field is applied through the external coils in order to limit the spread of the electron cloud, therefore preserving the position information. The electrons reach the MCP surface and undergo multiplication, providing charge carriers which are collected by the position-sensitive anode [125]. The ions finally pass through the outer grid, which is used to balance the forces on the carbon foil, and continue through the spectrometer.

Figure 4.8: Top: A schematic of the micro-channel plate detector from above, taken from Ref. [125]. The carbon foil centre is at 25cm from the target. Bottom: A picture of the MCP, taken from Ref. [125].

4.5.2 Magnetic Optics

After passing through the MCP entrance detector, the reaction products pass through a quadrupole-dipole setup which separates them based on their charge and momentum. The quadrupole magnet is 50 cm downstream of the target and has a maximum field of 0.85 T. The quadrupole magnet focuses in the vertical plane whilst defocusing in the horizontal plane. As a result, the ions exiting the quadrupole magnet are diverging significantly. The dipole magnet is used to transmit reaction products to the focal plane detectors 320 cm downstream. The front face of the dipole magnet is 160 cm downstream of the target and the maximum magnetic rigidity of the dipole magnet is set to 1.2 Tm considering a field of 1 T and a bending radius of 1.2 m. The two magnets are shown in Figure 4.7.

Due to the large acceptance of the PRISMA spectrometer, limitations are placed on the modification of the focusing and profiling of the magnetic optics. This means that optical aberrations are inherent in the resulting A/q and mass distributions. With no physical hardware correction for these effects, the trajectory of the ions is reconstructed during the analysis using the time, position and energy signals from the detectors part of the PRISMA spectrometer.

4.5.3 Multi-Wire Parallel-Plate Avalanche Counter

After exiting the dipole magnet, the ions pass through the Multi-Wire Parallel-Plate Avalanche Counter which provides x - y positions and timing. The MWPPAC acts as the ‘start’ of the time-of-flight (ToF) measurements, with the delayed MCP as the ‘stop’, since a particle passing through the MCP but not the MWPPAC would not be considered as an event. As shown in Figure 4.7, the focal plane of the PRISMA spectrometer is tilted 60° with respect to the central trajectory, with the MWPPAC and IC placed orthogonal to the central trajectory. In order to match the acceptance of the PRISMA spectrometer, the MWPPAC is 100 cm wide, 13 cm high, and has three electrodes; the x plane, y plane, and the central cathode enclosed in two $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ Mylar foil support windows on either end of the detector [126]. Both the x -plane anode and the central cathode are split into 10 sections, with gold-plated tungsten wires placed across the detector. The wires are separated by 0.33 mm in the cathode and 1 mm in the x -plane anode. The y -plane anode is not segmented as with the x -plane and has 130 wires spaced 1 mm apart with the wires placed two-by-two. A position resolution of 1 mm in the x -plane and 2 mm in the y -plane is obtainable via a delay-line readout [127, 128]. A picture of the MWPPAC at the focal plane of PRISMA is shown in Figure 4.9.

The MWPPAC detector chamber is filled with a gas which is ionised when the reaction products pass through the MWPPAC. Liberated electrons are accelerated to the anodes under influence of an external electric field and the positive ions are accelerated to the central cathode which is negatively biased at 500 - 600 V. The collected charge produces a signal which is processed and eventually provides the x , y position. The timing signal is measured by the wires in the cathode. A timing resolution of 300 - 400 ps and $\sim 100\%$ efficiency is achievable for heavy ions.

4.5.4 Ionisation Chamber

The Ionization Chamber (IC) is located 60 cm downstream of the MWPPAC. The IC is used to obtain measurements of energy, E , and energy loss, ΔE . The IC can be filled with different types of gas at different pressures, depending on the reaction being used in the experiment. From the measurement of E and ΔE , the identification of the atomic number of the ion is possible. Using this and the position and time information

obtained by the MCP and MWPPAC, the mass-to-charge ratio can be found, allowing the complete identification of a nuclide.

The IC detector has dimensions $120 \times 110 \times 20 \text{ cm}^3$ and is split into 10 longitudinal sections, which are perpendicular to the focal plane, as shown in Figure 4.7. The 10 sections match those of the MWPPAC, and there are also two side sections, labelled A and B, which are used to veto trajectories that escape the active volume. In addition, the detector is split along its depth into four sections, giving a total of 48 anode and

Figure 4.9: A picture of the PRISMA magnetic spectrometer in place at INFN-LNL. Here the focal plane detectors are indicated by A (MWPPAC) and B (IC), taken from Refs. [129, 130].

The reaction products first pass through a Mylar window which has thickness $1.5 \mu\text{m}$, in order to separate the gas from the vacuum, after which they ionise the gas, therefore losing energy until they are stopped. The resulting ions and electrons are accelerated to the cathode and anode planes, respectively, where the charge collected is proportional to the energy lost by the reaction products interacting with the gas. Frisch grids

are placed in front of each anode to separate the chamber into a region of ionisation, between the cathode and the grid, and a region of charge collection, between the grid and the anode. In principle this dissociates the dependence of the signal collected from the distance of the ion-electron pair to the anode. As explained in Section 3.4, the Bethe-Bloch formula describes the energy lost through ionisation by charge particles travelling through matter.

4.6 Experimental Details

This thesis concerns the analysis of data taken from an experiment conducted in February 2023 at the Laboratori Nazionali di Legnaro (LNL), which is part of the Istituto Nazionale Fisica Nucleare (INFN). A ^{112}Sn beam was delivered by the Tandem-ALPI accelerator complex and impinged on a ^{238}U target of 1 mg cm^{-2} thickness. A niobium fronting was applied to the target for stabilisation. The resulting beam-like multi-nucleon transfer reaction products were selected using the PRISMA magnetic separator which was placed at the grazing angle of 56° . The summed signals from the first two rows of the IC of PRISMA were selected to give the energy loss, ΔE , with the sum of all four rows providing the total energy E . The MWPPAC was filled with isobutane gas (C_4H_{10}) and the IC was filled with carbon tetrafluoride (CF_4) at a pressure of 26 mbar. Target-like multi-nucleon reaction products were detected with the DANTE detector array consisting of three $40 \times 60 \text{ mm}^2$ units mounted at the target position, surrounding the ^{238}U target. One detector was placed opposite the entrance of the PRISMA spectrometer for the application of DANTE-PRISMA event selection, while the other two were positioned facing each other, as shown in Figure 4.7, for DANTE-DANTE event selection. The PRISMA-aligned detector was placed at an angle as calculated by two-body kinematics, considering the grazing angle for beam-like reaction products entering the PRISMA spectrometer. The prompt coincident γ rays were detected with the AGATA detector array, consisting of 34 operational detector crystals. Nine LaBr_3 detectors were placed around the target position for the purpose of lifetime measurements when observing coincidences with the AGATA spectrometer. However, during the analysis it became apparent that the identification of nuclear lifetimes was not possible and therefore a detailed discussion of these detectors is not included in Section 4.4.

In total, the experiment ran for 10 days of beam time. The total amount of data collected in this experiment corresponding to useful events was $\sim 1.5 \text{ TB}$. The data have been analysed using the ROOT data-analysis framework and laboratory specific software [131]. The useful events correspond to $\sim 72\%$ of the total experiment time, with the other $\sim 28\%$ arising from time between runs and test runs that produced no usable data.

Chapter 5

Data Analysis

This chapter focuses on the data processing and results obtained from the use of the detectors described in Chapter 4, beginning with the AGATA spectrometer post-PSA analysis, followed by analysis of the data from the PRISMA spectrometer detectors, and finally the analysis of the DANTE detectors. After this, coincidence analysis to apply further selectivity to the dataset is shown. The online analysis is performed using a software framework called Narval that uses algorithms called actors to process the raw data [110]. Figure 5.1 shows a diagram of the workflow of the Narval actors including the analysis stages of the AGATA spectrometer and the merging of the AGATA and ancillary detectors.

5.1 The AGATA Spectrometer

This section outlines the steps which are required to produce γ -ray spectra from the AGATA spectrometer.

5.1.1 Pre-processing Corrections

As described in Ref. [132], pre-processing corrections are applied before the data are passed through the Pulse-Shape Analysis (PSA) algorithm (see Section 4.2.4). The first step is to perform energy calibrations, as would be done when using any HPGe detectors. Secondly, time alignments are performed so that the signal from the segments and the core are aligned before the PSA algorithm is applied. Lastly, due to the segmentation of the AGATA spectrometer detector crystals, signals can be induced in neighbouring segments where an event is detected in another segment. Therefore, a correction is applied to account for this *cross-talk*. Although the pre-processing corrections are all applied online, it is worth briefly discussing them here

Figure 5.1: Diagram of the workflow of the Narval actors. This figure is taken from Refs. [129, 130].

for the sake of continuity and completeness.

5.1.1.1 Initial Energy Calibration

After an interaction within the detector crystal, the collected signal is processed using digitisers which extract a signal amplitude through the application of trapezoidal filters. The resulting amplitude is used for the energy calibration. When applying the trapezoidal filter, two parameters can be adjusted, which are based on the detector rate and the crystal used, to optimize the filter applied to the amplitude. These parameters are the shaping-time and the pole-zero which are related to the decay-time and rise-time of the detector, respectively. The calibration is performed using software developed for the calibration of the detectors of the AGATA spectrometer (see Appendix A.1.1) to identify transitions from the decay of known radioactive sources. It is noted that there are some dead segments which have to be dealt with manually when processing

the correction.

After the calibration has been performed the fitted parameters for each detector are entered into a configuration file. These parameters are applied before the PSA algorithm is applied.

5.1.1.2 Time Alignment

The second pre-processing correction to be made is the time alignment of the segment signals to the core. The PSA determines the position of the γ -ray interaction point by comparing the pulse shapes with a database containing known interaction points that are assigned to pulse shapes. Therefore, it is important that the time alignment is performed before the application of the PSA algorithm so that there is not an offset between segment and core values which would provide a poor PSA result. An example of the aligned core time peak is shown in Figure 5.2. This spectrum is obtained after an event is registered as a set of 38 waveforms (segments plus core) from an AGATA crystal, then digital shaping is applied to the obtained pulses from which the peak of the signal is determined to give the time signal. The same program used to perform the initial energy calibration is used to perform this alignment but with different options. These options select the biggest peak in the spectrum and apply a shift to align it to the given channel number. The spectrum is also re-binned after the shift based on overlaps between old and new bin boundaries.

Figure 5.2: Time signal peak for segment 15 of crystal 06A before (red) and after (black) the online time alignment.

5.1.1.3 Cross-talk Correction

The segmentation of the crystals of the AGATA spectrometer causes individual segments to be coupled via the capacitance of the bulk germanium material. This creates an electronic network between the segments,

leading to an observable cross-talk effect, which can cause a signal detected from a γ -ray interaction in one segment to be detected in a neighbouring segment causing a degradation of the centroid and resolution of the measured γ -ray energies [133]. The shift in the measured γ -ray energies and the energy resolution are linearly dependent on the multiplicity of firing segments, meaning that events with a high segment multiplicity can cause a significant decrease in the accuracy of the resulting peak centroid and the full-width half maximum (FWHM) values. An example of such deterioration is seen in Figure 5.3 where transitions from a ^{60}Co source were used to measure the dependence of the energy resolution on the segment multiplicity. As shown in the figure, an increase in the segment fold leads to a continual decrease in both the resolution and centroid of the measured γ -ray energy. To recover precision in both these quantities, it is necessary to account for the cross-talk effect.

Figure 5.3: The segment sum energy peaks for the $E_\gamma = 1332.5$ -keV transition from a ^{60}Co source with increasing segment fold. For every increasing fold the peak position shifts by 2.32 keV and the peak width decreases by 0.5 keV. This test was done using the AGATA detector crystal S001 in a single test cryostat. The percentages provide a fold distribution, e.g. only 38% of the detected γ rays contribute to the two-fold photopeak. This figure was taken from Ref. [134]. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

In order to correct for the cross-talk effects, a model is applied based on matrix formalism. To start, the measured energies, E_{meas} , and the correct energies, E_{true} , can be related through,

$$E_{meas} = \mathbf{B} \cdot E_{true}, \quad (5.1)$$

where \mathbf{B} represents a non-symmetric matrix which accounts for the observed distortions to the energy spectrum arising from cross-talk and other accountable effects. The matrix elements, also called cross-talk parameters, can be determined using two methods which are further detailed in Ref. [133, 134]. To apply cross-talk corrections, the first step is to establish calibration coefficients, which are verified by the in-built software in order to generate cross-talk spectra, which are then processed to determine cross-talk coefficients. This software is detailed in Appendix A.1.1. The matrix of coefficients is then inverted and applied to the spectra to perform the correction. By applying this procedure it is possible to recover one broken or missing segment per crystal. Provided that more than one segment is affected, the core signal cannot be used to recover the energies of the segments.

5.1.1.4 Unstable Segments

The segments of detector crystals have the potential to become lost, broken, or unstable, resulting in the detection of inaccurate signals and, as a result, a poor energy centroid and FWHM. Three possibilities are explained here. In the case of a lost segment, the resulting spectra indicate that the segment has collected no signal, despite physical charge collection. A common reason for this is that the connection between the crystal pre-amplifier and the digitizer is faulty [135]. A broken segment results in charge that is not collected in the segment, to be collected in neighbouring segments leading to a peak centred at a lower energy in the core. Lastly, in the case of unstable segments, the signal is collected, however, a potential effect is that the resulting energy will shift with time, which propagates in the spectrum as two structures which look similar but have different gains applied.

These effects can be accounted for by comparing the sum of the segment signals to the core signal. Since the summed energy of the segments is equal to the energy of the core, a crystal with one lost segment can be easily recovered via the difference between core and sum of segment energies. If a crystal has multiple problematic segments it is only possible to recover one segment, meaning that the remaining charge is uncollected and an incomplete event is recorded. Unstable segments can be approximated as a lost segment by setting the gain to zero, provided the other segments in the crystal work as expected. If there are more than one unstable or broken segments then the core signal cannot be used for recovery.

5.1.2 PSA Corrections

After the pre-processing has been applied, pulse shape analysis (PSA) is used to extract the shapes of the signals measured in the AGATA detectors. The details of how this works have already been covered in Section 4.2.4, however, it is worth mentioning that the PSA results are highly dependent on the results of the pre-processing stage.

5.1.3 Post-PSA Corrections

After the PSA process has been applied, final corrections at the local level are applied to prepare the data for applications with ancillary detectors. The stages of post-PSA corrections are discussed below.

5.1.3.1 Neutron-Damage Correction

The utilisation of a segmented detector crystal allows a correction to be performed to account for the damage to the crystal lattice of the detector material by incident radiation.

In an ideal case, a detector crystal forms a perfect lattice, facilitating the easy movement of charge carriers. This enables efficient collection of these carriers and accurate signal measurement from interactions within the detector material. In reality, however, damage to the crystalline structure is inevitable. In the case of incident radiation like γ rays or electrons, minimal damage is caused to the detector material at relatively high energies [94]. However, this is not the case for heavier radiation, such as fast neutrons. Here, the incident radiation causes a number of lattice atoms to be displaced from their origin, hence creating multiple atom vacancies which, along with the original displaced atoms, form trapping sites for charge carriers leading to incomplete charge collection and an inaccurate signal measurement. The effect of neutron damage in the detector crystal manifests as a left-hand tail on the full-energy peak in the resulting spectrum, which can cause a significant decrease in the energy resolution.

Ordinarily, these defects are permanent and the only way to remove them is through annealing [94, 136]. However, this process is time consuming and means the detector is unusable during the process. Annealing is often implemented at the end of experimental campaigns which, due to the continued irradiation of the detector material, can significantly reduce the charge collection efficiency of the detection system as the campaign progresses. The application of the highly-segmented germanium crystals can, however, provide an alternative method to combat damage specifically from fast neutrons. The segmentation of the detector crystal, and therefore the application of Pulse-shape Analysis (PSA), allow the effects of neutron damage to be accounted for, improving the energy resolution of the detector. To correct for these effects, the shape of

the signals from the PSA is used to determine the mean-free path of the charge carriers for each segment. The shape of the signal is then corrected depending if the path of the charge carriers differs from some nominal value inside the detector material [137]. In cases of extreme damage to the crystal, the core contact can be used to recover the signal from a segment, as the sum of all segment energies equals the core contact energy. This is supported by the fact that the core is less sensitive to neutron damage due to the fact that hole trapping is more dominant than electron trapping for n-type HPGe detectors. Since γ -ray interactions mostly happen far from the core electrode, meaning the holes have to travel short distances before being collected at the outer electrodes, the core is less sensitive to incomplete charge collection and therefore neutron damage.

During the analysis process, the effects caused by neutron damage are corrected to obtain a significantly improved photopeak resolution. To correct the energies of the peaks observed from the source materials, software is employed which takes the PSA positional information and determines a set of optimum correction parameters that minimize the FWHM and the tail on the left of the energy peaks in the spectrum (see Appendix A.1.2) [138]. Then, another correction is performed to account for possible shifts induced from the neutron-damage correction. An example of the energy peaks of a ^{60}Co source before and after neutron-damage correction process has been applied is shown in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: Segment 15 of crystal 00A before (red) and after (black) the neutron-damage correction process has been applied. The full-energy peaks of the 1173-keV γ ray and 1332-keV γ ray are shown from a ^{60}Co source run performed after the experiment. Here, a gain of 1.25 was applied during the correction process and so the 1332-keV peak is seen at channel 1665.

5.1.3.2 Final Energy Re-calibration

A final recalibration of the AGATA spectrometer crystal segments is performed in addition to the energy calibration performed at the end of the neutron-damage correction process. This is done with additional offsets and a ^{152}Eu source run to account for the non-linearity of the individual detectors which were not included in the previous calibrations. After the final recalibration has been performed it is possible to compare the resulting source spectra before the post-PSA corrections, after the neutron-damage corrections, and after the neutron-damage corrections with the final energy calibration for both the core and segment signals. Shown in Figure 5.5, the 1408-keV transition from ^{152}Eu is shown before and after the final energy calibration. Here, the comparison between the spectrum after the neutron-damage correction process and the spectrum after the neutron-damage correction and final energy calibration is observed. It is noted that the statistics differ from that shown in Figure 5.4 due to a different sample of data being used for the recalibration process and a different source being used.

Figure 5.5: A γ -ray energy spectrum from the decay of a ^{152}Eu source showing the 1408-keV peak from a segment of crystal 00A for multiple stages of the correction process. Here, the signal after the neutron-damage correction process has been applied is shown in red and the black signal represents the result after the neutron-damage correction and final energy re-calibration have been applied.

5.1.3.3 Force Segments to Core

After the application of the neutron-damage correction and energy calibration, the signals from the segments are either chosen to be forced to the fraction of the core signal for each segment, or to retain the current signal. This decision is made by observing the results of the previous two stages. Due to the effect of neutron

Figure 5.6: Time signal peaks for segment 0 in crystal 00A, compared to all other segments for $\sim 6\%$ of the dataset after the global time alignment process has been completed. Here the dotted line indicates channel 500.

damage on the segments of individual crystals, there is a chance that one of the segment signals is lost and/or distorted with respect to the other segments and the expected γ -ray transition energies. In this case, the segment signal is recoverable using the core contact signal. The core signal is simply the sum of the signals of all the segments and as such a missing or lost signal in one segment can be accounted for by the difference between the sum of the segments and the core. In the case where there is more than one segment signal missing, the core signal can no longer be used for recovery. Here, the crystal has to be removed from use by editing it from the topology (see Appendix A.4). In order to check if forcing the signal of the selected segments to the core signal has made an improvement, a comparison between applying the option on the selected crystals and not applying it should be made using the resulting γ -ray spectra.

5.1.3.4 Global Time Alignment

A post-PSA time alignment is performed throughout the dataset after each time that there was a global timestamp failure during the experiment. It is noted that this alignment is independent of the previous corrections and it is therefore not required to be done at the end of the post-PSA analysis. Figure 5.6 shows this alignment for a particular run which constitutes $\sim 6\%$ of the dataset. Here, the alignment of the signals of all segments as measured relative to segment 0 for crystal 00A is shown. The alignment at channel 500 is expected due to the offset applied when applying the correction program. In order to check that the global time alignment has been performed correctly, the signals for all segments as seen by each individual segment must be checked.

5.2 PRISMA Analysis

The analysis of data from the PRISMA spectrometer detectors is complex and requires a methodical approach. The steps are laid out in the following sections of this chapter. Detector calibrations are discussed first, followed by the analytical process which is described in stages. During the analysis process, a run of significant length, consisting of $\sim 6\%$ of the full dataset, was used to perform the necessary steps to determine the required parameters and to perform corrections to arrive at the ultimate mass distributions. The parameters and corrections can then be applied to the whole dataset. It should be assumed that, unless stated otherwise, the figures and results shown in this section are produced using the data from the sample run ($\sim 6\%$ of the dataset).

5.2.1 Detector Calibration

The first step is to set thresholds and apply positional calibrations for the detectors within the PRISMA spectrometer setup.

5.2.1.1 MCP

The Micro-Channel Plate (MCP) detector at the entrance of the PRISMA magnetic spectrometer is used to measure the position and time of ions entering the PRISMA spectrometer. As such, all events should have well defined x , y , and t signals. Using a two-dimensional plot of the x position against the y position, a gate can be placed on the spectrum to remove events arising from misfired triggers or unwanted events which do not have both a well-defined x and y position in the detector. This is shown in the top panel of Figure 5.7. A physical barrier is placed in front of the MCP detector to provide definite reference positions that can be used in the position calibration. The set of reference points are labelled on the top of Figure 5.7 and listed in Table 5.1. The bottom panel of Figure 5.7 shows the calibrated 2D plot of the x position against the y position, with appropriate units. The calibration takes the measured reference positions given by the user and applies a transformation using a series of parameters in several stages to convert the uncalibrated matrix into the one shown in the figure. Further information on the individual steps of the calibration process are detailed in Ref. [123]. Comparing the difference in scale between the top and bottom panels of Figure 5.7 it is shown that by applying the two-dimensional gate a factor of $\sim 10^4$ entries is lost. This is expected due to a significant amount of entries in the top spectrum of Figure 5.7 arising from events that do not have well defined positions or are false-triggers, therefore contributing to the overflow/underflow of the electronics.

Figure 5.7: Top: Raw un-calibrated two-dimensional MCP matrix. As shown the red line indicates the gate applied to remove unwanted events. Bottom: Calibrated two-dimensional MCP matrix showing the cross close to the expected reference points used for calibration.

Position (#)	x [mm]	y [mm]
0	2.62	-2.07
1	1.04	-0.19
2	2.62	1.81
3	4.28	-0.26
4	-10.67	22.04
5	-8.02	18.74
6	-12.26	15.12
7	-14.82	18.07
8	16.45	22.48
9	20.07	18.71
10	17.37	15.79
11	13.75	19.66
12	19.80	-15.42
13	22.48	-18.27
14	18.76	-21.75
15	16.12	-18.77
16	-13.79	-14.12
17	-9.35	-17.22
18	-11.79	-20.67
19	-16.27	-17.77

Table 5.1: Reference points on the cross placed on the front of the MCP for visual aid.

5.2.1.2 MWPPAC

The Multi-Wire Parallel-Plate Avalanche Counter (MWPPAC), as explained in Section 4.5.3, is a detector at the focal-plane of the PRISMA spectrometer that is used to measure the position and timing of the reaction products that have passed through the magnetic optics, after passing first through the MCP. The signals received from the MWPPAC are used in combination with the MCP for the determination of the time-of-flight (ToF) with the MWPPAC cathode signals commonly used as trigger for the data acquisition [123, 127, 130].

The MWPPAC has a three-electrode structure with a central cathode (*cath*) and *x* and *y* anodes. Both the *cath* and *x* anode electrodes are divided into 10 sections with each of the 10 sections providing signals for the left (x_l), right (x_r), and *cath* wires. In addition, the *y* anode, common to all cathode sections and orthogonal to the *x* anode wires provides two signals, up and down, that are mainly used for the centring of the beam. This gives a total of 32 signals per event. It is the time difference between x_l and x_r signals that allows the determination of the focal-plane position using,

$$x_{\text{FP}} = x_r - x_l. \quad (5.2)$$

Figure 5.8: Left: Raw x_l signal spectrum for segment 4 of the MWPPAC. The red lines shown indicate the threshold lines used to constrain the data. Right: Raw cathode signal spectrum for segment 4 of the MWPPAC. Threshold lines are set loosely here.

The determination of the position of the ions at the focal-plane is used in the reconstruction of their trajectories through the spectrometer. A calibration is performed on each section to achieve a good focal-plane position. Figure 5.8 shows spectra for the x_l and cathode signals for one section of the MWPPAC (Section 4.5.3). A similar distribution to that of x_l is expected for x_r . Thresholds set in the distributions are the result of individual sections only being able to measure one event at one specific time. The majority of events with higher order multiplicity will not contribute to the identification of an interaction. As such, an overflow or underflow is necessary in order to detect a significant amount of the recoiling ions with the thresholds applied being used to account for the higher multiplicity events that are not initially registered. In the case where a x_l or x_r signal is outside the set threshold values, and therefore lost, a recovery can be made using the signal of the cathode since,

$$x_{cath} = x_l + x_r. \quad (5.3)$$

Rearranging this equation therefore gives the value for the left or right signal that is lost. This recovery improves the statistics and therefore the efficiency of the detector. The resulting x_{FP} position distribution is shown in Figure 5.9. The central wires of the segments in the MWPPAC are short-circuited to provide a reference point for each section, this is visible in both the x_l and x_{FP} plots shown. Further calibrations are performed to reduce the impact of noise in the cathode signal.

Figure 5.9: Calibrated x_{FP} distribution. Here a peak can be seen at the centre of each segment from the short circuiting of the central wires.

A plot of the summed anode signals ($x_l + x_r$) against the cathode signal allows a polygonal gate to be applied to remove unwanted counts arising from noise. During the online analysis a simple ‘open’ gate was used to include all values. During the offline analysis a more stringent 2D gate was applied, as shown in Figure 5.10. Under ideal conditions, equation 5.2 is expected to hold giving constant values on the axes of Figure 5.10. In reality however, an event-by-event drift is seen which occurs for all signals, therefore causing deviations from constant values. As shown in Figure 5.10, a gate is applied around the drifted signal data, allowing the inclusion of the drifted signals and removal of all other events.

Figure 5.10: The application of a gate on the matrix of $x_r + x_l$ vs. $x_{cathode}$. This allows the removal of events arising from noise.

5.2.1.3 Ionisation Chamber

As mentioned in Section 4.5.4, the ionisation chamber (IC) is the final detector encountered by ions entering the PRISMA spectrometer. The purpose of the IC is to stop and detect all ions that are transported to the focal plane of PRISMA [130]. The IC measures the total energy (E) and energy loss (ΔE) of the reaction products. By plotting the ΔE for each segment against E , thresholds can be applied to help to select the desired events. Examples of these spectra for some of the segments or ‘pads’ are shown in Figure 5.11. A low-energy peak, due to electrical noise, is visible in all four spectra. Upper and lower thresholds were therefore set for each pad to remove noise; these are represented by the red lines in Figure 5.11. The individual segments of the IC are gainmatched using a pulser which sends signals to each pad from which gain coefficients are obtained.

Figure 5.11: Energy loss for four sections of the IC. The four sections represent the full depth of the chamber with sections A, B, C, and D shown for the second row of 10 segments.

5.2.1.4 Side Sections

As discussed in Section 4.5.4 the IC has a section at each side as well as the 10 central section. The side sections of the ionisation chamber are used as a veto such that if an ion deposits energy in one of the side sections, the event is rejected since its total energy has not been measured within the IC. As is the case for the other IC sections, upper and lower thresholds are applied to the energy loss spectra for individual side sections. The thresholds then provide a region of energy deposition that result in an event being rejected.

Figure 5.12: Energy loss spectra for four side sections. Thresholds are used to exclude noise and the resulting signals are used to veto events.

Examples of energy loss spectra for four side pads are shown in Figure 5.12.

5.2.2 Z Identification

Once the MCP and focal-plane detectors of the PRISMA spectrometer have been calibrated, the next step in the data analysis is the Z identification of ions at the focal plane. Due to the processes involved in the energy loss of charged particles in matter, as discussed in Section 4.5.4, ions with different Z values will have different behaviour in a plot of energy loss (ΔE) against the total energy (E). Here, ΔE corresponds to dE , the energy lost by the reaction products interacting with the gas in the chamber, in the Bethe-Bloch formula (Equation 3.16). To identify the atomic number of the ions, a two-dimensional gate was applied to the plot of ΔE versus E for the first two layers of the ionisation chamber. For this experiment, the energy loss was defined as the sum of energies measured in the first two layers of the chamber, labelled as rows 0 and 1 in Figure 4.7.

As shown in Figure 5.13, characteristic banana-shaped curves are observed. Individually, these represent the atomic numbers of the ions detected in the ionisation chamber. As expected the most intense line corresponds to the tin isotopes ($Z = 50$). Then, with decreasing intensity events from indium ($Z = 49$), cadmium ($Z = 48$),

Figure 5.13: Energy loss in the first two IC layers plotted against the total energy. The atomic numbers of the reaction products are labelled in red.

silver ($Z = 47$), palladium ($Z = 46$), and rhodium ($Z = 45$) reaction products are observed. Figure 5.14 shows the complete spectrum, in which other Z values can be seen. These ions are not only from multi-nucleon transfer but also from fission reactions of the target-like nuclei, as shown by the labels added to the figure. The Z values obtained in this process are used in the subsequent analysis. The separation between the atomic numbers is close due to the small differences in ΔE between adjacent values. An improvement could be made by using different gas in the IC with improved stopping power.

5.2.3 Time-of-Flight Calibration

The time-of-flight (ToF) of the ions passing through the PRISMA spectrometer is determined by the start and stop signals taken from the cathodes of the MWPPAC and delayed time signal of the MCP, respectively. The first step of the calibration is to align the ToF signal throughout all MWPPAC sections. Then, an initial ToF value is estimated which can be later adjusted, if necessary, by observing the in-beam AGATA-PRISMA coincident γ -ray spectra. Since the MWPPAC signals are section dependent, each segment must be aligned with respect to the others in order to accurately measure the ToF of the ions. A plot of the ToF against the x position on the focal-plane as measured in the MWPPAC allows a visualisation of the alignment of the sections from which adjustments can be made to correct the alignment, where necessary. An example of a well-aligned ToF vs. x focal-plane plot is shown in Figure 5.15. Once all sections have been aligned, an

Figure 5.14: Energy loss measured in the first two layers of the IC plotted against the total energy of the reaction products. Here the yellow shape indicates the projectile-like ions that result from multi-nucleon transfer. The red shape indicates reaction products measured arising from fission of the target-like uranium ions. A colour scale has been set for the z-axis to emphasize the different structures.

estimate of the ToF is made by setting an offset to the value within the software calibration file (see Appendix A.2). Knowing that the length of the PRISMA spectrometer, L , is ~ 6.5 m and given an estimate of the velocity of the ions, v , the ToF is given by,

$$ToF = \frac{L}{v}. \quad (5.4)$$

By measuring the centroid of a photopeak from a known transition in the AGATA-PRISMA coincident γ -ray spectra the difference between the observed and expected value can be determined and the ToF offset value can be adjusted (see Section 5.2.6). Using Figure 5.15 the ToF offset value, which has been set in the configuration files of the analysis (see Appendix A.2.1), can be confirmed. Here the ToF is set to ≈ 200 ns.

5.2.4 Ion Identification

5.2.4.1 Trajectory Reconstruction

The ability of the PRISMA spectrometer to select ions in exotic regions of the nuclear chart relies upon good trajectory reconstruction and ion tracking. This is performed using specialised software to estimate the en-

Figure 5.15: Time-of-flight plotted against the x -position at the focal plane as measured by the MWPPAC. The different sections of the focal-plane detector are visible along with the estimated ToF value.

ergy and position of ions throughout the entrance detector and the focal-plane detectors and also the motion of the ions in the magnetic fields of the focussing elements [122, 127, 128].

In order to calculate the ion trajectory, a procedure was followed which is described below. Firstly, the path length, L , that the ions take through the various detectors and ion fields is calculated assuming that the ions take a central trajectory. This means that the path length from the target to the MCP entrance detector, labelled as L_a , and the length from the dipole to the MWPPAC, L_c , can be assumed to be linear. The path length through the magnetic optics is, however, more complex. Assuming ideal fields, the effect of the quadrupole magnet on the trajectories of the ions can be summarised through the Lorentz force which, when the magnetic field of the quadrupole is applied, gives the forces (F_y and F_z) imposed on the ions in the vertical (y) and horizontal (z) axes as,

$$F_y \simeq qv_x B_y, \quad (5.5)$$

and,

$$F_z \simeq -qv_x B_z. \quad (5.6)$$

Here, v_x is the velocity vector in the orthogonal direction, and B infers the magnetic field strength in the

respective directions. This overall provides a focusing effect in the vertical direction and a hyperbolic defocusing in the horizontal direction. Since the reconstruction assumes central trajectories only the horizontal plane is considered. On exiting the quadrupole, the ions are assumed to have linear paths. The effect of the dipole on the trajectories is approximated using the magnetic rigidity, $B\rho$, of the ion tracks, as described by,

$$B\rho = \frac{p}{q}. \quad (5.7)$$

Here, B is the magnetic field strength, ρ is the bending radius, p is the ions momentum, q is the charge state of the ion, and v is its velocity. Leaving the dipole. The ions are again assumed to have a linear path through the MWPPAC and finally the IC where their energy loss (ΔE) and total energy deposited (E) are measured. The total path length can then be approximated as sum of all path lengths as,

$$L_{tot} = L_a + L_b + L_c, \quad (5.8)$$

where L_b is the path length of the magnetic optics given by,

$$L_b = L_{quadrupole} + L_{quadrupole-dipole} + L_{dipole}. \quad (5.9)$$

From Equations 5.4, 5.6, and equating the momentum to the product of the mass, m , and the ion velocity, v , a relation between the time of flight and the mass-to-charge ratio can be found,

$$ToF = \frac{L}{B\rho} \frac{m}{q}. \quad (5.10)$$

The path of the ion is fully defined knowing its position, final energy, and ToF.

5.2.4.2 Optical Parameter Optimisation

The trajectory reconstruction implemented assumes ions passing through the magnets all experience the same magnetic fields. In reality, edge effects are expected due to a range of ion paths through the optics. Because of this, optical parameters of the magnets are manually optimized to best approximate the path length of the ions through the spectrometer.

In this analysis the parameters that required optimisation were the quadrupole length, the dipole exit angle, the dipole entrance angle, the target to quadrupole distance, and the target to dipole distance. Due to the

Parameter	Value [arb. units]
Target to quadrupole distance	500
Quadrupole length	370
Dipole entrance angle	11
Dipole exit angle	126
Target to dipole distance	1600

Table 5.2: Optical parameters that were optimized for this analysis. Other parameters that could be optimised in configuration file are not listed here as they were not changed from original values set online.

number of parameters that required optimisation, the number of combinations of parameter values that were needed was large. It was discovered that several parameters had inverse relationships with one another therefore allowing a range for acceptable values for each parameter to be determined. For example, an increase in the quadrupole length parameter required a decrease in the target to dipole distance in order to show a noticeable change in the resulting spectra. Therefore, by trialling combinations of multiple values, a range for each parameter was identified. These ranges were then used to optimise the parameter values by observing the resulting A/q spectra. Figure 5.16 shows an example of well optimised and poorly optimised optical parameters for two different histograms which are used later in the analysis. Within the range, appropriate steps to alter the parameters by were determined to further reduce the processing time.

Table 5.2 lists the optical parameters after optimisation. It is noted that throughout the optimisation, it was determined that several parameters had specific relationships. Determining the relationships between the optical parameters enhanced the efficiency of the optimisation process. Ultimately, a trade off between A/q and q resolution had to be achieved in order to observe good resolution in the final mass distribution.

5.2.5 Charge State Selection and Mass Identification

Once the optical parameters have been optimised, there are several further stages to the analysis before obtaining the final mass distributions. Magnetic aberrational effects must be corrected to achieve good resolutions for the mass-to-charge (A/q) ratio. From the calibrated A/q values and the calculated effective charge states the masses are finally observed.

5.2.5.1 Charge State Identification

In order to determine the charge states corresponding to the Z values, the motion of the ions in the dipole magnet is considered. Using Equation 5.6 and substituting the kinetic energy of the ions a similar relation for

Figure 5.16: The difference between optimised and non-optimised optical parameters. (A) and (C) show the plot of the mass-to-charge ratio against the x_{FP} of the MWPPAC, (A) demonstrates poor optimisation and (C) shows improved optimisation. (B) and (D) show the total measured ionisation chamber energy against the product $\rho\beta$. Here (B) shows the result of poor optimisation and (D) good optimisation.

the Lorentz force is obtained through,

$$B\rho = \frac{2E}{vq}, \quad (5.11)$$

where B is the magnetic field strength, ρ is the bending radius, E is the total energy of the ion measured by all sections of the Ionisation Chamber (IC), q is the charge state of the ion, and v is its velocity, which, when expressed relativistically ultimately leads to the relation,

$$E_{IC} \propto \rho\beta. \quad (5.12)$$

Therefore plotting the total ionisation chamber energy, E_{IC} , against the product $\rho\beta$ allows the selectivity of the resulting charge states of the ion which passes through the spectrometer. Applying the two-dimensional Z gates to such a spectrum results in the charge states for each atomic number. Examples of these distributions are given in Figure 5.17 for $Z = 50$ (Sn) and $Z = 48$ (Cd). The two-dimensional gates applied allow further selection of the data with a gate on both Z and q simultaneously. As shown by the scale on the right-hand side of the figures, a decrease in the number of entries from Sn to Cd ions is observed, as expected.

Figure 5.17: $Z = 50$ (top panel) and $Z = 48$ (bottom panel) gated matrices of the total IC energy against $\rho\beta$ allowing selection of the individual charge states.

Figure 5.18: $Z = 50$ gated matrix of the total IC energy against $\rho\beta$ with applied two-dimensional gates to select the charge states from $q = 39$ to $q = 31$, moving left to right. This is a result of the summation of all of the data in order to demonstrate the charge states.

When optimising the optical parameters further improvements to the E_{IC} versus $\rho\beta$ or to the A/q distributions can be made, but with a sacrifice in resolution for the other. In more detail, it was found that the optical parameters that resulted in E_{IC} versus $\rho\beta$ histograms with the best resolutions meant that the corresponding A/q distributions suffered in resolution. Therefore, when choosing values for the optical parameters, a trade off in resolution was made. However, due to the application of easily adjustable two-dimensional gates applied to select the charge states, a reduction in the resolution of the charge states is not a limiting factor in the analysis. Figure 5.18 shows the application of these gates for $Z = 50$. The charge states were selected in accordance with the most probable states expected to be observed from the REACTION software.

5.2.5.2 Aberrational Corrections

The ideal conditions assumed during the trajectory reconstruction allow the velocity and ToF of the ions passing through the spectrometer to be determined. However, these conditions do not accurately represent the paths of the majority of the ions, with the actual paths experienced by the ions being subject to deformities arising from non-uniformity effects in the magnetic fields causing inconsistencies in the path lengths of the ions. As a consequence, these aberrations significantly reduce the resolution of the resulting A/q ratio

measured using the detectors of the PRISMA spectrometer. Corrections must be applied to histograms of A/q against the position measured in the MCP and MWPPAC detectors to account for these effects. The top, middle, and bottom panels of Figure 5.19 present examples of the A/q ratio plotted against the x and y positions of the MCP and also the x position of the MWPPAC both before and after the aberrational corrections have been performed.

In order to correct for the visible distortions in the A/q lines, two methods were employed. Firstly, by applying a two-dimensional gate around one A/q line in the distributions, a polynomial function can be fit to the data points captured within the gate by applying a fit to the resulting peak when projecting on the y -axis. Using a 10-channel increment each peak centroid is taken as one data point for the polynomial fit [139]. This process is then repeated until all data points on the x -axis have been covered. A polynomial function of a selected order can then be fit to the resulting data points.

The application of polynomials to interpolate the A/q aberrations raises several issues. Due to the complexity of the distortions seen in the distributions, as evidenced in the histograms shown in Figure 5.19, a high-order polynomial, greater than the 10th order, is required to try to map the A/q lines. As a result, the application of a high-order polynomial to interpolate a line function is subject to the Runge effect [140]. This effect, which is more apparent as the order of the polynomial increases and at higher orders, results in large oscillations of the function that is used to fit to the data and an overall a reduction in the accuracy of the method.

Instead of a high-order polynomial, a cubic spline can be used by following the A/q line along the x -position to more accurately create an estimation of the distortion seen. A cubic spline is a series of third-order polynomials between selected data points, or knot points, which allows improved fitting. When using cubic splines, the second-order derivative of the polynomial is set to zero at the end points to ensure a smooth line passing through all data points. Increasing the number of knot points results in a more accurate fit to the data rather than a reduction in accuracy. During the analysis, both methods were tested and it was seen that the application of cubic splines to the data resulted in a better correction of the aberrational effects for all plots. In particular, the A/q against x_{FP} histogram was unable to be corrected accurately using the polynomial method owing to the requirement for a high-order polynomial due to the observed complexity of the data from section-to-section of the MWPPAC. The resulting correction using this method still displayed aberrational effects yielding in poor A/q resolutions.

The overall improvement following the aberrational corrections can be seen from the A/q distribution seen

Figure 5.19: Top row: A/q against the x -position of the MCP before (left) and after (right) the aberrational corrections are applied. Middle row: A/q ratio against the Y -position of the MCP before (left) and after (right) the aberrational corrections have been applied. Bottom row: A/q ratio against the X -position of the MWPPAC before (left) and after (right) the aberrational corrections have been applied.

Figure 5.20: A $Z = 50$ gated A/q distribution before (red) and after (blue) aberrational corrections have been applied.

in Figure 5.20. Here a comparison of the A/q distribution is observed before and after the aberrational corrections have been applied. Before the corrections have been applied both the peak resolution and peak-to-background are poor with the individual A/q values being indistinguishable from one another. The A/q distribution after the corrections shows a significant improvement and allows the identification of individual centroids resulting from a number of charge states.

5.2.5.3 Mass Calibration

A linear calibration is applied after the aberrational corrections in order to align the observed centroids of the A/q peaks to their expected values. This is carried out for each Zq -gated distribution. An example of this is shown Figure 5.21 for $Z = 50$ and $q = 36$. In order to calibrate to the correct A/q ratio, the masses that are expected to be seen in each histogram are individually selected. The assignment of the masses is estimated at first and then later corrected by observing the coincident AGATA-PRISMA γ -ray spectra. If the resulting γ -ray transitions do not match the selected nucleus then the calibration has to be performed again. In Figure 5.21 a clear shift in the A/q distribution can be seen after the calibration. A large improvement in the resolution of the peaks in the corresponding mass distributions is seen after this calibration is applied.

In order to determine the final mass distributions a simple multiplication of the Z -gated A/q values by the charge state is expected. However due to non-linearity effects, this results in poor mass distributions. To account for the non-linearity, an effective charge state, q_{eff} , is employed by measuring the peak centroids of the Zq -gated A/q distributions and comparing them to the expected mass values. This effective charge state is determined by taking an average of the calculated effective charge for each centroid in each Zq -gated A/q distribution. The resulting Z -gated mass distributions are shown in Figure 5.22 for the projectile-like nuclei from $Z = 50$ to $Z = 45$. The resulting mass resolutions and FWHM values are listed in Table 5.1. The distributions shown are produced using only a subset of the data which constitutes $\sim 6\%$ of the full data set.

Figure 5.21: A Zq -gated A/q distribution before (red) and after (blue) the final linear calibration has been applied. Assigned mass (A) values are labelled for most prominent peaks and masses in both distributions for reference.

From Table 5.3 and in Figure 5.22 it can be seen that the both the peak-to-background and the resolution for the mass distribution associated with $Z = 45$ are worse than the other observed Z -gated mass distributions. This is expected due to the uncertainty on the application of the polynomial gates for $Z = 45$ in Figure 5.13.

Although the application of the two-dimensional gates to select the charge states can generally overcome this problem the dispersion of the data around the lines may lead to this observed reduction in the peak-to-background for this nucleus. It is possible that the peak-to-background could be improved by altering the optical parameters however the impact of this change could also cause a reduction in the resolution or peak-to-background for other Z values. In addition to this, the resolution and peak-to-background values for the other nuclei are not similarly impacted enough to warrant a repeat of the analysis process. Ultimately, the method of selection of the various masses observed in the distributions, which is explained below, allows

Figure 5.22: Calibrated Z -gated mass distributions for the observed projectile-like nuclei.

the accurate selection of the nuclei of interest whilst retaining good statistics when experiencing a reduced resolution or peak-to-background ratio.

Z	Mass Resolution	Peak-to-background
50	$\sim \frac{1}{260}$	16:1
49	$\sim \frac{1}{250}$	15:1
48	$\sim \frac{1}{250}$	12:1
47	$\sim \frac{1}{250}$	11:1
46	$\sim \frac{1}{250}$	11:1
45	$\sim \frac{1}{230}$	6:1

Table 5.3: Values of the mass resolutions and peak-to-background ratios of the most prominent peaks shown in each Z -gated mass distribution. Here the denominator values are rounded due to the estimation of the calculation.

In order to select the masses to observe the resulting coincident AGATA-PRISMA spectra, either integer values or two-dimensional gates applied to the plot shown in Figure 5.23, can be applied. If two-dimensional gates are not applied in the software, the peaks in the mass distribution are selected by applying a gate of ± 0.5 around the set value. In Figure 5.23 clear separation between the mass lines are seen as a function of X_{FP} of the MWPPAC. This plot is useful for the gating process compared to the one-dimensional projection of the mass, especially at lower Z values where the statistics are low.

Deviations in the mass resolution, which would potentially result in the exclusion of data and loss of statistics, can be accounted for by gating around the mass of interest even with relatively poor resolutions.

The parameters and conditions determined throughout the analysis are applied to the entire data set. Ordinarily, either of the above methods of gating is appropriate to select the mass. Throughout the data analysis process, however, it was found that the mass distribution for the full data set had a significantly reduced peak-to-background ratio. After looking at the individual mass distributions for each run, the measured centroids for the mass peaks were found to change. A plot of the centroid of the $A = 112$ peak for $Z = 50$ as a function of the run number was made to visualise this deviation throughout the experiment; this is shown in Figure 5.24. Looking through the complete dataset it was noticed that the sharp changes in the centroid values correspond to either a change between one of the three uranium targets or a steering of the beam away from a previous beam spot due to degradation of the target. The requirement for a change of target or steering of the beam was necessary due to the high energy and intensity of the beam which, in some cases, caused damage to the target. The result of these changes means that the full dataset cannot not be summed to give

Figure 5.23: Two-dimensional projection of the mass distribution as a function X_{FP} of the MWPPAC gated on $Z = 48$.

mass distributions with acceptable resolutions or peak-to-background ratios.

Figure 5.24: Measured centroid values for the $Z = 50$ $A = 112$ mass peak as a function of the run number.

From Figure 5.24 it is clear that the use of integer gates would result in poor selection of the masses meaning that after summing the individual runs together, the resolution of the Z -gated mass distributions would be poor. Instead, the application of the two-dimensional gates to the matrices, like the one shown in Figure 5.23, allow accurate selection of the masses for each Z identified for each individual run. The resulting coincidence

spectra are therefore unaffected by the observed deviation in centroid value when using this gating method.

5.2.6 Doppler Correction

The analysis of the PRISMA spectrometer is completed once a Doppler correction is applied to the resulting AGATA-PRISMA γ -ray coincidence spectra. To be able to accurately identify new transitions in exotic nuclei the accurate measurement of the energy of the photopeak is required. To determine whether the time-of-flight (ToF) value, and therefore the Doppler correction, has been set correctly in the analysis, a transition of known energy is used to identify if the measured energy matches the expected value for the transition. Initially observed γ -ray peak centroids resulting from a gate on the projectile-like binary partner at the focal plane of the PRISMA spectrometer can display deviation from the expected value due to the Doppler effect (see Section 3.5.3). The amount by which the energy is shifted by is dependent on the angle of emission of the radiation, θ , and the velocity of the recoil, v . Under relativistic considerations, the velocity can be written in terms of the speed of light, c , as $\beta = v/c$. From a similar form to that given in Equation 3.19, the energy detected in the AGATA spectrometer germanium detectors can be written as,

$$E'_\gamma = \frac{E_{\gamma,0}}{\gamma(1 - \beta\cos\theta)}, \quad (5.13)$$

where γ is the Lorentz factor given by,

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}, \quad (5.14)$$

and $E_{\gamma,0}$ is the initial energy of the γ ray if the ion is at rest. In order to obtain coincident spectra for both the projectile-like and target-like reaction products a correction for the observed Doppler effect is necessary.

In the case of the projectile-like nuclei, the angle of emission and the velocity are determined through the trajectory reconstruction previously mentioned in this chapter. For the target-like reaction products, the variables needed to recover the real γ -ray energy are determined through binary-partner kinematic calculations which allow event-by-event correction of the γ -ray energies arising from AGATA-PRISMA coincidences. During the analysis a variable related to the ToF labelled as the ToF offset was used to alter the time-of-flight and hence the velocity of the projectile-like nuclei for the trajectory reconstruction. This value was set online and was optimised throughout the offline analysis depending on the deviation observed between the observed photopeak centroids in the Doppler-corrected AGATA-PRISMA coincident γ -ray spectrum and the expected transition energy, which is calculated using known transitions from nuclei within the dataset. Using Equation 5.13 for both the observed and expected energies, assuming that the value of $\gamma \sim 1$, and applying the values of $E_{\gamma,0}$, E'_γ and θ from a plot of the detected γ -ray energy against the angle of emission, two values for

Figure 5.25: Top panel: Non Doppler-corrected spectrum of the measured γ -ray energies as a function of the angle of emission. Bottom panel: Doppler-corrected spectrum of the measured γ -ray energies as a function of the angle of emission. Both spectra are gated on the projectile $^{112}_{50}\text{Sn}$ and show the energy of the $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ ground-state transition.

β can be determined. The first β value uses the current measured Doppler-corrected energy for $E_{\gamma,0}$, and the second includes the expected transition energy for the same variable. Then using Equation 5.4 two ToF values can be determined; the difference of which represents the deviation from the ToF value that results in the expected transition energies using a known transition from a nucleus present in the data. As shown in Figure 5.25, examples of the two-dimensional spectra used to measure the γ -ray energy as a function of emission angle are observed before and after the Doppler correction is applied. This example is only for one transition within one nucleus. In order to confirm the change in the ToF offset, a repeat of the above process is performed for several other known transitions within other nuclei that have been observed. If it is found

that the ToF value needs to be changed, the repeat of the analysis from Section 5.22 is required.

5.3 DANTE Analysis

This section details the analysis of the DANTE detector located opposite to the entrance of the PRISMA spectrometer. It is noted that whenever DANTE is mentioned in this section, only one MCP-based detector is involved.

5.3.1 Time Alignment of DANTE

In order to view events registered in the DANTE detector, the timestamps associated with them have to be aligned with the global timestamp of the AGATA spectrometer, which is in turn aligned with that of the PRISMA spectrometer. To check the alignment, the raw data of the DANTE detector and AGATA spectrometer are used to plot the time differences between the DANTE timestamps and the AGATA timestamps. The clock for the DANTE events, unlike that for AGATA spectrometer events, is reset after each run and as such, the timestamp difference between the two detectors is different for each run. Figure 5.26 shows an example of a peak in the timestamp difference histogram for one run. Once this peak is observed, the centroid value is used to create an output file of combined DANTE and PRISMA raw data which are aligned to the global timestamp of the AGATA spectrometer. This process is repeated for each run due to the difference in timestamp offset values of the DANTE data. Once all runs have been aligned and the data have been merged, the coincidences between AGATA and all ancillary detectors are obtained. During the beam time, the firmware of the DANTE MCP digitisers was changed from Pulse-Height Analysis (PHA) to Pulse-Shape Discrimination (PSD). As a result, the timestamp difference plot did not show a distinct peak in the runs which used PSD digitisers, which accounted for $\sim 80\%$ of the dataset, due to the software interpreting the signal from a digitiser with PHA firmware. In order to correct for this, the configuration file of the software (see Appendix A.3.1) used to take the raw CAEN digitiser information and convert to AGATA Data Format (ADF), had to be updated for the runs in which the digitisers were changed.

Once the change is accounted for, the peak is observed, allowing the timestamp offset between DANTE and the AGATA spectrometer to be identified for the remaining runs. An example of the difference in timestamps after the alignment has been performed is shown in Figure 5.27. Due to the timestamps of the AGATA and PRISMA spectrometers being aligned, the alignment between AGATA and DANTE also provides an alignment between PRISMA and DANTE. It is noted that DANTE is aligned by comparing the raw data to the raw data for a signal AGATA crystal. Since all the AGATA crystals have been aligned in time, this means that DANTE is aligned with all AGATA detectors. A timing window is specified between AGATA

Figure 5.26: Timestamp difference between the raw timestamp of the AGATA spectrometer and that of DANTE.

and DANTE and PRISMA and DANTE in order to select valid coincident events to merge together. This is optimised when observing the coincident γ -ray spectra.

Figure 5.27: Timestamp difference peak between the AGATA spectrometer and DANTE after the alignment process has been completed.

5.3.2 DANTE Coincidences

After the alignment of the timestamps, the events collected in DANTE can be merged with the events from AGATA and PRISMA to observe coincidences.

One important quantity that is obtained from the coincidence between PRISMA and DANTE is the difference in time-of-flight, ΔToF , between that measured from the entrance MCP of PRISMA and the DANTE MCP opposite to the entrance of PRISMA. This allows a separation between events arising from fission of the target-like reaction products and reaction products arising from multi-nucleon transfer between the projectile and target. This is due to the expectation that the fission reaction products will be slower and are therefore detected with a longer time-of-flight, meaning that the time-of-flight difference between the PRISMA MCP and the DANTE MCP will be larger for the fission products than that for the MNT reaction products. Figure 5.28 shows two histograms of the ΔToF distributions for two runs which use the PHA and PSD firmware. Here, runs of equal length ($\sim 6\%$ of the full dataset) were used in order to compare the impact on statistics when changing the digitiser firmware. It is clear that the larger structure in the histograms, which is anticipated to represent the fission reaction products, has a smaller ΔToF value than that the distribution expected to arise from multi-nucleon transfer reactions. This contradicts the explanation given above. This is explained by the trigger set when building coincident events. In this case the ‘start’ trigger was set to be the MCP entrance detector of PRISMA meaning that the resulting timestamp difference is not the PRISMA MCP timestamp minus the timestamp of the DANTE detector, but the DANTE timestamp minus the PRISMA timestamp, hence explaining why the distribution expected to arise from fission of the target-like reaction products appears at a lower ΔToF value than the multi-nucleon transfer distribution. Ultimately, the identification can be confirmed by observing the resulting γ rays when applying a gate on the distributions.

The identification of events involving target-like nuclei and fission fragments can be achieved by plotting the ΔToF against TKEL, as shown in Fig. 5.28, a polygonal gate can be applied to select both of the observed structures, from which coincident γ -ray spectra can be created. After the application of the gate, it is possible to choose events that do not occur from fission of the target-like products. It is expected that the selection of events which arise from multi-nucleon transfer reactions will show a significantly reduced background in the coincident γ -ray spectrum, allowing the identification of known γ -ray transitions for the target-like reaction products of interest.

Figure 5.28: Time-of-flight difference between the MCP at the entrance of the PRISMA spectrometer and the MCP of DANTE opposite the entrance of the PRISMA spectrometer. The top panel shows an example of the difference for a run in which PHA digitisers were used and the bottom panel shows a run for which the digitizers with PSD firmware were used.

Figure 5.29: The difference in time-of-flight between the MCP at the entrance to the PRISMA spectrometer and the MCP of DANTE opposite the entrance to PRISMA against the total kinetic energy loss (TKEL) measured in the ionisation chamber of the PRISMA spectrometer.

5.4 Total Kinetic Energy Loss Selection

The total kinetic energy loss (TKEL) is a parametrisation of the kinetic energy difference before and after a nuclear reaction has taken place. It can be used in nuclear spectroscopy to select reactions which populate specific states. This selection method is sometimes used in the measurements of nuclear lifetimes and cross-sections to distinguish between excited states feeding to lower-lying states [123]. In addition to the use of TKEL selection for direct reactions, the method can also be applied to other reaction mechanisms. Multi-nucleon transfer reactions often use magnetic spectrometers to provide selection of reaction products which require accurate velocity, energy, and angular information to perform event-by-event trajectory reconstruction. These parameters can also be used to calculate the TKEL. For a system of two initial and final nuclei, the Q -value can be written as,

$$Q = (M_0 + M_1 - M_2 - M_3)c^2 = E_2 + E_3 - E_1, \quad (5.15)$$

where M_0 denotes the mass of the target nucleus, M_1 is the projectile nucleus mass, M_2 and M_3 are the masses of the recoiling reaction products, and E_1 , E_2 , and E_3 represent the kinetic energies of the projectile and reaction-product nuclei [141]. The Q -value is related to the TKEL as,

Figure 5.30: The total kinetic energy loss distribution for the reaction $^{112}\text{Sn} + ^{238}\text{U}$ in the top panel. The bottom three panels show the results before (top) and after gating on the selections denoted by 'A' and 'B' on the top panel. It should be noted that the top panel is not calibrated to give accurate TKEL values.

$$\text{TKEL} = -Q. \quad (5.16)$$

The use of multi-nucleon transfer as a reaction mechanism results in the production of many channels in the region of interest. The purpose of gating on the TKEL is to select events where a target-like nucleus is populated in a lower excited state and hence minimize the contribution from spontaneous fission which would contribute to the background in the γ -ray spectrum. The relationship between the TKEL and the energies resulting from the de-excitation from a nuclear state permit this selectivity, where a gate on low TKEL values allows a reduction in transitions from high-lying states and the inverse is true for a gate on high TKEL values. An example of a TKEL distribution, along with the result of applying gates at high and low TKEL values, is shown in Figure 5.30. To optimise the application of the gate setting, a gate at a low TKEL value is initially set, after which a range of low TKEL values is scanned through to determine which maximises the peak-to-background and resolution of the transitions in the prompt γ -ray spectrum. The width of the gate range is similarly set based on the optimisation of the resulting prompt γ -ray spectrum peaks.

Chapter 6

Results and Discussion

In this chapter the aims of the experiment are first presented. Then the excitation-energy and angular momentum systematics of the nuclei $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ are shown. After this the resulting γ -ray spectra from the coincidence measurements between the AGATA spectrometer and the PRISMA magnetic spectrometer are shown. Later, the AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE coincidence spectra are shown. Further gates on the TKEL are shown for the AGATA-PRISMA γ -ray spectra, including tentative identification of the first excited states in $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$.

6.1 Aims of the Experiment

The aim of the present experiment was to identify and study excited states in $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ for which there are presently none identified. Theoretical models, such as that used by Nomura *et al.* [11], predict a minimum in the potential energy surface of ^{234}Pu with values of $\beta_2 \simeq 0.22$ and $\beta_3 \simeq 0$, while ^{232}Pu is predicted to have values $\beta_2 \simeq 0.22$ and $\beta_3 \simeq 0.21$. This prediction demonstrates a rapid onset of octupole deformation, with a β_3 value of 0.2 in ^{232}Pu indicating strong octupole deformation. These values along with other theoretical predictions for the neutron-deficient actinide region of the nuclear chart (see Section 2.5) provide the motivation for this experiment. The neutron-deficient plutonium nuclei have been hard to populate due to the inaccessibility when employing fusion-evaporation reactions because of the low production cross sections when using stable beam and target combinations. Because of this, multi-nucleon transfer is proposed here as the reaction method. This has previously not been used as a reaction method using this beam and target combination. The AGATA detector array in combination with the PRISMA spectrometer was chosen to provide the selection required to identify the reaction products of interest. In addition, DANTE was used at the target position to identify the target-like products from the multi-nucleon transfer reactions and to help

remove background of γ rays due to fission. The experiment aimed to identify excited states up to $12 \hbar$ in the $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ nuclei. Additionally, the identification of low-lying negative parity states and E1 transitions, indicative of octupole correlations, were key goals.

This section discusses considerations in the preparation and planning of the experiment discussed in this thesis. The systematics of neighbouring nuclei with known excited states are shown.

6.1.1 Rate Estimates

The production cross sections for the $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ nuclei were calculated using the GRAZING9 software using a beam energy of 808 MeV (laboratory-frame) [142]. Values of 8 mb and 14 mb were obtained for $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$, respectively [143]. This, however, does not take into account the estimation that over $\sim 95\%$ of the cross section will lead to prompt fission. Taking this into account provides the effective production cross sections for $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ of 0.4 mb and 0.7 mb, respectively. Considering 14 days of beam time, a ^{112}Sn beam with intensity of 5 pnA, a ^{238}U target with a thickness of 1 mg cm^{-2} , PRISMA transmission efficiency of $\sim 5\%$, AGATA detection efficiency of $\sim 12\%$ from 50 to 500 keV, and γ -ray multiplicity of ~ 10 , the total number of detected ions at the focal plane of PRISMA for $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ was calculated to be 1.9×10^6 and 3.3×10^6 ions, respectively. This is estimated to result in the collection of 2.4×10^6 and 1.4×10^6 PRISMA- γ singles events, and 4.3×10^5 and 2.4×10^5 PRISMA- $\gamma\gamma$ events for ^{234}Pu and ^{232}Pu , respectively.

6.1.2 Systematics of Nuclei of Interest

The systematics explained in Section 2.5.4 are shown here for three even-even isotopes $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ due to their close proximity with the nuclei of interest. It is expected that the behaviour observed in $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ can be contextualised in terms of the onset of octupole deformation by looking at the evolution of the systematics along the isotopic chain. Shown in Figure 6.1 are the level energies of the positive-parity yrast bands of $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ [82, 144–147]. The excited states up to $16 \hbar$ are included as this is the limit of the known excited states for ^{236}Pu whereas $^{238,240}\text{Pu}$ extend to $30 \hbar$ and $32 \hbar$ in the ground-state bands, respectively. The excitation energies of the states in the ground-state bands in these isotopes provides an indication of the energies of the states for the $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ nuclei. It is expected that the first and second excited states of $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ will be difficult to observe in the γ -ray spectra due to the competition of between γ decay and internal conversion. As the internal conversion coefficient scales with increasing Z and decreasing transition energy, internal conversion is expected to be the dominate decay mode for low-energy transitions, therefore resulting in a low chance of observing the $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$ and $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ γ -ray transitions, which are expected

to occur at ~ 50 keV and ~ 100 keV, respectively. These transition energies would have internal conversion coefficient values of 427.1 and 15.8, respectively, assuming E2 multipolarity indicating the difficulty of observing them in the γ -ray energy spectrum [148]. The transition between the $6^+ \rightarrow 4^+$ states, which is expected to have energy ~ 150 keV, would have an internal conversion coefficient value of 2.2 which is lower than that for the $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$ and $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ transitions but still relatively large.

Figure 6.1: Energies of states in the ground-state bands of $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ up to $16\hbar$, plotted against the mass number, A .

Figure 6.2 shows plots of the total angular momentum projected on the rotation axis, I_x , as a function of the rotational frequency, $\hbar\omega$, for the $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ isotopes. As shown in the figure, all three nuclei show a smooth increase in I_x as $\hbar\omega$ increases. This is expected for nuclei that do not exhibit a backbend associated with quasi-particle alignment. The observation of a backbend would indicate a structural effect which is not seen in octupole deformed nuclei. With increasing rotational frequency the aligned angular momentum for the positive-parity band and negative-parity band will converge, indicating that the nuclei develop towards a stable rotational shape at higher rotational frequency values. As shown, I_x values for ^{240}Pu and ^{238}Pu show similar behaviour. The data for ^{236}Pu show a lack of negative parity states but the positive-parity band I_x values show similar behaviour to those for ^{240}Pu and ^{238}Pu .

Nuclei exhibiting octupole correlations show characteristically low-lying negative-parity states with respect

to the positive-parity states. As the rotation of the nucleus reaches higher spin values the energies of the negative-parity states move closer to the midpoint of the adjacent positive-parity state energies. As a result, a calculation of the difference between the midpoint of the positive-parity band states and the energy of the negative-parity state which sits in between the two positive states, can be made. Figure 6.3 shows the parity splitting as a function of the spin of the level taken from the level schemes of the $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ nuclei. Here, all three nuclei show a reduction in the parity splitting as the spin increases. In the case of ^{240}Pu and ^{238}Pu

Figure 6.2: Total angular momentum along the rotation axis for the positive-parity (black) and negative-parity (red) bands of $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ against the rotational frequency.

the reduction to zero is shown at $\sim 30 \hbar$. As shown, the data for ^{236}Pu does not provide sufficient information to be able to conclude.

Figure 6.3: The energy difference between the midpoint of positive-parity states and the adjacent negative-parity states for the $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ nuclei as a function of the spin.

Figure 6.4 shows the ratios of the rotational frequencies for the positive-parity and negative-parity bands for $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$. As the angular momentum increases, the data are expected to approach one if the nucleus is statically octupole deformed [79]. As shown, the three plutonium nuclei approach this limit as the spin increases but do not appear to meet the exact value. In the case of ^{240}Pu , the data appears to be still increasing up to the limit of the experimental data, however for ^{238}Pu , the data begins to plateau at $I \sim 24 \hbar$ corresponding to a rotational frequency ratio value $\omega^-/\omega^+ \sim 0.9$.

The results of the systematics leads to an interpretation that the plutonium nuclei in the mass range $A \geq 236$ indicate a region with limited octupole correlations compared to the light actinides. It is expected for the plutonium nuclei of interest, that the octupole correlations should increase with decreasing A , approaching the onset of octupole deformation for $A \leq 232$, predicted by the theoretical calculations detailed in Section 2.5. Better understanding of this region would be obtained with the identification of higher spin, negative-parity states in ^{236}Pu . This, along with the identification of excited states in $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$, would provide further experimental data at the extremes of known neutron-deficient plutonium isotopes to compare

to the theoretical predictions and current experimental results. The identification of higher spin states in both positive-parity and negative-parity states in these nuclei would provide additional data from which plots such as those shown in Figures 6.1 - 6.4 can be made to infer structural properties.

Figure 6.4: Rotational frequency ratios for the $^{236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ nuclei, calculated from the known level energies against the spin.

6.2 AGATA Testing

The calibrations of the AGATA spectrometer were carried out using standard ^{152}Eu and ^{133}Ba calibration sources. The calibration runs were conducted after the experiment. The results for the energy resolution and efficiency calibrations are shown in this section. It is noted that the length of the source run for ^{152}Eu was longer than for the ^{133}Ba source run.

6.2.1 Energy Resolution

A comparison between the source data and the in-beam data can be made from a plot of the ratio of FWHM and measured γ -ray energy against the measured γ -ray energy. This is shown in Figure 6.5, expressed as a percentage, for the ^{152}Eu source data and the in-beam data after selecting $Z = 50$ and $A = 112$ from PRISMA and Doppler correcting to obtain ^{112}Sn . Then Doppler correcting for the binary partner gives the spectra for ^{238}U , respectively.

Figure 6.5: The ratio of the FWHM and the measured energy centroids against the measured energy centroid for three data sets. The black points and fitted line indicate the energy resolution curve using data from a ^{152}Eu source run. The red and blue points indicate the same measurement using the in-beam AGATA-PRISMA-gated γ -ray spectra for ^{112}Sn and ^{238}U after a Doppler correction has been applied, respectively.

As shown in the figure, the in-beam ^{238}U data is significantly worse than for the ^{152}Eu source and ^{112}Sn projectile data. A factor of ~ 3 difference is observed between the target and source resolutions at ~ 400 keV. This difference is not as significant when comparing between the source data and the results for the ^{112}Sn γ -ray transitions. Generally, the ^{112}Sn data is shown to follow the results of the fitted source data for increasing energy. This is expected when considering that the projectile-like reaction products are detected in the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, meaning that there has been a kinematic reconstruction and Doppler correction based on the trajectory of the products through the PRISMA spectrometer. The results shown for ^{238}U are expected to be less accurate as the Doppler correction relies on a two body kinematic reconstruction of an un-detected nucleus using the detected ^{112}Sn nuclei.

6.2.2 Efficiency Calibration

The relative detection efficiency was calculated using the combined ^{152}Eu and ^{133}Ba γ -ray data. A normalisation factor was applied when plotting the ^{133}Ba data onto the plot with the ^{152}Eu . The results of this are shown in Figure 6.6. Here, the relative peak areas of transitions were compared to literature values. The efficiency calibration was performed using the EFFIT program which is part of the RADWARE software

package [149]. This provided the γ -ray intensities used to calculate the relative efficiencies plotted. The function used to fit the data is split into two components to describe the behaviour at high and low energies. The efficiency is described at low (~ 100 keV) and high (~ 1 MeV) energies as,

$$A + Bx + Cx^2, \quad (6.1)$$

and,

$$D + Ey + Fy^2, \quad (6.2)$$

respectively. Here, the x and y coefficients are defined as,

$$x = \ln\left(\frac{E_\gamma}{E1}\right), \quad (6.3)$$

and,

$$y = \ln\left(\frac{E_\gamma}{E2}\right). \quad (6.4)$$

The reference values of E1 and E2 are set to 100 keV and 1 MeV, respectively, and E_γ is the γ -ray energy of interest. The complete functional form of the efficiency is then defined as,

$$\mathcal{E} = \exp\{[(A + Bx + Cx^2)^{(-G)} + (D + Ey + Fy^2)^{(-G)}]^{-\frac{1}{G}}\}. \quad (6.5)$$

Efficiency data extracted from the calibration data and the fit to the data are shown in Figure 6.6. The parameters produced from the fit are listed in Table 6.1.

Parameter	Value
A	0.7(3)
B	2.7(4)
C	0.0(0)
D	2.54(3)
E	-0.26(10)
F	0.05(9)
G	-15.0(0)

Table 6.1: The seven parameters obtained during the efficiency calibration to describe the relative detection efficiency as a function of the measured γ -ray energy from ^{152}Eu and ^{133}Ba source data. During the fit the values of C and G were fixed at 0 and -15, respectively.

Figure 6.6: The relative detection efficiency as a function of measured γ -ray energy using combined data from ^{152}Eu and ^{133}Ba source runs. Fitted line of best fit was performed using the RadWare analysis software.

6.3 AGATA γ -ray Spectra

This section describes the results from AGATA in combination with the ancillary detectors which are used to apply selectivity to the γ -ray events. To begin, an introduction to the AGATA spectrometer results is given. Then the results of the AGATA-PRISMA coincidences are shown starting with the time window applied between AGATA and PRISMA to identify coincidence events. Following this, the coincidence results for the most intense nuclei observed for each value of Z and the respective binary partners are presented. The observed transitions are listed and level schemes are included where possible. After this, the results from coincidences with the target-like reaction products in DANTE are shown. Finally, the results of applying selectivity on the total kinetic energy loss (TKEL) for the AGATA-PRISMA coincidence spectra are shown with the first identification of excited states in ^{234}Pu , allowing a tentative level scheme to be made.

To demonstrate the level of selectivity that has been applied during the analysis, it is worth including the prompt γ -ray spectrum without conditions from any other ancillary detectors. In Figure 6.7 the prompt γ -ray energy spectra for the core electrodes and after the tracking algorithm has been applied are shown. From these spectra it is possible to measure peak areas for several transitions that arise from background sources

and therefore are not Doppler shifted like the γ -rays which are emitted from target-like and projectile-like reaction products. From these peak areas it is possible to calculate the peak-to-total ratio for each transition, this is shown in Table 6.2. The total area in the core electrode spectrum is 6.02×10^8 whilst the total area for the tracked spectrum is 3.93×10^8 .

Energy	511 keV	563 keV	1014 keV	1434 keV
Core	$3.948(5) \times 10^{-3}$	$2.441(13) \times 10^{-4}$	$6.975(22) \times 10^{-4}$	$9.648(80) \times 10^{-5}$
Tracked	$4.911(7) \times 10^{-3}$	$3.275(18) \times 10^{-4}$	$9.827(32) \times 10^{-4}$	$1.295(11) \times 10^{-4}$

Table 6.2: Peak-to-total ratios for background transitions in the core electrode and tracked γ -ray spectra.

Figure 6.7: A γ -ray energy spectrum for the core electrode and after the tracking algorithm has been applied.

In Figure 6.7, the peak at 511-keV comes from the annihilation of a positron, creating two photons at 511-keV. The peaks at 563-keV, 1014-keV, and 1434-keV arise from neutron induced ($n, n'\gamma$) reactions in ^{76}Ge , ^{27}Al , and ^{52}Cr , respectively. As shown in the spectrum, at lower γ -ray energies the core electrode spectrum is observed to have higher counts than that for the tracked spectrum. By comparing the peak-to-total ratios for each transition it is clear that the tracking algorithm provides better peak-to-total values, giving an average factor of ~ 1.5 improvement when compared to the core.

6.3.1 AGATA-PRISMA Results

In this section the γ -ray spectra associated with the reaction products from the multi-nucleon transfer reactions are shown. As detailed in Section 5.2, the projectile-like reaction products are observed from the mass distributions (see Figure 5.22) for each atomic number. A Doppler correction is applied based on the reconstruction of the reaction products paths through PRISMA. The identification of the target-like binary partner is then performed through a Doppler correction using two-body kinematics. Due to the reaction mechanism, the number of reaction products, and therefore the number of spectra, is large. Therefore, to provide a more focused description of the results of this thesis, the spectra associated with the most intense masses for each observed atomic number are presented in this section. For completeness, additional γ -ray spectra, which have been observed for each atomic number, are given in Appendix B. This is not an indication that the nuclei shown in the main body of this text provide a more interesting physics discussion, but to emphasise that the identification of the correct isotopes of interest has been successful and that the results for the nuclei of interest can be trusted. A separate section gives the results for the plutonium nuclei of interest.

Figure 6.8 shows a plot of the time coincidence between AGATA and PRISMA for a single run, which represents around $\sim 1\%$ of the dataset. The top panel of the figure shows that there are two peaks present in the distribution and it is therefore necessary to determine what each peak corresponds to. Two gates are applied to observe the resulting coincident γ -rays after requiring the identification of the projectile, ^{112}Sn , from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA. It is clear from Figure 6.8(b) and 6.8(c) that the gate applied to the main peak structure, which occurs at ~ 150 ns in the time coincidence distribution, results in the expected lines associated with the Z and A selected with PRISMA. In Figure 6.8(b), the $^{112}\text{Sn } 2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$, 1256-keV transition is clearly visible. The gate applied to the smaller structure results in background and no clear peak at the expected energies for ^{112}Sn . The gate applied in Figure 6.8(a) which was used to produce Figure 6.8(b) is therefore applied throughout the dataset.

Figure 6.8: (a) A histogram showing the time difference between the timestamps of events in AGATA and PRISMA. The shaded regions indicate the gates used to identify the origins of the peaks. (b) A γ -ray spectrum in coincidence with the pink shaded region. (c) A γ -ray spectrum in coincidence with the blue shaded region.

6.3.1.1 Inelastic Channel

Figure 6.9 shows the prompt γ -ray spectrum when applying a gate on the time coincidence between AGATA and PRISMA and selecting $Z = 50$ and $A = 112$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, giving the γ -ray energy spectrum for ^{112}Sn .

Figure 6.9: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{112}Sn with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 50$, from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 112$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through PRISMA has been applied.

The spectrum shows the γ -ray transitions previously identified as belonging to $A = 112$, which was the beam in this experiment. These transitions are the most intense of any of the projectile-like reaction products. The observed transitions are listed alongside literature values for the transition energies in Table 6.3. The transitions observed in the figure are shown in a partial level scheme for ^{112}Sn in Figure 6.10. As shown by the comparison between the measured and the literature values in Table 6.3, there is an average deviation between the centroid energies of ~ 0.3 keV, with a maximum deviation of 0.5 keV for the 301-keV and 1256-keV transitions. A potential reason why this occurs is that the Doppler correction in the analysis of the PRISMA spectrometer was not optimised. In the case of ^{112}Sn , all transitions in the ground-state band up to $6\hbar$ are observed and additional transitions arising from several side bands are observed. The dashed line for the $9^- \rightarrow 7^-$ transition indicates a γ -ray that was not observed in this work. Additionally the observed 893-keV γ -ray transition is expected to compete with the 1167-keV transition for the $6^+ \rightarrow 4^+$. The transitions indicated with an asterisk are transitions from ^{238}U which have been Doppler broadened due to the correction being applied for ^{112}Sn . Transitions at ~ 550 -keV and ~ 1525 -keV are observed as transitions in ^{27}Al and the transition at ~ 1375 -keV is identified as from ^{52}Cr . These transitions arise from neutron induced ($n, n'\gamma$) reactions.

Figure 6.10: A partial level scheme for ^{112}Sn showing the transitions observed in this work.

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
262.57(30)	2.31(60)	613(50)	263.03(7)	(9) ⁻	(8) ⁻
301.20(30)	2.00(60)	593(49)	301.70(10)	6 ⁺	4 ⁺
663.79(20)	6.10(10)	2880(107)	663.61(1)	8 ⁺	6 ⁺
742.09(30)	5.43(80)	961(62)	741.7(1)	10 ⁺	8 ⁺
804.27(70)	5.33(20)	2643(103)	805.11(7)	(7) ⁻	6 ⁺
893.25(10)	4.50(20)	2437(99)	893.2(2)	6 ⁺	4 ⁺
990.05(4)	4.92(10)	10053(201)	990.5(1)	4 ⁺	2 ⁺
1096.54(20)	5.82(50)	2118(92)	1097.38(7)	3 ⁻	2 ⁺
1166.82(30)	5.92(60)	791(56)	1166.71(1)	6 ⁺	4 ⁺
1256.09(2)	6.91(10)	39001(395)	1256.61(1)	2 ⁺	0 ⁺

Table 6.3: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{112}Sn taken from Ref. [147].

Figure 6.11 shows the γ -ray spectrum for the target nucleus ^{238}U . This spectrum is obtained via the same conditions required to obtain the spectrum in Figure 6.9 but with a Doppler correction for the target nucleus.

Similarly to the transitions observed in the projectile nucleus, these transitions are the most intense of the target-like reactions products. The transitions labelled on the centroids in the figure are observed as the ground-state transitions in the target nucleus from $4\hbar$ to $22\hbar$. These are shown in a level scheme for the ground-state band of ^{238}U in Figure 6.12. As shown, Figure 6.12 does not include the transitions from the $J^\pi = 4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$ and $J^\pi = 2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ states, which are included in the level scheme, as they were unable to be observed in the γ -ray spectrum. These transitions compete with internal conversion as a mode of decay, which is expected to be dominant at low energies. The internal conversion coefficients for these transitions are calculated as 604.3 and 11.1 for the 45-keV $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ transition and 104-keV $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$ transition, respectively. The observed transitions are listed with the literature values in Table 6.4. A comparison between the measured and literature values shows an average deviation of ~ 0.7 keV with a maximum deviation of 1.3 keV for the $18^+ \rightarrow 16^+$ transition.

Figure 6.11: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{238}U with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 50$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 112$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the unobserved binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
158.53(5)	4.06(10)	12231(221)	158.9(4)	6 ⁺	4 ⁺
210.09(4)	5.55(10)	24653(314)	210.6(4)	8 ⁺	6 ⁺
257.25(3)	5.93(10)	22380(299)	257.8(4)	10 ⁺	8 ⁺
299.82(4)	7.10(10)	18628(273)	300.6(4)	12 ⁺	10 ⁺
338.13(6)	7.79(20)	12931(227)	338.8(4)	14 ⁺	12 ⁺
372.11(10)	7.64(30)	6804(165)	372.9(4)	16 ⁺	14 ⁺
401.26(22)	7.87(50)	3240(114)	402.6(4)	18 ⁺	16 ⁺
427.35(52)	7.87(120)	1362(74)	427.9(4)	20 ⁺	18 ⁺
449.29(93)	8.39(170)	868(59)	448.9(4)	22 ⁺	20 ⁺

Table 6.4: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{238}U [147].Figure 6.12: A partial level scheme for ^{238}U showing the transitions observed in this work. The $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$ and $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ transitions have dashed lines to indicate they were not observed in this work.

6.3.1.2 One Proton Transfer Channel

Figure 6.13 shows the γ -ray spectrum after gating on the projectile-like reaction product ^{112}In . This channel corresponds to the most intense mass in the $Z = 49$ mass distribution and is populated through the transfer of one proton from the projectile to the target and a neutron from the target to the projectile ($-1p+1n$ channel). The observed transitions are listed and compared with literature values in Table 6.5.

Figure 6.13: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{112}In with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 49$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 112$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
178.10(40)	2.29(70)	25(32)	178.5(3)	14^+	13^+
186.89(10)	3.12(20)	1634(81)	187.1(3)	9^-	8^-
206.57(20)	3.62(60)	983(63)	206.8(3)	$(2)^+$	1^+
248.69(50)	4.87(110)	501(45)	249.68(30)	8^-	7^+
262.27(60)	2.35(50)	242(31)	263.1(3)	8^-	7^+
272.82(20)	2.39(50)	684(52)	272.7(3)	15^+	14^+
318.98(20)	4.37(40)	976(136)	319.2(3)	8^+	7^+
393.59(40)	2.00(40)	136(23)	393.3(3)	16^+	15^+
438.74(30)	2.00(40)	571(48)	438.0(3)	$(21)^+$	$(20)^+$
552.28(50)	4.98(130)	1471(77)	552.4(3)	12^-	11^-
588.34(10)	3.51(40)	1656(81)	558.2(3)	10^+	9^-
725.51(52)	5.87(70)	740(54)	724.3(3)	11^-	10^-
1445.61(30)	5.22(60)	439(42)	1445.2(3)	10^+	8^+

Table 6.5: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{112}In . The literature values are taken from Ref. [147].

The level scheme displayed in Figure 6.14 is based on the literature results, but shows the transitions observed in Figure 6.13, the displayed levels and transitions represent a small part of a larger level scheme for ^{112}In . Transitions missing from the level scheme but listed in Table 6.5 are single transitions assigned to another band within the level scheme and are therefore not included in this figure.

Figure 6.14: Partial level scheme for ^{112}In showing the transitions observed in this work.

The transfer of $+1p -1n$ in the target-like nucleus results in the production of a ^{238}Np target-like fragment. After a Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile-like nucleus, ^{112}In , the prompt γ -ray spectrum for ^{238}Np displayed in Figure 6.15 is obtained. The identification of the γ -ray transitions in this nucleus is difficult due to the large background from prompt fission and competition with internal conversion since the majority of the known transitions in the nucleus ^{238}Np have energies below 100 keV. The structures at ~ 170 keV and ~ 210 keV are expected to arise from poor Doppler correction of ^{112}In transitions. Additionally, the structures at ~ 590 keV and ~ 810 keV arise from the neutron induced $(n, n'\gamma)$ reactions in ^{76}Ge .

Figure 6.15: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{238}Np with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 49$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 112$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.

6.3.1.3 Two-Proton Transfer Channel

The transfer of two protons from the projectile nucleus to the target results in cadmium ($Z=48$) and plutonium ($Z=94$) projectile-like and target-like nuclei, respectively. Then the transfer of neutrons either way results in differing isotopes of both these elements. The most intense channel is when no neutrons ($-2p +0n$) are transferred from the target to the projectile nucleus, this results in the projectile-like nucleus ^{110}Cd with binary partner ^{240}Pu . The coincident γ -ray spectrum for ^{110}Cd after gating on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and selecting $Z = 48$, $A = 110$ from PRISMA is shown in Figure 6.16. The main transitions observed in the spectrum are listed in Table 6.6 along with the literature values. A level scheme of the ground-state rotational band is shown in Figure 6.17. Transitions are observed up to $16\hbar$.

Figure 6.16: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{110}Cd with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 110$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

The prompt γ -ray spectrum for the target-like nucleus ^{240}Pu is shown in Figure 6.18. This is populated through the pick-up of two protons by the target from the projectile. After applying the selection of $Z = 48$ and $A = 110$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA a Doppler correction is applied for the binary partner to obtain this spectrum. Similar to the spectrum for ^{238}Np , the observation of transitions in this spectrum is not possible due to the high backgrounds arising from the prompt fission. Structures at ~ 500 keV and ~ 800 keV are expected to arise from neutron induced reactions on ^{76}Ge along with the structure at ~ 600 keV which may also have a contribution from the poor Doppler correction of a transition in ^{110}Cd .

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
335.38(30)	5.13(50)	1234(70)	335.5(2)	10 ⁺	8 ⁺
398.18(30)	4.44(70)	1124(67)	398.5(5)	7 ⁻	6 ⁺
466.14(20)	3.93(40)	882(59)	466.6(2)	9 ⁻	7 ⁻
560.49(10)	4.56(30)	1724(83)	560.9(1)	12 ⁻	10 ⁺
657.11(10)	4.80(10)	8266(182)	657.8(2)	2 ⁺	0 ⁺
794.55(20)	4.70(40)	962(62)	795.5(1)	8 ⁺	6 ⁺
853.47(30)	4.31(50)	527(46)	854.2(2)	14 ⁺	12 ⁺
883.60(10)	5.12(20)	4420(133)	884.5(1)	4 ⁺	2 ⁺
936.59(10)	4.86(50)	2457(99)	937.7(1)	6 ⁺	4 ⁺
1074.61(40)	4.65(101)	420(41)	1074.6(2)	16 ⁺	14 ⁺

Table 6.6: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{110}Cd . The literature values are taken from Ref. [147].

Figure 6.17: A partial level scheme for ^{110}Cd showing the transitions observed in this work.

Figure 6.18: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{240}Pu with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 110$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.

6.3.1.4 Three-Proton Transfer Channel

The transfer of three protons from the projectile to the target nucleus results in the population of silver ($Z = 47$) isotopes. The most intense mass for these isotopes is obtained without the transfer of any neutrons from the target to the projectile ($-3p+0n$), giving the nucleus ^{109}Ag . The prompt γ -ray spectrum shown in Figure 6.19 for ^{109}Ag is obtained by gating on $Z = 47$ and $A = 109$ from PRISMA and Doppler correcting using the trajectory reconstruction of the reaction products path through the PRISMA. From the spectrum shown in Figure 6.19, transitions previously identified for this nucleus are labelled.

Figure 6.19: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{109}Ag with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 47$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 109$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
156.42(20)	2.00(10)	167(26)	157.3(1)	13/2 ⁺	11/2 ⁺
186.73(20)	3.12(50)	519(46)	186.2(1)	25/2 ⁺	23/2 ⁺
213.60(20)	2.01(180)	240(31)	213.5(1)	17/2 ⁻	15/2 ⁻
249.08(20)	4.16(50)	624(50)	249.4(1)	23/2 ⁻	21/2 ⁺
273.07(20)	2.50(60)	218(30)	273.5(1)	21/2 ⁺	19/2 ⁺
298.51(30)	3.19(50)	289(34)	298.8(1)	27/2 ⁺	25/2 ⁺
393.95(20)	2.08(50)	173(26)	393.5(1)	29/2 ⁺	27/2 ⁺
405.89(40)	2.00(30)	84(18)	407.1(1)	31/2 ⁺	29/2 ⁺
640.69(40)	7.14(80)	1460(76)	640.6(2)	11/2 ⁺	9/2 ⁺
673.5(30)	3.60(120)	168(26)	673.4(2)	19/2 ⁺	17/2 ⁺
772.80(30)	3.54(90)	248(32)	772.3(3)	15/2 ⁺	13/2 ⁺
797.53(10)	4.98(20)	1462(76)	798.0(1)	13/2 ⁺	9/2 ⁺
963.37(20)	5.15(40)	732(54)	963.5(1)	17/2 ⁺	13/2 ⁺
1275.63(50)	5.81(90)	242(31)	1275.7(2)	15/2 ⁻	13/2 ⁺

Table 6.7: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{109}Ag . The literature values are taken from Ref. [147].

All of the transitions observed in Figure 6.19 are listed in Table 6.7 and are included in the partial level scheme shown in Figure 6.20. The unlabelled transition between $J^\pi = 17/2^+$ and $J^\pi = 15/2^+$ could not be observed in the spectrum due to its proximity to the 186.7-keV transition, it is therefore indicated by a dashed line in Figure 6.20. Transitions up to $31/2 \hbar$ are observed in the ground-state band of ^{109}Ag , with the 641-keV and 798-keV transitions populating the $J^\pi = 9/2^+$ state. A 214-keV transition from a negative-parity side band within the level scheme is also included. The $J^\pi = 15/2^-$ state that this transition populates feeds into the ground-state band through a 1276-keV transition. Figure 6.21 shows the prompt γ -ray spectrum for the target-like nucleus ^{241}Am after Doppler correcting for the binary partner of ^{109}Ag . From this spectrum there are no transitions observed due to the large background observed.

6.3.1.5 Four-Proton Transfer Channel

The transfer of four protons from the projectile nucleus to the target nucleus results in a series of projectile-like palladium ($Z = 46$) nuclei. Of these nuclei, the most intense mass identified from the analysis of the PRISMA spectrometer is $A = 106$ which is populated through the $-4p-2n$ channel. The resulting γ -ray spectrum gated on ^{106}Pd in PRISMA and Doppler corrected using the reaction product trajectories through the spectrometer is shown in Figure 6.22. The observed transitions labelled on the figure are listed in Table 6.8 along with the literature values for comparison.

A partial level scheme constructed from the transitions listed in Table 6.8 is shown in Figure 6.23 with

Figure 6.20: A partial level scheme for ^{109}Ag showing the transitions observed in this work.

Figure 6.21: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{241}Am with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 47$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 109$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.

transitions being observed up to $16\hbar$. The brackets surrounding the spins and parities listed in Table 6.8 indicate a tentative assignment. The binary partner of ^{106}Pd is populated through the $+4p+2n$ production channel which results in the nucleus ^{244}Cm . Applying a Doppler correction for the binary partner of the

Figure 6.22: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{106}Pd with the selection of $Z = 46$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 106$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
395.72(50)	5.56(80)	386(39)	396.26(5)	(7^-)	(5^-)
511.40(10)	4.46(10)	1770(84)	511.78(10)	2^+	0^+
554.82(20)	4.85(60)	642(51)	555.20(2)	12^+	10^+
570.38(20)	4.34(40)	651(51)	570.47(5)	10^+	8^+
716.74(10)	4.60(10)	1712(83)	717.31(10)	4^+	2^+
804.74(30)	4.17(70)	314(35)	805.10(2)	14^+	12^+
846.81(10)	4.69(20)	1060(65)	847.43(2)	6^+	4^+
885.18(20)	5.07(50)	501(45)	885.97(5)	8^+	6^+
1000.82(40)	2.00(60)	71(17)	1000.00(3)	(16^+)	14^+
1167.38(30)	5.06(50)	377(39)	1168.25(5)	$(5)^-$	4^+

Table 6.8: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{106}Pd . The literature values are taken from Ref. [147].

projectile-like nucleus and observing the coincident γ -rays gives the spectrum shown in Figure 6.24. As with the prompt γ -ray spectra for previously mentioned target-like reaction products, the identification of excited states in ^{244}Cm from this spectrum is not possible.

Figure 6.23: A partial level scheme for ^{106}Pd showing the transitions observed in this study.

Figure 6.24: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{244}Cm with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 46$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 106$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.

6.3.1.6 Five-Proton Transfer Channel

The transfer of five protons from the projectile to the target nucleus produces rhodium ($Z=45$) nuclei. As shown in Figure 5.13 this is the lowest value of Z that was identified in the ΔE versus E distribution (Figure 5.13) in the ionisation chamber of PRISMA. The transfer of five protons and two neutrons ($-5p-2n$ channel) gives the most intense rhodium nucleus ^{105}Rh . The prompt γ -ray spectrum obtained after gating on $Z = 45$ and $A = 105$ and Doppler correcting using the path reconstruction is shown in Figure 6.25. The transitions observed in the spectrum are listed, along with the transition energies from literature.

Figure 6.25: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{105}Rh with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 45$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 105$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
148.89(20)	3.06(30)	269(33)	149.12(1)	$9/2^+$	$7/2^+$
215.47(30)	2.22(50)	94(19)	216.00(10)	$25/2^+$	$23/2^+$
280.14(20)	2.00(160)	118(22)	280.40(30)	$27/2^+$	$25/2^+$
325.88(50)	3.87(100)	165(26)	326.15(1)	$5/2^-$	$1/2^-$
452.75(30)	2.24(100)	96(20)	453.70(10)	$11/2^+$	$9/2^+$
460.78(30)	2.00(170)	103(20)	460.40(20)	$23/2^+$	$21/2^+$
522.32(40)	3.64(70)	198(28)	522.80(10)	$9/2^-$	$5/2^-$
645.38(30)	4.78(80)	489(44)	645.80(10)	$13/2^+$	$9/2^+$
667.25(30)	3.59(60)	281(34)	668.10(10)	$13/2^-$	$9/2^-$
810.56(30)	2.50(60)	118(22)	810.60(50)	$17/2^+$	$13/2^+$
914.17(30)	3.32(50)	189(27)	915.40(60)	$21/2^+$	$17/2^+$

Table 6.9: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{105}Rh . The literature values are taken from Ref. [147].

Figure 6.26 shows a partial level scheme for ^{105}Rh constructed from the γ -ray transitions listed in Table 6.9. Additional γ -ray transitions that have been observed are assigned to other side bands for this nucleus. The binary partner of ^{105}Rh is ^{245}Bk . After applying a Doppler correction for the binary partner of ^{105}Rh the prompt γ -ray spectrum is shown in Figure 6.27. The observation of transitions in this spectrum is not possible.

Figure 6.26: Partial level scheme for ^{105}Rh showing the transitions observed in this work.

6.3.1.7 Nuclei of Interest

To observe the γ -ray spectra for the $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ nuclei of interest, the selection of the binary partners $^{118,116}\text{Cd}$ detected at the focal plane of the PRISMA spectrometer is initially required. Coincident γ -rays observed with the AGATA spectrometer detectors gated on the time coincidence peak between AGATA and PRISMA, the atomic number $Z = 48$, and the masses $A = 116$ and $A = 118$ are shown in Figure 6.28 and 6.29 for ^{116}Cd and ^{118}Cd , respectively. Compared to the most intense mass observed at the focal plane of PRISMA for the plutonium nuclei, $A = 110$, these nuclei are populated through the transfer of an additional 6 neutrons from the target to the projectile for ^{116}Cd and 8 neutrons for ^{118}Cd . A large drop in counts is therefore expected when observing the γ -ray spectra. As shown in Figures 6.28 and 6.30, the binning for the histogram has been changed from 1 keV per channel to 2 keV per channel to attempt to identify transitions in the projectile-like nuclei. The observed transitions for ^{116}Cd are listed in Table 6.10, from which a tentative level scheme has

Figure 6.27: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{245}Bk after with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 45$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 105$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.

been constructed. This is shown in Figure 6.29.

Figure 6.28: The γ -ray singles spectrum with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 116$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
512.7(60)	6.29(180)	101(20)	513.50(5)	2 ⁺	0 ⁺
706.0(60)	4.83(130)	84(18)	706.0(1)	4 ⁺	2 ⁺
807.0(80)	3.74(130)	73(17)	807.1(1)	6 ⁺	4 ⁺

Table 6.10: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{116}Cd taken from Ref. [147].

Figure 6.29: Partial level scheme for ^{116}Cd showing the transitions observed in this work.

Figure 6.30: The γ -ray singles spectrum with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 118$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

The identified literature values for the yrast band transitions in ^{118}Cd are listed in Table 6.11. From the transitions labelled in Figure 6.30 for ^{118}Cd , only the 676.4-keV transition can be confidently assigned to the $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$ transition. As a result no level scheme is produced.

E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
487.77(10)	2^+	0^+
677.13(10)	4^+	2^+
771.00(10)	(6^+)	4^+
654.96(10)	(8^+)	(6^+)
427.00(10)	(10^+)	(8^+)
561.1(10)	(12^+)	(10^+)
788.00(10)	(14^+)	(12^+)

Table 6.11: A table showing literature values for the identified yrast transitions in ^{118}Cd taken from Ref. [147].

Figure 6.31: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{232}Pu after with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 118$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.

The observation of γ -ray transitions in these cadmium nuclei, as well as the other projectile-like reaction products detailed in this section, indicates that the masses assigned to the projectile-like recoils during the PRISMA spectrometer analysis are correct. Therefore, after the consideration for neutron evaporation, confidence can be taken when applying a Doppler correction for the binary partners of the projectile-like cadmium nuclei that the resulting γ -ray spectrum will give the corresponding plutonium isotopes. In this case, the gate on $^{118,116}\text{Cd}$ and Doppler correction for the binary partners provides the prompt γ -ray spectra for $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$, respectively, as shown in Figures 6.31 and 6.32. Unlike the projectile like reaction products, these histograms have not been re-binned to 2 keV per channel as this does not provide any further

improvement when attempting to identify transitions.

Figure 6.32: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{234}Pu after with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 116$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction for the binary partner of the projectile nucleus has been applied.

Both figures show few distinguishable features. The background due to fission and the small production cross sections for $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ means the identification of γ -ray transitions in these nuclei is not possible without applying further selectivity on the data.

6.3.2 AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE Results

As explained in Section 4.3, the DANTE array was used during this experiment to detect the target-like products from the multi-nucleon transfer reactions. As such, the DANTE array, which is placed around the target, can be used to help to remove the fission background from the detection of the target-like products. The results of applying the conditions using the DANTE array are discussed for $^{234,236}\text{Pu}$ below. The results for ^{232}Pu are not included due to a lack of counts.

Figures 6.33 and 6.34 show three prompt γ -ray spectra for ^{236}Pu and ^{234}Pu , respectively, with different coincidence conditions applied. As shown by the spectra there is a significant drop in statistics from the previous level of selectivity. The comparison between the spectra shown in panel (a) and that shown in panel (b), which require coincident AGATA-PRISMA and AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE events, respectively, provides a result which is not expected. It was expected that the DANTE detectors should be $\sim 95\%$ efficient for the detection of reaction products. Therefore, there should only be a small drop in counts when applying a condition for DANTE to be included. The observed drop in counts between the two spectra is calculated to

Figure 6.33: Singles γ -ray spectra for ^{236}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{114}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner. (a) Spectrum with a condition on the detection of ^{114}Cd in PRISMA, a Doppler correction for the binary partner, and with a gate on the time coincidence between AGATA and PRISMA. (b) Same as (a), but also requiring that a signal is detected in DANTE within a time coincidence between DANTE and AGATA-PRISMA. (c) Same as (b) with an additional condition on the ToF versus TKEL distribution selecting only the target-like reaction products resulting from multi-nucleon transfer.

be $\sim 90\%$, giving an efficiency for DANTE of $\sim 10\%$.

Figures 6.33(c) and 6.34(c) show the result of attempting to remove events arising from fission by applying a gate on the ΔToF versus TKEL distribution (Figure 5.29). As shown by Figure 5.28, the separation of the distributions arising from the two reaction mechanisms was clearer before the change in digitiser firmware for the DANTE detector compared to that after the change. As mentioned previously, around 80% of the data was collected after the change in the digitiser firmware. This made the identification of events corresponding to target-like multi-nucleon transfer reaction products more difficult. Nevertheless, the selection was performed and the results are shown. The result of selecting the events corresponding to target-like nuclei shows a further

Figure 6.34: Singles γ -ray spectra for ^{234}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{116}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner. (a) AGATA γ -ray spectrum with a condition on the detection of ^{116}Cd in PRISMA, a Doppler correction for the binary partner, and with a gate on the time coincidence between AGATA and PRISMA. (b) Same as (a), but also requiring that a signal is detected in DANTE within a time coincidence between DANTE and AGATA-PRISMA. (c) Same as (b) with an additional condition on the ToF versus TKEL distribution selecting only the target-like reaction products resulting from multi-nucleon transfer.

drop in statistics compared to panel (b), leading to < 100 entries in the ^{236}Pu spectrum and < 30 entries in the ^{234}Pu spectrum. From these spectra, it is not possible to identify peaks with such low statistics. The number of counts decrease by $\sim 98\%$ from panels (b) to (c) in Figures 6.33 and 6.34. Given an intrinsic efficiency of $\sim 95\%$ for the DANTE detector and the same decrease in statistics after selecting the events arising only from multi-nucleon transfer, the resulting γ -ray spectra (panels (c)) would be expected to have ~ 360 and ~ 1580 entries for ^{234}Pu and ^{236}Pu , respectively.

6.3.3 TKEL Gated AGATA-PRISMA Results

As shown in Section 6.3.2, coincidence with DANTE reduced the counts of the resulting γ -ray spectra such that there were no observed transitions. As explained in Section 5.4 the application of selectivity on the total kinetic energy loss (TKEL) can provide some separation between γ -rays arising from different reaction mechanisms. This section describes an alternative to the use of DANTE through the application of TKEL gates to attempt to reduce the fission background. Figures 6.35, 6.36, and 6.38 show the results of gating on the TKEL measured in the ionisation chamber of PRISMA whilst applying a condition on the binary partner cadmium nuclei and a Doppler correction for the target-like $^{236,234,232}\text{Pu}$ nuclei. The TKEL distribution is seen in the top panel of the figures, along with the gate applied. The result of the application of the gate, with the ungated γ -ray energy spectrum are shown in the bottom and middle panels, respectively. The bottom panel also indicates transitions that have been tentatively identified for the plutonium nuclei.

6.3.3.1 TKEL selectivity for ^{236}Pu

The TKEL-gated γ -ray spectrum for ^{236}Pu is shown in Figure 6.35(c). The TKEL distribution shown in Figure 6.35(a) does not show distinct structures that provide a clear separation between reaction mechanisms, meaning the removal of events arising fission of target-like nuclei is challenging. This is reflected in Figure 6.35(c) which shows a reduced level of background to that in the middle panel but with reduced statistics. The gate applied in Figure 6.35(a) was determined using the knowledge of the expected selectivity described in Section 5.4 when selecting a low-TKEL value. A scan of low-TKEL regions were then tested to determine which gate best reduced the fission background in the resulting spectrum shown in Figure 6.35(c). Nevertheless, transitions have been observed and are listed in Table 6.12. These transitions are observed with aid of the accepted literature values for the ground-state band transitions of ^{236}Pu . Using some of these transitions a level scheme could be constructed for the ground-state rotational band in ^{236}Pu , however, it is noticed that the majority of energies that would be assigned to transitions deviate from the literature values by ~ 2 keV. A potential combination of factors could be influencing the accuracy of the measured values shown in the table. Finally, the optimisation of the Doppler correction for the target-like reaction products could be another factor influencing the measured centroid energies. The Doppler correction for the target-like nucleus is done by inferring kinematics for a binary partner which is not observed.

Figure 6.35: (a) TKEL distribution for ^{114}Cd that is gated on to obtain the coincident γ -ray energy spectra. (b) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{236}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{114}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner when selecting all of the distribution in (a). (c) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{236}Pu after the gate shown in (a) is applied. Only the resulting γ -ray energy spectra are re-binned here to identify transitions.

6.3.3.2 TKEL selectivity for ^{234}Pu

The transitions tentatively identified in Figure 6.36(c) are the first transitions identified in ^{234}Pu and are listed in Table 6.13. The TKEL gate applied in Figure 6.36(a) was applied using the same method as the gate applied in Figure 6.35(a). Using the identified transitions, a tentative level scheme, shown in Figure 6.37, has been built using the aid of the isotopic level schemes and systematics (see Section 6.1.2) of ^{236}Pu , ^{238}Pu , and ^{240}Pu . The figure shows the energies of the excited states using the identified transition energies. As the $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ and $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$ transitions are not visible in the γ -ray energy spectrum, it is not possible

This Work			Literature		
E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	E_γ [keV]	J_i^π	J_f^π
155.56(50)	2.45(120)	28(11)	158.35(2)	6 ⁺	4 ⁺
211.11(60)	2.00(50)	18(8)	209.90(20)	8 ⁺	6 ⁺
257.39(60)	2.17(140)	14(8)	257.80(20)	10 ⁺	8 ⁺
297.12(100)	2.00(170)	23(10)	300.80(20)	12 ⁺	10 ⁺
373.39(150)	6.79(190)	33(12)	372.40(20)	16 ⁺	14 ⁺
401.84(60)	2.29(80)	13(7)	402.00(50)	18 ⁺	16 ⁺
583.44(120)	6.42(190)	48(14)	582.80(20)	(2 ⁻)	3 ⁻
652.67(120)	4.05(260)	25(10)	653.68(12)	1 ⁻	2 ⁺

Table 6.12: Comparison of measured γ -ray energies, FWHM, and areas with literature values for ^{236}Pu .

to add these transitions to the level scheme. The energy of these states have been inferred from isotopic systematics. Additional identified transitions to those placed in the tentative level scheme are listed in Table 6.13. It is anticipated that some of the transitions listed in Table 6.13 that are not included in the tentative level scheme will be transitions in a side band of the level scheme of ^{234}Pu . In particular, there are several transitions listed in the table that are close to transition energies in the level schemes for the isotopes ^{236}Pu , ^{238}Pu , and ^{240}Pu . Unfortunately, the limited number of counts in the spectrum means that the identification of transitions from a side band connecting with the tentative ground-state band shown in Figure 6.37 is not possible. Additionally, higher energy transitions identified that are expected to indicate the transition from negative-parity to positive-parity states could not be added to the level scheme.

E_γ [keV]	FWHM [keV]	Peak area	Intensity
157.82(260)	10.00(550)	19(9)	100(66)
196.37(50)	2.55(110)	9(6)	-
211.22(50)	2.00(60)	6(5)	8(8)
232.69(50)	2.00(50)	5(4)	-
250.99(110)	2.43(130)	6(5)	5(5)
300.37(60)	2.49(120)	7(5)	5(5)
348.90(160)	4.10(130)	8(6)	6(6)
364.05(100)	5.01(150)	12(7)	-
373.37(50)	2.00(60)	5(4)	-
435.38(120)	5.48(190)	14(8)	-
494.67(140)	3.93(270)	9(6)	-
516.87(70)	2.00(90)	6(5)	-
682.68(90)	2.91(150)	7(5)	-
766.74(50)	2.00(50)	5(5)	-

Table 6.13: Identified γ -ray energies, FWHM, areas, and intensities for ^{234}Pu . The intensities are only shown for the transitions listed in the level scheme and are normalised to the 157-keV transition.

Figure 6.36: (a) TKEL distribution for ^{116}Cd that is gated on to obtain the coincident γ -ray energy spectra. (b) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{234}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{116}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner when selecting all of the distribution in (a). (c) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{234}Pu after the gate shown in (a) is applied. Only the resulting γ -ray energy spectra are re-binned here to identify transitions.

6.3.3.3 TKEL Selectivity for ^{232}Pu

To attempt to provide selectivity of γ -ray transitions in ^{232}Pu the application of a gate on the TKEL distribution in coincidence with AGATA and the selection of ^{118}Cd in PRISMA is performed. The TKEL distribution along with the selectivity applied and the resulting prompt γ -ray spectrum after applying the gate is shown in Figure 6.38. Due to the large amount of nucleons transferred to populate this nucleus, the counts in the TKEL gated γ -ray spectrum suffer significantly. However, tentative assignments of transitions have been made for the first time in this nucleus. The TKEL gate applied in Figure 6.38(a) was applied using

Figure 6.37: Tentative level scheme for ${}^{234}\text{Pu}$ using transitions identified from the AGATA-PRISMA, TKEL-gated γ -ray spectrum. Only transitions in the ground-state band are identified. Here, the values of x and y are the energies of the $J^\pi = (4^+)$ and $J^\pi = (2^+)$ states, respectively, which could not be identified in this work.

the same method as the gate applied in Figure 6.35(a). Due to the limited statistics, the peaks in the γ -ray spectrum are not able to be fit with a Gaussian distribution to provide information on the FWHM or peak areas and are therefore only labelled on the γ -ray spectrum in Figure 6.38(c). A tentative level scheme has been made using some of the identified transitions which are close to the transitions of nearby plutonium nuclei from Figure 6.38(c). This is shown in Figure 6.39. Similarly to the level scheme for ${}^{234}\text{Pu}$, only transitions in the yrast band have been assigned therefore limiting the amount of understanding that can be obtained relating to the octupole correlations in this nucleus, due to the lack of negative-parity states identified.

6.3.3.4 Rotational Alignments for Nuclei of Interest

From the tentative assignments of transitions to the ground-state bands of ${}^{232,234}\text{Pu}$, the plot of the total angular momentum along the rotation axis, I_x as a function of the rotational frequency, $\hbar\omega$ can be obtained, as shown in Figure 6.40. The transitions identified for ${}^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ are plotted alongside those for the nearby isotopes for comparison. As shown, the data for ${}^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ closely matches the results for the nearby plutonium isotopes.

Figure 6.38: (a) TKEL distribution for ^{118}Cd that is gated on to obtain the coincident γ -ray energy spectra. (b) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{232}Pu after gating on the binary partner ^{118}Cd and Doppler correcting for the binary partner when selecting all of the distribution in (a). (c) shows the γ -ray spectrum for ^{232}Pu after the gate shown in (a) is applied. Only the resulting γ -ray energy spectra are re-binned here to identify transitions.

6.3.3.5 TKEL Evolution

Observing the TKEL distributions for binary partners of the three plutonium nuclei discussed here, it is noticed that there is an evolution in the structure of the distribution with respect to a change in A . It is seen that as the value of A increases, a separation of the TKEL distribution becomes more apparent, with Figure 6.38(a) showing a separation. To investigate this further the TKEL distributions for all observed A values for $Z = 48$ are shown in Figure 6.41. It is clear from this figure that there is an evolution as A changes, starting from ^{118}Cd which shows a separation between two distributions, the TKEL distribution changes to

Figure 6.39: Tentative level scheme for ^{232}Pu using transitions identified from the AGATA-PRISMA, TKEL-gated γ -ray spectrum. Only transitions in the ground-state band are identified. Here, the values of x and y are the energies of the $J^\pi = (4^+)$ and $J^\pi = (2^+)$ states, respectively, which could not be identified in this work.

a single distribution with a slope towards higher TKEL values for ^{114}Cd . This changes to slope towards lower TKEL values for ^{110}Cd and finally begins to move back to a central position for the lowest mass identified, corresponding to ^{105}Cd . This evolution is not fully understood, nor is it expected to occur as the mass changes. This evolution is seen to occur for atomic numbers with $Z \geq 48$ identified in the PRISMA spectrometer, with a clearer separation between two structures at lower A values. For nuclei with $Z \leq 48$ observed in PRISMA, the shape of the TKEL distribution remains consistent as the mass changes.

Figure 6.40: Total angular momentum along the rotation axis for ground-state bands in $^{232,234,236,238,240}\text{Pu}$ as a function of rotational frequency. In the case of $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ the data points are calculated using the transition energies identified in this work.

Figure 6.41: A plot showing the TKEL distributions for the series of observed cadmium nuclei ranging from $^{105-118}\text{Cd}$.

Chapter 7

Summary

This thesis is concerned with an experiment that was conducted at the Legnaro National Laboratory. The aim of the experiment was to search for excited states in the neutron-deficient plutonium isotopes $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$. These nuclei lie in a region of predicted octupole deformed plutonium nuclei and have not previously been studied in in-beam γ -ray spectroscopy. In the experiment, a 857 MeV ^{112}Sn beam was incident on a ^{238}U target. The reaction products of interest were produced from multi-nucleon transfer reactions. Three apparatus used in the experiment were the AGATA spectrometer, the PRISMA magnetic spectrometer, and the DANTE detector array. The AGATA spectrometer detects the prompt γ rays which are emitted at the target position. The PRISMA mass spectrometer identifies the Z and A values of the projectile-like reaction products. The combination of information from AGATA and PRISMA enables the study of prompt γ rays from specific reaction products. DANTE was used to detect the target-like reaction products. To be able to identify excited states in the plutonium nuclei of interest, the removal of events arising from fission, which contribute to the background observed in the prompt γ -ray spectra, is required. These backgrounds are observed due to the high fission cross section when using a ^{238}U target. The application of a gate on the time-of-flight difference between that measured by the DANTE detector opposite the entrance to the PRISMA spectrometer and the entrance MCP detector of PRISMA provides a method to separate multi-nucleon transfer events from events arising from fission.

Results from the analysis of the data collected from the detectors have been presented. Corrections to the data collected from the AGATA spectrometer have been performed including correction for the effect of neutron damages to the detector material, energy calibrations, and time alignments. The analysis of the PRISMA data has been carried out including the calibration of the detectors, the identification of the atomic numbers of the nuclei observed at the focal plane, the optimisation of optical parameters, charge-state

selection, and aberrational corrections. The resulting mass distributions have good resolutions giving clear separation between individual masses, allowing good selectivity of the projectile-like nuclei.

Unlike AGATA and PRISMA, the analysis of the DANTE detector provided more challenges. The first step in the analysis was to align the timestamp of MCP detector opposite to the entrance to the PRISMA spectrometer with the timestamps of AGATA and PRISMA, therefore allowing AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE coincidences to be observed. This provided more of a challenge than the analysis of AGATA and PRISMA. Firstly, the time offset between the DANTE events and the AGATA and PRISMA events was determined for each individual run. This involved sorting a sample of the raw data to compare the timestamps of DANTE and AGATA for a particular run, then, after determining the offset values, they were applied in order to merge the PRISMA and DANTE raw data. However, due to the change of the digitiser firmware during the experiment, modification of the sort code for the time alignment was necessary. As a result, the DANTE spectra differed between runs where the different digitiser firmware was used. This impacted the subsequent analysis steps. Position calibrations had to be applied individually for groups of runs according to the digitiser firmware that was used. Separate calibration files were required for each case. After the merging of the PRISMA and DANTE data, a polynomial gate on the 2D spectrum of the time-of-flight difference (ΔToF) versus the total kinetic energy loss (TKEL) was set for individual runs. This was used to reduce the fission background. The individual application of the gate was required due to the inconsistency in the separation of the reaction mechanisms as a function of run number. This meant that, for example, gates applied to earlier runs would not select all relevant data in later runs.

In addition to the selectivity expected from the DANTE detector array, nine La_3Br detectors were placed around the target position during the experiment for the measurement of excited state lifetimes. As mentioned in Section 4.6 the identification of lifetimes was not possible during the analysis. This was due to the low counting statistics and background in the resulting γ -ray spectra and also due to the detectors not being applied to the main sort code of the analysis.

The spectra resulting from the coincidence analysis of the AGATA and PRISMA data show the selection of the projectile-like reaction products, with transitions observed for the most intense masses for each observed atomic number. The AGATA-PRISMA spectra, applying a Doppler correction for the unobserved target-like reaction products, have also been corrected for the binary partners of the most intense masses observed. The spectra show a significant background due to γ rays following fission. As a result, the identification of transitions for target-like nuclei with $93 \leq Z \leq 97$ was difficult. The results of coincidence analysis of DANTE and AGATA-PRISMA data show very limited statistics in the γ -ray spectra, allowing no

identification of excited states in the nuclei of interest.

Several problems were encountered throughout the analysis process. These are listed here:

- **Deviation of PRISMA mass centroids** - It was found that the centroids of the Z -gated mass distributions resulting from the analysis of the PRISMA spectrometer deviated from the expected mass centroids throughout the experiment. To correct for this, two-dimensional gates had to be applied to individual masses for each observed Z within each run of the experiment.
- **High backgrounds in γ -ray spectra** - The in-beam prompt γ -ray spectra showed significant background. The most likely causes of this background are fission fragments with an incorrect Doppler correction and the incomplete collection of the energy of a γ ray due to Compton scattering from AGATA detectors close to the edge of the array.
- **DANTE digitiser firmware change** - The change in digitiser firmware for the DANTE MCP resulted in worse separation of the structures observed in the time-of-flight difference plots. This meant that the removal of events arising from fission was more difficult after the change in firmware, which accounted for the majority of the data set.
- **DANTE efficiency loss** - It was noticed that there was a significant drop in statistics when requiring the condition for DANTE to be included in events, which led to γ -ray spectra that provide no distinguishable features. Literature values suggest the efficiency of the DANTE detector array for heavy ions to be $\sim 95\%$, however, an efficiency of $\sim 10\%$ was measured in this study. The unexpected loss of statistics arises when comparing AGATA-PRISMA-gated γ -ray spectra to AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE-gated γ -ray spectra for the target-like reaction products. As a result, the use of the DANTE detector was not favoured to be able to identify excited states in the nuclei of interest. It has been shown that the drop in counts between the AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE-gated γ -ray spectrum and the AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE-gated γ -ray spectrum with the application of the polynomial gate on the multi-nucleon transfer reaction products in the Δ ToF versus TKEL distribution, is of the order of magnitude that is expected when considering the high fission probability of the target-like reaction products.

Removal of the requirement for conditions on DANTE was made because the low DANTE efficiency was causing low counts. Instead gates on the TKEL distributions were applied to observe AGATA-PRISMA coincidence spectra, from which excited states have been identified. The gating on the TKEL has been performed for the $^{232,234,236}\text{Pu}$ nuclei. As a result, the first tentative identification of excited states in $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$ has been made with the aid of systematics of nearby plutonium isotopes, leading to the production of tentative level schemes. Additionally, aligned angular momenta for the positive-parity states have been

plotted and compared to those for the isotopic plutonium nuclei. The limited amount of statistics means that the identification of negative-parity states is not possible for $^{232,234}\text{Pu}$, therefore information regarding the evolution of octupole deformation in this region cannot be made.

Future experiments would benefit from improvements to the online sorting of the data. Providing better understanding of the reaction whilst conducting the experiment would allow changes to be made dynamically. Additionally, the DANTE detector array was not included in the analysis software until after the experiment had been conducted. As a result, the selection of coincident AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE events was not possible until later in the analysis. If the results of the AGATA-PRISMA-DANTE coincidence spectra were found earlier in the analysis process, further efforts could have been made to account for the loss in statistics.

The development of the AGATA detector array to its full 4π configuration is expected to provide a significant increase to the detection efficiency and performance compared to third generation germanium detector arrays. Future tests of the AGATA detector array with high γ -ray multiplicity reactions are scheduled [150], before the introduction of new “phase 2” electronics and the AGATA zero-degrees campaign. After this the AGATA detector array will be moved to GANIL to begin a new experimental campaign. In the GANIL campaign, there will be opportunities to extend the work described in this thesis using AGATA coupled to the VAMOS recoil separator.

Appendix A

Analysis Codes and Configuration Files

During the course of the analysis numerous scripts and codes were used to help with the processing of the data. This appendix will briefly explain the codes that were used. The codes are listed in different sections based on the part of the analysis in which they were used. Additional configuration files that are complementary to the codes are also included to give better understanding of the analysis process.

A.1 AGATA Analysis

There are two main processing steps of the analysis of the AGATA spectrometer, Local Level Processing (LLP) and Global Level Processing (GLP). This appendix focuses on the LLP stages, which are explained along with the codes used. The data acquisition online uses the Narval framework which employs actors which are used to process the data [110]. Within the LLP there are three main actors as part of the Narval framework that are used to process the data flow, these are the preprocessing, PSA, and post-PSA actors, as detailed in Section 5.1. This appendix separates the codes according to the different actors. The GLP deals with the merging or building of the data to store in root trees after the calibrations and corrections are applied during the LLP analysis stages and has not been altered during this analysis. Because of this, it is not mentioned here.

A.1.1 The Preprocessing Actor

The preprocessing actor is used to manage the preparation of the traces and includes initial energy calibrations and time alignments. The codes employed, along with a brief description of their purpose, are listed

below. It should be mentioned that the entirety of the preprocessing analysis was performed online and was not changed offline.

- **RecalEnergy:** This program is used to load a γ -ray spectrum, from a calibration source, then search for the peaks within the spectrum. Once observed, the peaks are fit and matched with reference energies from known γ -ray sources. A polynomial calibration can then be applied. This is carried out for different channels (core and segments) for each crystal. The calibration parameters can then be saved and output to the terminal for the user. This script is employed throughout the AGATA analysis whenever a calibration is needed.
- **xTalkSort:** This program is used to analyse the effects of the cross-talk observed in the segments of the AGATA detector crystals. It sorts and analyses AGATA events by extracting segment and core energy information which are used to create cross-talk spectra. These spectra are then used by RecalEnergy to determine cross-talk matrices and coefficients to correct for the effect. The program can also be used to check the spectra after correcting for the cross-talk.
- **Colupdate.py:** This is a python script used to insert the calibration parameters into configuration files which are later referenced in the merging of the data. The user must provide the chosen columns from the input file to use.

A.1.2 The post-PSA Actor

- **sortPSAHits:** Estimates the impact of neutron damage on crystals and correct the measured energies. A grid of correction parameters for both electron and hole trapping parameters is applied which are determined as the optimum parameters that minimise the FWHM and the tail on the left hand of the energy peaks.
- **Trapping.cal:** This is a configuration file that contains output trapping parameters of SortPSAHits which are used to correct for the damage due to neutron interactions within the detector material.
- **SolveTT.py:** Used in the global time alignment to identify the time peaks and align them to a given channel. The result should be that all peaks are well aligned for each segment and core with respect to all segments, within a crystal.

A.2 PRISMA Analysis

- **CheckCal.C:** Used for the calibrations of the MCP, MWPPAC, and IC of the PRISMA magnetic spectrometer. Within the ROOT macro, are several functions which are used to plot spectra to aid in the calibrations and setting of thresholds of the detectors of the spectrometer. Additionally the macro can be used to convert polynomial gates applied during the calibrations to ".ban" format which are then read in the configuration files during the analysis sorting.
- **MCP_cal.C:** A C macro used specifically for the calibration of the MCP position matrix. This is used to apply the correction detailed in section 5.2.1.1 using input values measured from the observation of the matrix from the output root file.

A.2.1 Configuration Files

Here are listed a set of configuration files that are stored in a configuration directory which is referenced when running the sorting of the PRISMA analysis.

- **mcp.conf:** This configuration file contains the paths to the '.ban' files used for the calibration of the MCP detector. These files provide values for polynomial gates applied to matrices used for the analysis.
- **solver.conf:** This configuration file contains parameters related to the optical parameter optimisation, as mentioned in Section 5.2.4.2.
- **ppac.conf:** Contains the paths to files that contain parameters used to set the MWPPAC calibrations and thresholds.
- **zed.conf:** Contains parameters for the range of allowed atomic numbers in the sort and also paths to the gates set on the observed atomic numbers as detailed in Section 5.2.2.
- **ionch.conf:** Contains the paths to files that contain parameters used to set the ionisation chamber calibrations and thresholds.
- **mass.conf:** Contains information related to the identification of the masses of the reaction products detected in the ionisation chamber of the PRISMA spectrometer. These include paths

to the files which contain the calibration parameters for the linear calibration and mass calibrations explained in Section 5.2.5.

- **side.conf:** Contains the paths to files that contain parameters used to set the side sections of the ionisation chamber calibrations and thresholds.
- **binarypartner.conf:** Configuration file containing information about the binary partner and reaction. Information such as the mass and atomic numbers of the beam and target, the target thickness, and the beam energy are included.
- **manager.conf:** Contains the paths to all the configuration files. This file is referenced when running the analysis of the data.
- **LUTPrisma.conf:** Contains information related to the individual channels of the detectors of the PRISMA spectrometer that produce independent signals. Examples of these include the different MWPPAC sections providing ToF information and also positional information.
- **selectorPrisma.conf:** Contains configuration information for the sorting of the PRISMA data. This file is taken as an input when compiling the data and is modifiable to select or deselect conditions to alter the output of the sort. As an example, an option labelled “ANA_HISTS” can be set to ‘YES’ or ‘NO’ to either enable or disable the output root files to contain histograms that have been created using the application of calibrations or additional calculated parameters from any analysis step.

A.2.2 Data Sorting

- **PrismaFilters:** Used to sort the data for the PRISMA spectrometer. Takes raw PRISMA data, chosen by selecting a run number, and applies corrections using the links to all other configuration files which contain application of parameters, calibrations, and thresholds. These configuration files are referenced in the working directory and are automatically chosen unless specified. The output files are root trees which can be viewed through a root terminal from which the user can construct a desired histogram.
- **RunAnalysis:** Used to sort the data of the PRISMA spectrometer. The user can either choose to run

PrismaFilters alone or to run PrismaFilters and then agataselector. The second option allows the combination of the outputted root trees into a single output with preprogrammed histograms created that are useful in the analysis (e.g. ΔE vs. E , IC_E vs. $\rho\beta$, Z -gated mass distributions, etc.).

A.3 DANTE Analysis

A.3.1 Time Alignment

- **ListFrames:** Used to print the individual dataframes for files in ADF format. The output provides information about the ADF key, the timestamp of the dataframe, the event number, what is contained within the event, and also the difference in timestamps between the previous and current event. The ADF key can be used to identify the ancillary detector, with the event number describing which signal of the ancillary is produced.
- **ReadCaenRaw.set:** Configuration file that is read when running ReadCaenRaw. This file contains information regarding the individual ancillary detectors including board and channel numbers along with offsets.
- **generate.sh:** This script is used to produce a text file output which contains the output of the ListFrames script for AGATA and selected ancillary detector. The output is then used to compare timestamps between AGATA and the ancillary detector.
- **fix.C:** This program is used to take the text file output from generate.sh and produces a root file which compares the timestamps of the AGATA array and the ancillary detector. This is used to determine a time offset peak which is then applied when merging the caendat data to produce an ADF file to time align the ancillary detectors.
- **ReadCaenRaw:** Used to read raw ancillary data in Caendat format and produce an output file combining all raw caendat files into a single file in ADF format. This is used in the DANTE analysis to combine the DANTE and PRISMA raw data with the additional time offset value.

A.4 Merging

- **gen_conf.py:** Script used to generate the configuration files required before the sorting of the AGATA and ancillary data. Information relating to the AGATA analysis is stored here including the neutron-damage correction parameter files, the recalibration files, global time alignments, and the ForceSegmentsToCore option. Additionally, ancillary configuration paths are specified, trapping parameters are linked to, and Narval actors are identified.
- **Topology.conf:** Contains the list and order of the application of the Narval actors that are used to process the AGATA and ancillary data. Within this file, a loop is defined over all the AGATA detector crystals in use. This loop goes through several chains of actors, each used to run different stages of the processing. An example of a typical workflow is as follows; AGATA crystals are looped over to read post-PSA data and further filtering is applied, then the AGATA data is sent to an event builder. The event builder takes AGATA and ancillary data and sends them to the event merger to combine the two. The merger combines AGATA and ancillary data and applies tracking logic to match the correct events. The TreeBuilder is then used to store the processed data into root trees.
- **femul:** This is a program that takes the topology file as an input and runs the sorting and merging of the data. Femul is able to run complex topologies (multiple input lines and one output line) and works as an alternative to using Narval directly.
- **selector.conf:** Contains configuration information for the AGATA spectrometer along with all other ancillaries present in the experiment. Individual detector configurations are listed and are allowed to be selected or deselected. In addition, coincidence information between the detectors is present allowing coincidence timing windows to be managed. Options such as 'TOF_OK' are present for the PRISMA spectrometer to allow the option to filter the data for events which only have an accepted time-of-flight signal through the PRISMA spectrometer. This file is edited throughout the analysis to suit the user's preferences.
- **RunSelector:** Used to run the sorting of the data of the AGATA spectrometer and all selected ancillary detectors. This takes the selector.conf as an input along with options to limit the number of events processed and the number of threads used to process the data to limit the time to process the data and the strain on the computer. The user can then view the results of the

analysis of all detectors together in a single output root file.

Appendix B

In-beam AGATA-PRISMA Spectra

B.1 Projectile-like Reaction Products

B.1.1 tin - 0p channel

Figure B.1: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{113}Sn with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 50$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 113$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

Figure B.2: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{111}Sn with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 50$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 111$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

B.1.2 indium - 1p transfer channel

Figure B.3: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{111}In with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 49$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 111$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

Figure B.4: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{113}In with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 49$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 113$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

B.1.3 cadmium - 2p transfer channel

Figure B.5: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{109}Cd with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 109$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

Figure B.6: The γ -ray singles spectrum with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 48$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 111$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

B.1.4 silver - 3p transfer channel

Figure B.7: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{108}Ag with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 47$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 108$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

Figure B.8: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{110}Ag with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 47$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 110$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

B.1.5 palladium - 4p transfer channel

Figure B.9: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{105}Pd with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 46$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 105$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

Figure B.10: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{107}Pd with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 46$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 107$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

B.1.6 rhodium - 5p transfer channel

Figure B.11: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{104}Rh with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 45$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 104$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

Figure B.12: The γ -ray singles spectrum for ^{106}Rh with a gate on the prompt time peak between AGATA and PRISMA and the selection of $Z = 45$ from the ionisation chamber of PRISMA, and $A = 106$ from the corresponding Z -gated mass distribution. A Doppler correction based on the path of the reaction product through the PRISMA spectrometer has been applied.

References

- [1] Institute of Physics. *100 incredible years of physics - nuclear physics* (2020).
- [2] World Nuclear Association. *Outline History of Nuclear Energy* (2025).
- [3] J. Chadwick. Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character, **136**, (1932), pp. 692.
- [4] S. A. Moszkowski and C. W. Wong. *Early Nuclear Physics*.
- [5] M. G. Mayer. Phys. Rev., **75**, (1949), pp. 1969.
- [6] A. N. Bohr and B. R. Mottelson. Mat. Fys. Medd. Dan. Vid. Selsk., **27**.
- [7] I. Y. Lee, M. A. Deleplanque, and K. Vetter. Rep. Prog. Phys., **66**, (2003), p. 1095.
- [8] S. Akkoyun *et al.* Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **668**, (2012), pp. 26.
- [9] J. Valiente-Dobón *et al.* Nucl. Instr. and Meth. Phys. Res. A, **1049**, (2023), p. 168040.
- [10] Y. Cao, S. E. Agbemava, A. V. Afanasjev, W. Nazarewicz, and E. Olsen. Phys. Rev. C, **102**, (2020), p. 024311.
- [11] K. Nomura, R. Rodríguez-Guzmán, L. M. Robledo, and J. E. García-Ramos. Phys. Rev. C, **103**, (2021), p. 044311.
- [12] J. Lilley. *Nuclear Physics Principles and Applications*. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd., Chichester, NY (2001).
- [13] K. S. Krane. *Introductory Nuclear Physics*. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd., New York, NY (1988).
- [14] S. S. M. Wong. *Introductory Nuclear Physics*. Prentice-Hall, Inc (1998).
- [15] R. Casten and R. Casten. *Nuclear Structure From a Simple Perspective*. Oxford University Press (2000).

- [16] P. A. Butler and W. Nazarewicz. *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, **68**, (1996), pp. 349.
- [17] E. S. Paul. *Lecture Notes in Advanced Nuclear Physics, PHYS490* (2009).
- [18] E. Fermi. *Z. Physik*, **60**, (1930), pp. 320.
- [19] N. Bohr and J. A. Wheeler. *Phys. Rev.*, **56**, (1939), pp. 426.
- [20] D. L. Hill and J. A. Wheeler. *Phys. Rev.*, **89**, (1953), pp. 1102.
- [21] W. Nazarewicz. *Nucl. Phys. A*, **574**, (1994), pp. 27.
- [22] I. Hamamoto and B. R. Mottelson. *Scholarpedia*, **7**, (2011), p. 10693.
- [23] K. Heyde. *Basic Ideas and Concepts in Nuclear Physics*. IOP Publishing, 3rd edition edition (2004).
- [24] I. Ragnarsson and S. G. Nilsson. *Shapes and Shells in Nuclear Structure*. Cambridge University Press (1995).
- [25] H. A. Jahn, E. Teller, and F. G. Donnan. *Proc. Roy. Soc. Lond. A*, **161**, (1937), pp. 220.
- [26] F. Asaro, F. Stephens, and I. Perlman. *Phys. Rev.*, **92**, (1953), pp. 1495.
- [27] F. Stephens, F. Asaro, and I. Perlman. *Phys. Rev.*, **96**, (1954), pp. 1568.
- [28] K. Alder, A. Bohr, T. Huus, B. Mottelson, and A. Winther. *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, **28**, (1956), pp. 432.
- [29] G. Leander, W. Nazarewicz, G. Bertsch, and J. Dudek. *Nucl. Phys. A*, **453**, (1986), pp. 58.
- [30] P. A. Butler. *J. Phys. G*, **43**, (2016), p. 073002.
- [31] P. Spagnoletti *et al.* *Phys. Rev. C*, **105**, (2022), p. 024323.
- [32] P. A. Butler *et al.* *Nature*, **10**, (2019), p. 2473.
- [33] K. Hardt, P. Schüler, C. Günther, J. Recht, K. Blume, and H. Wilzek. *Nucl. Phys. A*, **419**, (1984), pp. 34.
- [34] R. Kulesa *et al.* *Z. Phy. A*, **344**, (1989), pp. 299.
- [35] L. P. Gaffney *et al.* *Nature*, **497**, (2013), pp. 199.
- [36] J. Cocks *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **645**, (1999), pp. 61.
- [37] H. Wollersheim *et al.* *Nucl. Physics A*, **556**, (1993), pp. 261.
- [38] T.Kibedi and R. Spear. *Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables*, **80**, (2002), pp. 35.

- [39] T. F. Thorsteinsen, K. Nybø, and G. Løvnhøiden. *Physica Scripta*, **42**, (1990), p. 141.
- [40] M. Debray *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **568**, (1994), pp. 141.
- [41] F. Cristancho *et al.* *Phys. Rev. C*, **49**, (1994), pp. 663.
- [42] S. Khazrouni, A. Chevallier, J. Chevallier, O. Helene, G. Ramanantsizehena, and N. Schulz. *Z. Phys. A*, **320**, (1985), pp. 535.
- [43] N. Schulz *et al.* *Z. Phys. A*, **339**, (1991), pp. 325.
- [44] M. Aliche *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **567**, (1994), pp. 685.
- [45] I. Ahmad *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **505**, (1989), pp. 257.
- [46] I. Ahmad *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **576**, (1994), pp. 246.
- [47] I. Ahmad, J. Gindler, A. Friedman, R. Chasman, and T. Ishii. *Nucl. Phys. A*, **472**, (1987), pp. 285.
- [48] R. K. Sheline and G. A. Leander. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, **51**, (1983), pp. 359.
- [49] W. Reviol *et al.* *Phys. Rev. C*, **74**, (2006), p. 044305.
- [50] D. Ward, G. Dracoulis, J. Leigh, R. Charity, D. Hinde, and J. Newton. *Nucl. Phys. A*, **406**, (1983), pp. 591.
- [51] M. Dahlinger *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **484**, (1988), pp. 337.
- [52] J. Hughes *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **512**, (1990), pp. 275.
- [53] N. J. Hammond *et al.* *Phys. Rev. C*, **65**, (2002), p. 064315.
- [54] H. Ower *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **388**, (1982), pp. 421.
- [55] B. Ackermann *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **559**, (1993), pp. 61.
- [56] S. E. Agbemava, A. V. Afanasjev, and P. Ring. *Phys. Rev. C*, **93**, (2016), p. 044304.
- [57] I. Ahmad, J. E. Gindler, R. R. Betts, R. R. Chasman, and A. M. Friedman. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, **49**, (1982), p. 1758.
- [58] K. Gulda *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **703**, (2002), pp. 45.
- [59] M. Würkner *et al.* *Nucl. Phys. A*, **725**, (2003), pp. 3.
- [60] L. González, R. Gaeta, E. Vaño, and J. Los Arcos. *Nucl. Phys. A*, **324**, (1979), pp. 126.

- [61] P. P. McKee. *Octupole Collectivity in ^{224}U* . Ph.D. thesis, School of Computing, Engineering, and Physical Sciences, University of the West of Scotland (2018).
- [62] J. F. Smith and P. P. McKee. *Octupole Collectivity in ^{224}U - unpublished*.
- [63] P. T. Greenless *et al.* AIP Conf. Proc., **495**, (1999), pp. 133.
- [64] P. Zeyen *et al.* Z. Phys. A, **328**, (1987), pp. 399.
- [65] D. Ward *et al.* Phys. Rev. C, **86**, (2012), p. 064319.
- [66] S. Zhu *et al.* Phys. Lett. B, **618**, (2005), pp. 51.
- [67] F. McGowan and W. Milner. Nucl. Phys. A, **571**, (1994), pp. 569.
- [68] T. Ishii *et al.* Phys. Rev. C, **72**, (2005), p. 021301.
- [69] N. Brewer *et al.* Nucl. Phys. A, **1039**, (2023), p. 122738.
- [70] B. Bucher *et al.* Phys. Rev. Lett., **118**, (2017), p. 152504.
- [71] J. Skalski. Physics Letters B, **238**, (1990), pp. 6.
- [72] K. Kaneko, M. Hasegawa, and T. Mizusaki. Phys. Rev. C, **66**, (2002), p. 051306.
- [73] S. Skoda *et al.* Phys. Rev. C, **58**, (1998), pp. R5.
- [74] P. A. Butler. Proc. Roy. Soc. Lond. A, **476**, (2020), p. 20200202.
- [75] P. Butler and W. Nazarewicz. Nucl. Phys. A, **533**, (1991), pp. 249.
- [76] L. P. Gaffney. *Octupole collectivity in ^{220}Rn and ^{224}Ra* . Ph.D. thesis, Department of Physics, University of Liverpool (2012).
- [77] Y. Huang *et al.* Phys. Rev. C, **93**, (2016), p. 064321.
- [78] R. Spear. Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables, **42**, (1989), pp. 55.
- [79] W. Nazarewicz and P. Olanders. Nucl. Phys. A, **441**, (1985), pp. 420.
- [80] L. M. Robledo and G. F. Bertsch. Phys. Rev. C, **84**, (2011), p. 054302.
- [81] A. M. Hurst *et al.* Phys. Rev. C, **81**, (2010), p. 014312.
- [82] K. Abu Saleem *et al.* Phys. Rev. C, **70**, (2004), p. 024310.
- [83] I. Wiedenhöver *et al.* Phys. Rev. Lett., **83**, (1999), pp. 2143.

- [84] V. P. Guinn. In *Radioactivity: Encyclopedia of Physical Science and Technology (3rd edition.)*. Academic Press, pp. 661–674 (2003).
- [85] C. A. Bertulani and P. Danielewicz. *Introduction to nuclear reactions*. Graduate student series in physics. CRC Press (2019).
- [86] P. Fröbrich and R. Lipperheide. *Theory of Nuclear Reactions*. Oxford science publications. Oxford University Press (1996).
- [87] A. Yadav *et al.* Phys. Rev. C, **107**, (2023), p. 044605.
- [88] N. Antonenko, J. Benlliure, A. Karpov, and D. J. Morrissey. *Reactions for Production of Exotic Nuclei*. Springer Nature Singapore, Singapore, pp. 91–139 (2023).
- [89] H. Freiesleben and J. Kratz. Phys. Rep., **106**, (1984), pp. 1.
- [90] C. Bhattacharya *et al.* Phys. Rev. C, **69**, (2004), p. 024607.
- [91] L. Corradi, G. Pollarolo, and S. Szilner. J. Phys. G, **36**, (2009), p. 113101.
- [92] A. Kamal. *Nuclear Physics (1st Edition)*. Springer (2014).
- [93] S. R. Cherry, J. A. Sorenson, and M. E. Phelps. *chapter 6 - Interaction of Radiation with Matter*. In *Physics in Nuclear Medicine (4th Edition)*. W.B. Saunders, Philadelphia, pp. 63–85 (2012).
- [94] G. Knoll. *Radiation Detection and Measurement (4th ed.)*. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd., Hoboken, NJ (2010).
- [95] T. K. Alexander and J. S. Forster. *Advances in Nuclear Physics*, volume 10. Springer (1978).
- [96] G. Gilmore and D. Joss. *Practical Gamma-ray Spectrometry (3rd Edition)*. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd., Chichester, England (2024).
- [97] J. England. *Techniques in nuclear structure physics - Part 1*. The MacMillan Press, London (1974).
- [98] W. R. Leo. *Scintillation Detectors*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 157–175 (1994).
- [99] P. Regan *et al.* Journal of Physics: Conference Series, **763**, (2016), p. 012004.
- [100] B. Milbrath, A. Peurrung, M. Bliss, and W. Weber. Journal of Materials Research, **23**, (2008), p. 2561–2581.
- [101] P. Regan. Applied Radiation and Isotopes, **70**, (2012), pp. 1125.

- [102] INFN-LNL. *ALPI Webpage* (2025).
- [103] A. Facco and J. Sokolowski. Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **328**, (1993), pp. 275.
- [104] C. A. Ur. AIP Conf. Proc., **1530**, (2013), pp. 35.
- [105] P. Twin, P. Nolan, R. Aryaeinejad, D. Love, A. Nelson, and A. Kirwan. Nucl. Phys. A, **409**, (1983), pp. 343.
- [106] J. Eberth and J. Simpson. Prog. Part. Nucl. Phys., **60**, (2008), pp. 283.
- [107] I. Lee *et al.* Nucl. Phys. A, **746**, (2004), pp. 255.
- [108] P. Sangsingkeow. Hard X-Ray, Gamma-Ray, and Neutron Detector Physics, **3768**, (1999), pp. 204 .
- [109] Mirion Technologies. *Segmented Coaxial Detectors* (2025).
- [110] A. Korichi *et al.* European Physical Journal A, **59**, (2023), p. 211.
- [111] L. Lewandowski, P. Reiter, and B. e. a. Birkenbach. Eur. Phys. J. A., **55**, (2019), p. 81.
- [112] A. Lopez-Martens, K. Hauschild, A. Korichi, J. Roccaz, and J.-P. Thibaud. Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **533**, (2004), pp. 454.
- [113] T. Kroll and D. Bazzacco. Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **463**, (2001), pp. 227.
- [114] K. Vetter, M. Burks, and L. Mihailescu. Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **525**, (2004), pp. 322.
- [115] A. Korichi and T. Lauritsen. Eur. Phys. J. A., **55**, (2019), p. 121.
- [116] J. van der Marel and B. Cederwall. Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **437**, (1999), pp. 538.
- [117] A. Lopez-Martens. *AGATA Analysis Workshop: Tracking* (2023).
- [118] J. J. Valiente-Dobón. *Kinematical Coincidences of DANTE Coupled to the AGATA Demonstrator in the Multinucleon-Transfer Reaction $58\text{Ni} + 96\text{Zr}$* , LNL Annual Report (2009).
- [119] J. J. Valiente-Dobón *et al.* AIP Conf. Proc., **853**, (2006), pp. 202.
- [120] R. Lombardi, F. Galtarossa, D. M. K. Rezynekina, and A. Goasduff. *Characterization of Micro-Channel Plate Detectors for Time-of-Flight Measurements in Nuclear Physics and Astrophysics Experiments*, LNL Annual Report (2021).
- [121] A. Giaz *et al.* Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **729**, (2013), pp. 910.
- [122] A. Stefanini *et al.* Nucl. Phys. A, **701**, (2002), pp. 217.

- [123] E. Pilotto. *In-beam commissioning of the AGATA-PRISMA setup at Legnaro National Laboratories*. Masters thesis, Università degli Studi di Padova, Padova, Italy (2022).
- [124] D. Montanari *et al.* Eur. Phys. J. A, **47**, (2011), pp. 1.
- [125] G. Montagnoli *et al.* Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **547**, (2005), pp. 455.
- [126] E. Fioretto *et al.* *The Magnetic Spectrometer PRISMA at LNL*. World Scientific, pp. 79–88 (2005).
- [127] Prisma Group. *The Detectors Webpage* (2001).
- [128] Prisma Group. *The PRISMA Spectrometer Webpage* (2002).
- [129] Laboratori Nazionali di Legnaro. *Photo Gallery - Apparati Sperimentali - Prisma* (2025).
- [130] S. Beghini *et al.* Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **551**, (2005), pp. 364.
- [131] R. Brun and F. Rademakers. Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **389**, (1997), pp. 81.
- [132] D. Bazzacco *et al.* *AGATA Data Analysis User's guide for Local Level Processing* (2019).
- [133] B. Bruyneel *et al.* Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **608**, (2009), pp. 99.
- [134] B. Bruyneel *et al.* Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A, **599**, (2009), pp. 196.
- [135] M. Siciliano. *Nuclear structure of the semi-magic tin isotopes close to ^{100}Sn : lifetime measurements of low-lying states in ^{106}Sn and ^{108}Sn* . Ph.D. thesis, Università degli Studi di Padova, Padova, Italy (2018).
- [136] L. Sajo-Bohus *et al.* Nucl. Instr. Meth. Physics Res. A, **648**, (2011), pp. 132.
- [137] B. Bruyneel *et al.* Eur. Phys. J. A, **49**, (2013), p. 61.
- [138] R. Perez-Vidal. *AGATA Analysis Workshop 2025 PostPSA Calibration* (2025).
- [139] F. G. T. Mijatovic, A. Goasduff. *PrismaFilters: PRISMA Data Analysis Guide* (2022).
- [140] R. G. McClarren. *Computational Nuclear Engineering and Radiological Science Using Python*. Academic Press, Elsevier Inc (2018).
- [141] A. B. Brown, C. W. Snyder, W. A. Fowler, and C. C. Lauritsen. Phys. Rev., **82**, (1951), pp. 159.
- [142] A. Winther. *GRAZING_9: A Fortran Program for Estimating Reactions in Collision between Heavy Nuclei* (2002).

- [143] J. F. Smith *et al.* *Octupole correlations in the neutron-deficient plutonium isotopes*. Proposal to Legnaro National Laboratory (2022).
- [144] M. Asai *et al.* The European Physical Journal A - Hadrons and Nuclei, **23**, (2005), pp. 395.
- [145] X. Wang. *Exotic Collective Excitations at High Spin: Triaxial Rotation and Octupole Condensation*. Ph.D. thesis, University of Notre Dame (2007).
- [146] X. Wang *et al.* Phys. Rev. Lett., **102**, (2009), p. 122501.
- [147] *Evaluated Nuclear Structure Data File (ENSDF)*. <https://www.nndc.bnl.gov/ensdf/>. Accessed: 11 August 2025.
- [148] T. Kibedi, T. Burrows, M. Trzhaskovskaya, P. Davidson, and J. C.W. Nestor. Nucl. Instr. Meth. A, **589**, (2008), pp. 202.
- [149] D. C. Radford. *RadWare: Data analysis tools for γ -ray spectroscopy*.
- [150] C. Sullivan *et al.* *Benchmarking 1π AGATA in Standalone and Coupled Configurations with EUCLIDES: Exploring the Present Limits of High- γ -Multiplicity Experiments*. Proposal to Legnaro National Laboratory (2025).